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Working Group on Stock Assessment of Demersal Species (WGSAD)

Rome, Italy, 12–17 December 2022

Report

Executive summary

The Working Group on Stock Assessment of Demersal Species (WGSAD)¹ was held in Rome, Italy, in hybrid modality, from 12 to 17 December 2022. The main objectives of the meeting were to: i) review the consistency of procedures to provide advice; ii) review the assessment of demersal stocks; and iii) run a hands-on data session to deal with methodological issues. Out of the 62 assessments presented, 60 were validated. Some of the assessments were accomplished within the framework of the relevant working groups of the Scientific, Technical and Economic Committee for Fisheries (STECF) of the European Commission. Only eight out of the 60 validated assessments adopted during the WGSAD indicated sustainable stock exploitation. Four of them referred to red mullet (*Mullus barbatus*) stocks, while three concerned stocks of crustacean species: blue and red shrimp (*Aristeus antennatus*), Norway lobster (*Nephrops norvegicus*) and spottail mantis shrimp (*Squilla mantis*). In addition, a thornback ray (*Raja clavata*) stock was considered likely to be under sustainable exploitation whereas four stocks were found to be overexploited but with low fishing mortality levels.

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Opening of the Working Group on Stock Assessment of Demersal Species

1. Due to travel limitations resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic the tasks of the Working Group on Stock Assessment of Demersal Species (WGSAD) were accomplished by means of a hybrid meeting held in Rome on 12 – 17 December 2022 with several participants following online. It was attended by a total of 111 participants from 17 Mediterranean riparian countries as well as from the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), the Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries of the European Commission (DG MARE) and the Secretariat of the General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean (GFCM).
2. Mr George Tserpes, as WGSAD Coordinator, acted as Chairperson. The meeting agenda is provided in Appendix 1 and the combined list of participants is provided in Appendix 2.
3. The WGSAD performed an appraisal of Mediterranean stock assessments for GFCM priority and non-priority species, as summarized below and in the table of advice provided in Appendix 3.
4. All stock assessment forms presented and finalized during the WG meeting as well as the respective STAR Excel Templates are available on the GFCM SharePoint page of the Expert Groups (<https://gfcml.sharepoint.com/EG>). Following the recommendations made at the 23rd session of the SAC, these will be made public on the GFCM webpage in advance of the subregional committees and will be validated by the SAC at its twenty-fourth session.

Status of priority stocks

European Hake (*Merluccius merluccius*)

5. During the session on European hake, assessments covering 21 geographical subareas (GSAs) were presented. In all cases, the stocks were estimated to be in overexploitation and reduction of fishing mortality was recommended. Relative biomass levels showed varying levels, while in two cases the stocks were considered as depleted. Further details are provided below.
6. An updated joint assessment for GSAs 1, 5, 6 and 7 was presented, using the assessment for all (a4a) method. The assessment formed the basis of advice for these areas. Results indicated that the stock is in overexploitation and depleted. Complementary advice was provided by separate assessments accomplished in GSAs 1, 5, and 6 by means of extended survivor analysis (XSA) for GSA 1 and a4a for GSAs 5 and 6. All separate assessments indicated the presence of overexploitation, in line with the joint one.
7. An assessment in GSA 1 was presented using two different modeling approaches (a4a and XSA) indicating the presence of overexploitation. The WGSAD decided to provide complementary advice based on the XSA model strengthened by the fact that its results were fully corroborated by the a4a model. The WGSAD agreed that in the coming year there should be a move towards a statistical catch at age approach with a full exploration of the a4a model, including full diagnostics and testing the impact of changes in the number of knots (k) in the submodels.
8. Hake in GSA 3 was assessed for the first time on its own, based on the results of the Transboran project that showed no connectivity between hake stocks in GSA 1 and GSA 3, as it was previously assumed. Results indicated that the stock is in overexploitation with relatively low biomass.
9. An updated assessment for GSA 4 was presented using pseudo-cohort analysis (VIT). Results indicated that the stock is in overexploitation.
10. An updated assessment for GSA 5 was presented using the a4a model. Results indicated that the stock is in overexploitation with relatively low biomass and the assessment was used for providing complementary advice.

11. An updated assessment with revised growth parameters was presented for GSA 6 using the a4a model. Results indicated that the stock is in overexploitation with relatively low biomass and the assessment was used for providing complementary advice.
12. The a4a update of the benchmark assessment for GSAs 8 – 11 (jointly) indicated that the stock is in overexploitation and based on the biomass reference points that were calculated, it is considered depleted. Implementation of a recovery plan was recommended.
13. An update of the benchmark joint assessment for GSAs 12 – 16 was presented. The results of SS3 model runs indicated that the stock is in overexploitation and overexploited.
14. The update of the benchmark assessment for GSAs 17–18 (jointly), using the SS3 method, indicated that the stock is under overexploitation. The assessment included a revision of the input data related to the ALK, triggering a re-estimation of reference points. The WGSAD questioned the validity of the biomass reference points, noting that Blim was extremely low. It was suggested not to include biomass reference points in the table of advice, pending a new benchmark. The WGSAD recommended a complete overhaul of the benchmark with the aim of i) revising the input data, ii) considering the use of additional historical data (e.g. historical catches and surveys), iii) revising the reference points.
15. An update of the benchmark assessment for GSA 19 was presented including a submodel revision of the a4a model used. Results indicated that the stock is in overexploitation with relatively high biomass.
16. An updated assessment for GSA 20 was presented, using a4a. Results indicated that the stock is in overexploitation, with relatively intermediate biomass. Another assessment providing similar results was also presented, but it was deemed to be based on a rather questionable reconstruction of the historical catch series.
17. A new assessment for GSAs 22-23 (jointly) was presented using a4a. Results indicated that the stock is in overexploitation, with relatively intermediate biomass. An assessment for GSA 22 alone that was also presented showed similar results, but it was deemed to be based on a reconstruction of the historical catch series that should be further investigated.

Deep-water rose shrimp (*Parapenaeus longirostris*)

18. During the session, assessments of deep-water rose shrimp covering 10 western and eastern Mediterranean GSAs were presented. In all cases the stocks were found to be in overexploitation or possibly in overexploitation, with mostly high relatively biomass levels. Reduction of fishing mortality was always recommended. Further details are provided below.
19. The updated assessment of GSA 1 was presented using the a4a modeling approach. Results indicated that the stock is in overexploitation with relatively high biomass.
20. A revised assessment was presented for GSA 3 and qualitative advice was provided, based for the first time on the a4a model. Results indicated that the stock is in possible overexploitation.
21. An updated assessment for GSA 4 was presented. Due to the short data series, qualitative advice was provided based on the VIT method, while the estimates were supported by LBSPR runs. Results indicated that the stock is possibly in overexploitation.
22. A revised assessment for GSA 5 was presented using the a4a approach. Results indicated that the stock is in overexploitation with relatively high biomass.
23. An updated assessment for GSA 6 was presented using the XSA method. The results indicated that the stock is in overexploitation, with relatively high biomass. During the discussion it was suggested to attempt future assessments through a statistical catch-at-age model.

24. A revised assessment for GSAs 8-11 (jointly) was presented using a4a. This included the addition of GSA 8 to the previous GSA 9-11 assessment, the adoption of a new maturity vector and the calculation of biomass reference points. Results indicated that the stock is in overexploitation with biomass above reference points.

25. A revised assessment was presented for GSA 22, including new catch data, and qualitative advice was provided, based on the a4a model. Results indicated that the stock is in possible overexploitation.

Red mullet (*Mullus barbatus*)

26. During the session, assessments of red mullet covering 16 GSAs were presented. In four GSAs (10, 11, 16, 22) the stocks were found to be sustainably exploited, while in the remaining GSAs, they were overexploited. Biomass levels were varying. For the GSAs undergoing overexploitation, reduction of fishing mortality was recommended, while for the rest it was recommended not to increase fishing mortality. Further details are provided below.

27. The updated assessment for GSA 1 using the a4a method indicated overexploitation with relatively high biomass.

28. The updated assessment for GSA 6 using the a4a method indicated overexploitation with relatively high biomass.

29. The updated assessment for GSA 7 using the a4a method indicated overexploitation with biomass being above the calculated reference points.

30. The updated assessment for GSA 9 using the a4a method indicated overexploitation with biomass being above the calculated reference points.

31. A revised assessment for GSA 10 using the SPiCT method was presented. Results indicated that the stock is under sustainable exploitation, with biomass being above reference points.

32. A new assessment was presented for GSA 11 using the XSA method. Results indicated that the stock is under sustainable exploitation, with relatively high biomass.

33. An update of the benchmark assessment was presented for GSAs 12-14 (jointly). Estimates obtained from XSA runs revealed that the stock is in overexploitation, with relatively low biomass.

34. An update of the benchmark assessment was presented for GSA 15. Estimates obtained from XSA runs revealed that the stock is in overexploitation, with relatively low biomass.

35. For GSA 16, the WGSAD reviewed the assessment based on the benchmarked model (XSA) and deemed it unsuitable for the provision of advice. An alternative model employing a4a was proposed and the WGSAD recommended its use as the current basis for advice, pending a new benchmark for the stock. Results of the a4a model suggested that the stock is under sustainable exploitation, with relatively low biomass.

36. An update of the benchmark assessment for GSA 19 was presented, using XSA. The results indicated that the stock is in overexploitation. Runs using the a4a model were also attempted but they were not considered stable enough for the provision of advice.

37. The updated assessment for GSA 20 using the a4a method indicated overexploitation with relatively high biomass.

38. A revised assessment with new sub-model settings was presented for GSA 22 using the a4a method. Results indicated that the stock is sustainably exploited, with relatively high biomass.

39. An updated assessment for GSA 24 was presented. Advice was based on CMSY and the estimates were supported by two additional methods, LBB and LBSPP and LIME. Results indicated that

the stock is overexploited but with low fishing mortality (sustainable exploitation). Thus, it was recommended not to increase fishing mortality.

40. The updated assessment for GSA 25 using the SAM method indicated overexploitation with relatively intermediate biomass.

Giant red shrimp (*Aristaeomorpha foliacea*)

41. Assessments of giant red shrimp covering 14 GSAs were presented during this session. Assessments covering 13 GSAs were validated and the stocks were estimated to be in overexploitation. Further details are provided below.

42. An updated, assessment for GSAs 9 - 11 (jointly) using the a4a method, was presented, including also estimates of biomass reference points. The stock was estimated to be in overexploitation, while the current biomass level is above the estimated reference points. The recommendation was to reduce fishing mortality.

43. A new assessment was presented for GSAs 18-20 (jointly), using a4a. Results indicated that the stock is in overexploitation and reduction of fishing mortality was recommended.

44. An updated assessment for GSAs 12-16 and 21west (jointly) was presented using the JABBA model. Results indicated that the stock is under overexploitation and overexploited. Immediate action to ensure reduction of fishing mortality was recommended.

45. An assessment for GSA 26 was presented using the LBSPR method. The results were considered preliminary as they include two years of data and the assessment was not validated.

Blue and red shrimp (*Aristeus antennatus*)

46. Assessments of blue and red shrimp covering eight GSAs were presented during this session and for seven GSAs they were validated. In all validated assessments, apart from that of GSA 1, the stocks were estimated to be in overexploitation. Further details are provided below.

47. An updated assessment for GSA 1 using a4a was presented. Results indicated that the stock is in sustainable exploitation, with relatively high biomass. The recommendation was to not increase fishing mortality.

48. A revised assessment for GSA 2 was presented employing the XSA method previously used. Results indicated that the stock is in overexploitation, with relatively high biomass. Reduction of fishing mortality was recommended.

49. An updated assessment for GSA 5 was presented using a4a. Results indicated that the stock is in overexploitation, with relatively low biomass. Reduction of fishing mortality was recommended.

50. A revised assessment, using additional data, was presented for GSA 6. It was based on the a4a method and results indicated that the stock is in overexploitation, with relatively low biomass. Reduction of fishing mortality was recommended.

51. A new assessment was presented for GSAs 18-20 (jointly), using a4a. The assessment utilized new sex-specific growth estimates that were deemed more reliable. Results indicated that the stock is in overexploitation and reduction of fishing mortality was recommended. The previous assessments had considered only GSAs 18-19 and the group noted that the addition of catches from GSA 20 had very little impact by comparison.

52. An assessment for GSA 26 was presented using the LBSPR method. The results were considered preliminary as they include two years of data and the assessment was not validated.

Blackspot seabream (*Pagellus bogaraveo*)

53. The update of benchmark assessment for blackspot seabream in the Strait of Gibraltar was presented, based on the gadget model update. Results indicated that the stock is depleted with

unsustainable exploitation and low fishing mortality. The recommendation was to proceed with immediate reduction of fishing mortality, implementing also a recovery plan. The WGSAD welcomed the work done towards standardizing the Moroccan and Spanish CPUE indexes and exploring the impacts of different standardization scenarios with JABBA and SS3, comparing them to the outputs of the gadget model. In light of a proposed discontinuation of the current Spanish CPUE index and the difficulties related to the yearly update of the Gadget model as well as the need for further exploration of data, modelling alternatives and model diagnostics, the WGSAD strongly recommended a new benchmark assessment in 2024, according to the provisions of Recommendation GFCM/45/2022/3.

Norway lobster (*Nephrops norvegicus*)

54. The WGSAD welcomed the validation of the first spatially-explicit model in the Mediterranean in an area that also includes a FRA (GSA 17). The status of the *N. norvegicus* stock is estimated to be very different in-side and outside the Jabuka/Pomo pit, with the stock outside the Pomo pit on the Italian side being in a particularly poor state. The WGSAD noted a number of issues which warned against the use of short term forecasts for the time being, to be solved before the next WGSAD, as follows

- The model estimates the proportion of total recruitment that is retained within the Pomo pits are increased from 60% in 2020 to over 90% in most recent years, which, in turn, drives the decline outside Pomo despite fishing pressure being substantially below F_{sb40} , which is used a conservative proxy for F_{msy} . In other words, the decline outside Pomo is not mediated by fishing but because a decrease of recruitment allocation outside Pomo. This may capture the true dynamics but a model miss-specification leading to spurious recruitment apportionment cannot be ruled at this stage.
- The group discussed the option to combine the MEDITS indices from ITA and CRO into a single index for the outside Pomo area to resolve apparent conflicts in the model fits.
- The one way downhill trend in SSB outside Pomo may pose challenges on making reliable short-term forecasts based on recent the low recruitment allocation <10% (e.g. average of 3 years), which would likely predict a short- to medium collapse of the outside Pomo area due to a lack of recruitment and irrespective of the management action (F or Catch). The forecasting properties of the current model should therefore be explored under both current F and current Catch scenarios. The spatial Stock Synthesis assessment of Indian Ocean yellowfin tuna could be used for reference here for developing model plausible criteria based on a “short-term forecast viability”.

Red coral (*Corallium rubrum*)

55. One update assessment and four new assessments covering four GSAs were presented during the session and all examined stocks were found to be either overexploited or possibly overexploited. Further details are provided below.

56. A new assessment for GSA 8 was presented, using the LBSPR method. Results indicated that the stock is possibly overexploited and a reduction of fishing mortality was recommended.

57. A new assessment for the northwestern waters of GSA 11 was presented, using the CMSY method. Results indicated that the stock is overexploited, while the current fishing mortality is at low levels. Reduction of fishing mortality and/or implementation of a recovery plan was recommended.

58. An update assessment for the northern waters of GSA 11 was presented, using the CMSY method. Last year the assessment was validated as qualitative, using LBSPR. Results indicated that the stock is possibly overexploited and in overexploitation. Immediate action to ensure a reduction in fishing mortality was recommended.

59. A new assessment for GSA 17 (Croatian waters) was presented, using the LBSPR method. Results indicated that the stock is possibly overexploited reduction of fishing mortality was recommended.

60. A new assessment for GSA 22 was presented, using the LBSPR method. Results indicated that the stock is possibly overexploited and reduction of fishing mortality was recommended.

Common cuttlefish (*Sepia officinalis*)

61. A revised assessment for common cuttlefish, with a new modeling approach (JABBA) was presented for GSA 17. Results indicated that the stock is in overexploitation and overexploited. Immediate action to ensure reduction of fishing mortality was recommended.

Spottail mantis shrimp (*Squilla mantis*)

62. An updated assessment for Spottail mantis shrimp in GSA 17 was presented using the SS3 model. Results indicated that the stock is sustainably exploited it was recommended to not increase fishing mortality. Nevertheless, the need for a benchmark session was underlined, towards i) re-investigating biological parameters, ii) addressing pending data issues and include more length data for pots, iii) including discards data, iv) considering a sex-separated model due to strongly different behaviour

Common sole (*Solea solea*)

63. The update of benchmark assessment for Common sole in GSA 17 was presented, using SS3. The results of the ensemble SS3 model indicated that the stock is overexploited with low fishing mortality. It was recommended to not increase fishing mortality.

Brushtooth lizardfish (*Saurida lessepsianus*)

64. A new assessment was presented for GSA 24 and qualitative advice was provided, based on the LBSPR method. Results indicated that the stock is in possible overexploitation and not to increase fishing mortality was recommended.

Assessments of non-priority stocks

Norway lobster (*Nephrops norvegicus*)

65. An updated assessment was presented for GSA 5 using the a4a method. Results indicated that the stock is sustainably exploited with relatively intermediate biomass levels. The recommendation was not to increase fishing mortality.

66. An updated assessment for GSA 6 was presented using a4a. The results of the model indicated that the stock is in overexploitation, with relatively low biomass and reduction of fishing mortality was recommended.

67. An updated assessment for GSA 9 was presented using a4a. Results indicated that the stock is in overexploitation and overexploited. It was recommended to decrease fishing mortality.

Deep water rose shrimp (*Parapenaeus longirostris*)

68. A revised assessment was presented for GSA 22 and qualitative advice was provided, based on the a4a model. Results indicated that the stock is in possible overexploitation and reduction of fishing mortality was recommended.

Horned octopus (*Eledone chirrhosa*)

69. A revised assessment for GSA 18, was presented using CMSY – BSM. Results indicated that the stock is overexploited, while the current fishing mortality is at low levels. Reduction of fishing mortality and/or implementation of a recovery plan was recommended.

Striped red mullet (*Mullus surmuletus*)

70. An updated assessment for GSA 5 was presented using the a4a model. Results indicated that the stock is in overexploitation, with relatively intermediate biomass. Reduction of fishing mortality was recommended.

Blackbellied angler (*Lophius budegassa*)

71. A new assessment was presented for GSA 7 and qualitative advice was provided, based on the a4a model. Results indicated that the stock is in possible overexploitation and reduction of fishing mortality was recommended.

Thornback ray (*Raja clavata*)

72. A new assessment for GSA 25, was presented and qualitative advice was provided, based on the AMSY method. Results indicated that the stock is possibly under sustainable exploitation and to not increase fishing mortality was recommended.

Goldband goatfish (*Upeneus moluccensis*)

73. A new assessment was presented for GSA 27 and qualitative advice was provided, based on the VIT model. Results indicated that the stock is in possible overexploitation and reduction of fishing mortality was recommended.

Summary on the status of demersal stocks in 2021

74. Out of the 62 assessments presented, 60 were validated; 51 were accepted providing quantitative advice, while 9 were considered as qualitative. Some of the assessments were accomplished in the frame of relevant STECF working groups. Of the 60 validated assessments, eight indicated sustainable exploitation, while in four additional cases the stocks were found to be overexploited but with low fishing mortality. Four of the assessments indicating sustainable exploitation were referring to various red mullet stocks.

75. As in previous years, the WGSAD recognized that European hake was the demersal species suffering from the highest fishing mortality and all stocks were under overexploitation. Other commonly exploited fish stocks, such as those of red mullet, are generally in a better situation and although they are in overexploitation in the majority of the cases, their biomass is mostly at relatively high levels.

76. During the sessions on stock assessment, general aspects related to the assessments carried out were reviewed, including methods and data used, stock status and a summary of the resulting scientific advice. In some cases, new analyses were carried out. Comments by the WGSAD on each stock assessment are summarized in the table included in Appendix 3. Creation of the table was facilitated by the STAR template, which has automated the process. Individual stock assessment summaries are available in this report and all SAFs are available on the GFCM SharePoint page of the Expert Groups (<https://gfcml.sharepoint.com/EG>) and will be published online in advance of the subregional committees (SRCs) and will be finally validated by the 24th session of the Scientific Advisory Committee for Fisheries (SAC) in 2023.

77. Out of the 60 validated assessments, 48 were carried out within a single GSA and 12 assessments spanned over several GSAs. With reference to the GFCM sub-regions, 33 assessments were carried out in the western Mediterranean, nine in the eastern Mediterranean and 18 covered GSAs of the central Mediterranean and the Adriatic Sea.

78. As in previous years, in the absence of reference points based on biomass, the WGSAD used the empirical reference framework for the relative level of stock biomass referred to the 33rd and 66th percentile, as agreed at the WGSAD 2012 meeting and as collected in the SAF template approved by the sixteenth session of the SAC (Malta, 2014). It should be noted, however, that biomass reference

points (Bpa and Blim) were estimated this year for several stocks, particularly of the western Mediterranean.

79. A full description of input data, parameters and assumptions for stock assessment were included in the SAFs and the STAR templates. Participants were also reminded that they should provide the GFCM Secretariat with raw input data and with the scripts run to perform the assessments (if any). To facilitate data transmission, an input and raw data folder was made available on the SharePoint. In this respect, the use of the SharePoint for the sixth consecutive year had proved to be very useful for exchanging information between participants and the working group coordinator.

Assessment methods

80. With regards to the methodology used, the majority (48) of the assessments utilized age-based methods or integrated approaches, while the remaining ones were based on production models and various data-poor approaches. It should be noted that in several cases more than one approach was tested. The WGSAD welcomed the advancement of methodologies used to assess Mediterranean stocks in the direction indicated by previous WGSAs. Thus, the proportion of stocks assessed using statistical catch-at-age methods or integrated analysis (e.g a4a, SAM, SS3) was around to 65%.

81. As in the previous year, the WGSAD discussed the use of abundance indices from the traditional trawl surveys, for tuning age-based models for certain crustacean stocks, such as those of Norway lobster. Given that such species may be inadequately sampled by those surveys, it was suggested to explore the use of commercial CPUE indexes, as well as the possibility of developing specific fishery independent surveys in the future.

Assessment summary sheets

SUMMARY OF ACCEPTED STOCK ASSESSMENTS BY SPECIES AND GSA

(Progressive numbers refer to the table of advice provided in Appendix 3).

N: 1

Stock: Blue and red shrimp (*Aristeus antennatus*)

GSA: 1

Author(s): Pérez Gil, J.L., Meléndez, M.J., González, M., Serna-Quintero, J.M, García, C., Torres, P., Hidalgo, L., Herrera, J., Acosta, J. and Ciercoles, C.

Fishery: Blue and red shrimp (*Aristeus antennatus*) is the most important resource of slope bottom trawling in the GSA1 (Northern Alboran Sea) and is targeted by the largest vessels of the deep water trawl fleet segment. The bottom otter trawl fleet catch red shrimp on the slope on muddy bottoms between depths of 400 to 800 m. A total of 35 vessels (2021) had fishing activities directed towards the pink shrimp in the GSA 1 fishing ground. This segment fleet, catches about 119 tonnes of red shrimp per year (average 2019-2021), 86 tons in 2021.

Data and parameters: The assessment was carried out using official landings and data on the size composition of otter bottom trawl catches for the years 2002-2021. Catch-at-length data were converted into catch-at-age data by cohort slicing procedures (R software). Length-weight relationship and maturity ogive comes from Spanish DCF and Natural mortality vector was estimated using PRODBIOM (Abella *et al.*, 1997).

Assessment method: The state of exploitation of this stock was assessed using (SCAA) stock assessment model (a4a) (Jardim and Millar, 2014). The assessment was performed using abundance index series from MEDITS trawl surveys. Yield-per-Recruit (Y/R) analyses was conducted based on the exploitation pattern resulting from a4a model and population parameters.

Model performance: Sensitivity and retrospective analyses were applied in the a4a models in order to check the robustness of the assessment. The final model considered for the update assessment and to provide the final outputs of the assessment was a4a.

Results: Recruitment, declined until 2007 and have been relatively stable over the 2008-2015 period, decreasing in the last years. Spawning Stock Biomass showed a decreasing trend in 2015-2017 period, increasing in the last year. Fishing mortality ($F_{\text{bar } 0-2}$) with values close to 1 in the 2007-2018 period, going down to 0.39 in the last year.

F_{current} (F_{bar} ages 0-2 (2021))	0.39
F_{target} (present assessment)	0.42
$F_{\text{current}}/F_{\text{target}}$	0.92
SSB_{current} (2020)(tonnes)	322
SSB 33% percentile biomass(tonnes)	235
SSB 66% percentile biomass(tonnes)	291

Diagnosis of stock status: Sustainable exploitation. ($F_{\text{current}} < F_{0.1}$) is above 1.66 with relatively high biomass (SSB higher than the 6th percentile).

Advice and recommendation: Not to increase fishing mortality

Figure 1. Comparison of the outputs of the previous year assessment (red line 2020, green line 2021) and update assessment performed this year (blue line).

N: 2

Stock: Blue and red shrimp (*Aristeus antennatus*)

GSA: 2

Author(s): Pérez Gil, J.L, Meléndez, M.J., González, M., Serna-Quintero, J.M, García, C., Torres, P., Hidalgo, L., Herrera, J., Acosta, J. and Círcoles, C.

Fishery: Blue and red shrimp (*Aristeus antennatus*) is the most important resource of slope bottom trawling in the GSA 2 (Alboran Island) and is targeted by the largest vessels of the deep water otter bottom trawl fleet segment. In GSA 2, bottom trawl operates, mainly in the middle slope, targeting blue and red shrimp. In this area, fishing trips last for 4-8 days, in contrast of the rest of the Western

Mediterranean, where fishing trips for trawlers only last for a single day. The main base port of this fleet is Almería (42 tons landed in 2021), and the fishing activity period goes from May to October.

A total of 17 vessels (average 2019-2021) had fishing activities directed towards the blue and red shrimp in the GSA 2 fishing ground. This segment fleet catches yearly about 54 tons of this species per year (average 2019-2021), 48 tons in 2021.

Data and parameters: The assessment was carried out using official landings and data on the size composition of trawl catches for the years 2009-2021. Catch-at-length data were converted into catch-at-age data by cohort slicing by sex procedures. Length-weight relationship and maturity ogive comes from Spanish DCF and Natural mortality vector was estimated using PRODBIOM (Abella *et al.*, 1997).

Assessment method: The state of exploitation of this stock was assessed by means of VPA Extended Survivor Analysis (XSA) (Shepherd, 1999). The assessment was performed using abundance index series from MEDITS trawl surveys. Yield-per-Recruit (Y/R) analyses was conducted based on the exploitation pattern resulting from XSA model and population parameters.

Model performance: Sensitivity and retrospective analyses were applied in the XSA model in order to check the robustness of the assessment. This assessment is based on the assessment done in 2020,

Results: Recruit_m(R), declined until 2014 and decreasing over the 2017-2020 period. Spawning Stock Biomass (SSB) remain stabilized from 2013. Fishing mortality ($F_{\text{bar } 1-3}$) is stabilized around values close to 0.5 in the 2014-2020 period. Decrease trend in the last year is observed.

F_{current} (F_{bar} ages 1-3 (2019-2021))	0.62
F_{target} (present assessment)	0.41
$F_{\text{current}}/F_{\text{target}}$	1.51
SSB ₍₂₀₁₉₋₂₀₂₁₎ tonnes	217
SSB 33% percentile biomass (tonnes)	159
SSB 66% percentile biomass (tonnes)	183

Diagnosis of stock status: The stock is in overexploitation, with relatively high biomass.

Advice and recommendation:

- Reduce F_{current} towards $F_{0.1}$
- Progressive reduction of the fishing effort

Figure 2. Comparison of the outputs of the previous year assessment (red line) and update assessment performed this year (blue line).

N: 3

Stock: Blue and red shrimp (*Aristeus antennatus*)

GSA: 5 – Balearic Islands

Author(s): Beatriz Guijarro, Núria Zaragoza and Marc Farré

Fishery: In the Balearic Islands, commercial bottom trawlers develop up to four different fishing tactics, which are associated with the shallow shelf, deep shelf, upper slope and middle slope, mainly targeted to: (i) *Spicara smaris*, *Mullus surmuletus*, *Octopus vulgaris* and a mixed fish category on the shallow shelf (50-80 m); (ii) *Merluccius merluccius*, *Mullus* spp., *Zeus faber* and a mixed fish category on the deep shelf (80-250 m); (iii) *Nephrops norvegicus*, but with an important by-catch of big *Merluccius merluccius*, *Lepidorhombus* spp., *Lophius* spp. and *Micromesistius poutassou* on the upper slope (350-600 m) and (iv) *Aristeus antennatus* on the middle slope (600-750 m). *A. antennatus* is a target species with a high economic importance.

Data and parameters: Size composition of commercial trawl catches and official landings (1992-2021), indexes from bottom trawl surveys (2001-2021). Growth parameters, length-weight relationship and maturity ogive obtained in the study area (Carbonell *et al.*, 1999, DCF data). Length was transformed to age by sex and the combined results were used for the assessment.

Assessment method: Statistical Catch-At-Age SCAA (a4a, FLR libraries) and Yield per Recruit (Y/R, FLRBRP package).

Model performance: Model residuals did not show any trend. Overall diagnostics are acceptable and retrospective analysis is consistent.

Results: Recruitment showed oscillations along the data series, with an decreasing trend for since 2017 and an increase for the last year. SSB also showed a decreasing trend, with the lowest values in the last five years. F values showed an increase in the last year.

$F_{\text{current}}(2021, \text{ages } 1-3)$	1.47
$F_{0.1}(2020)$	0.33
$F_{\text{current}}/F_{0.1}$	4.45

Current SSB (tons)	102
33 th percentile biomass (tons)	217
66 th percentile biomass (tons)	334

Diagnosis of stock status: In overexploitation, with relatively low biomass.

Advice and recommendation: To reduce fishing mortality

Figure 3. Comparison of the outputs of the previous year assessment (red line) and updated assessment performed this year (green line) for *A. antennatus* in GSA 5. The blue line represents the real catches.

N: 4

Stock: Deep water red shrimp (*Aristeus antennatus*)

GSA: 6

Author(s): Antonio Esteban, Encarnación García, Miguel Vivas, Amina Tifoura & Jose Luis Perez Gil.

Fishery: Trawl fleets fishing effort in the ports were quite stable for the period studied with small variations of the number of vessels in the recent years. Vessels length was between 12-24 m. The gears used corresponded to a trawl net 60 and 100 longest rope. The vertical opening was between 1-3 m. The cod end mesh size used was a squared 40 mm of mesh opening. The net was rigged two doors between 500-800 kgs. Trawl fleet in the four ports do daily trips with a unique haul directed to the red shrimp, with a duration between 5-7 hours. The number of harbours with red shrimp fleets is 31 for the whole area, and the number of boats in this area is 191. Discards of the red shrimp are null.

In 2021, landings were around 416 tonnes and total effort over 12252 fishing days by year and CPUE medium, 34.0 kgs/day

Data and parameters: Size composition of commercial trawl catches by sex, official landings and data from MEDITS surveys (1996-2021).

Growth parameters from L/W and Age/L relationships from Data Collection Framework (2013-15). M vector from ProdBiom (Abella et al, 1997)

Assessment method: Statistical catch-at-age – SCAA (a4a, FLR libraries), FLBRP package for yield-per-recruit analysis and Flash package for short-term forecast.

Model performance: Log catchability residuals and Retrospective analysis suggest that the model is consistent.

Results: Stock biomass showed oscillations for the entire data series, with a general decreasing trend. Also recruitment is decreasing, F increase last year with fluctuation along the time series studied.

$F_{current} (F_{bar\ 1-2})$ 2021	1.67±0.24
$F_{0.1}$ (2021)	0.34
$F_{current}/F_{0.1}$	4.91
Current SSB (tonnes) 2021	236.78±49.5
33 rd percentile SSB (tonnes)	318
66 th percentile SSB (tonnes)	421

Diagnosis of stock status: In overexploitation, with relatively low biomass.

Advice and recommendations:

- Reduce $F_{current}$ towards $F_{0.1}$
- Reduction of fishing effort.

Figure 4. Comparison of the outputs of the previous year assessment (red line) and revised assessment performed this year (blue line).

N: 5

Stock: Blue and red shrimp (*Aristeus Antennatus*)

GSA: 18-19-20

Author(s): STECF 22-16

Fishery: Blue and red shrimp is among the main target stocks for the demersal deep-water fishery in the Western and Central Mediterranean Mediterranean and of great economic interest (Kapisir *et al.*, 2022). It is harvested by bottom trawlers on the slope, commonly at depths ranging from 400 to 800 m. Over the last decades, the red shrimp fishing fleets have expanded their operations to various areas of the E. Mediterranean (Mitilineou, 2007, Vitale *et al.*, 2018). The blue and red shrimp, although less abundant in the Eastern Mediterranean, is an important commercially targeted species

(Kapiris *et al.*, 2022). The catches of the species have increased in recent years with an increasing exploitation ratio at Mediterranean level (FAO, 2020).

Data and parameters: Landings data for blue and red shrimp in GSAs 18, 19 and 20 were retrieved from the DCF 2022 data call for year 2021, while data before 2021 were retrieved from 2021 data call. The quality of the data has been checked for this stock in STECF 22-03 (STECF, 2022). Since STECF 22-03, the growth parameters have been updated and the VBGF parameters reported differ by sex, allowing a sex separated age slicing. In GSA 20, the species is not fished by the Greek fleets, hence there are no historical records of landings, except for year 2021 when landings of 10.10 tonnes were reported. Following STECF 22-03 recommendation, only LFDs from GSA 19 were used to inform the assessment (STECF, 2022). In effect, landings data from GSA 18 (ITA) and GSA 20 (GRC) add to the total catch and scale the LFDs during the SoP (sum of products) correction. All biological parameters for this species (growth curve, length-weight relationship, maturity, etc.) were informed from GSA 19 data.

Assessment method: The assessment was performed using the statistical catch-at-age model, a4a (Jardim *et al.*, 2015).

Model performance: Commercial catches and MEDITS survey index distributions showed poor internal consistency, which was slightly improved when the first years of the time series (2003-2007) were removed. The assessment could not capture the distribution of age0 of the index, while residual patterns were slightly improved when age0 was removed from both index and catch distributions. Overall, the model could not adequately capture the trends of the observed catch time series and the retrospective analysis showed uncertainty in fishing mortality.

Results: All fits showed consistent stock status in term of $F/F_{0.1}$ (F/F_{msy} proxy) indicating overexploitation of the stock. Overall the assessment was considered to be substantially improved with respect to the previous one (carried out during GFCM week of the deep-water red shrimps in Eastern and Central Med), and hence it was accepted as basis for advice.

$F_{current}$ (F_{bar} ages 1-3 (2021))	0.912
F_{target} (present assessment)	0.206
$F_{current}/F_{target}$	4.427
$SSB_{current(year)}$ (tonnes)	201.1
SSB 33% percentile biomass (tonnes)	273
SSB 66% percentile biomass(tonnes)	388

Diagnosis of stock status: In overexploitation

Advice and recommendations: Reduce fishing mortality

Comparative plot: New assessment. In February 2022 (GFCM week of the deep-water red shrimps in Eastern and Central Med) a first XSA assessment for ARA GSA 18-19, sex combined, was presented and validated for qualitative advice. However, since then, sex separated growth parameters for this stock became available (in GFCM DCRF data call), allowing a sex separated age slicing. For this reason the current assessment is regarded to be an improvement over this previous one. In addition this includes GSA 20, hence is considered to be a new assessment.

N: 6

Stock: Giant red shrimp (*Aristaeomorpha foliacea*)

GSA: 09, 10, 11

Author(s): STECF EWG 22-09.

Fishery: In the Mediterranean, *Aristaeomorpha foliacea* (Risso, 1827) is a dominant species of bathyal megafaunal assemblages, and it is sympatric with *Aristeus antennatus*. Both species have considerable interest for fisheries.

The giant red shrimp is mainly found in the epibathyal and mesobathyal waters of the Mediterranean. Due to a lack of enough information about the structure of giant red shrimp in the western Mediterranean, this stock was assumed to be confined within the GSAs 9, 10 and 11 boundaries.

Seasonal fluctuations are a proper characteristic of the landings of this species. The highest catch rates are observed in late spring-summer; even though peaks due to recruitment and other biological aspects do exist, the main factor affecting this seasonal pattern is the spatial distribution of the fishing effort. In fact, the fishing grounds where the giant red shrimp is targeted are distant from the coast, thus this fishery is strongly influenced by the weather conditions (Sartor et al., 2003; Sbrana et al., 2003).

Data and parameters: Size composition of commercial trawl catches and official landings (2005-2021), Medits survey indices (2005-2021). Growth parameters and maturity ogive were gathered from the Italian National Data Collection Programme, while the M vector was estimated using the Chen and Watanabe model.

Assessment method: Statistical Catch-At-Age, SCAA (a4a, FLR libraries), FLBRP package for yield per recruit analysis and Flash package for short-term forecast. The FLRef package was used to estimate the biomass reference points for this stock.

Model performance: Model residuals did not show any significant trend. Overall diagnostics are acceptable, and retrospective analysis is consistent.

Results: Since 2018 a gradual decrease in spawning stock biomass is observed while recruitment resulted constant. F is steadily increasing.

F_{current} ($F_{\text{bar } 1-3}$ in 2021)	0.767
$F_{0.1}$ (present assessment)	0.426
$F_{\text{current}}/F_{0.1}$	1.800
SSB_{current} (tons)	466.27
B_{MSY}	762.43
B_{pa}	381.21
B_{lim}	190.61

Diagnosis of stock status: In overexploitation, with biomass above B_{pa} .

Advice and recommendation:

- Reduce F_{current} towards $F_{0.1}$
- Progressive reduction of the fishing effort

Figure 5. Comparison of the outputs of the previous year assessments (blue line ref year 2019, green line ref year 2020) and updated assessment performed this year (red line, ref year 2021).

N: 7

Stock: Giant Red Shrimp (*Aristaeomorpha foliacea*)

GSA: 12-16, 21w (Western Sector)

Author(s): Danilo Scannella, Othman Jarboui, Olfa Ben Hadj Hamida Ben Abdallah, Jurgen Mifsud, Fabio Falsone, Okbi Rejeibi, Miriam Gambin, Vita Gancitano, Kelly Camilleri, Sergio Vitale, Luca Ceriola, Fabio Fiorentino

Fishery: Giant Red Shrimp, *Aristaeomorpha foliacea* (ARS), is an important species for commercial deep water demersal fisheries in the South-central Mediterranean Sea. It is fished exclusively by bottom trawling on deep fishing grounds ranging mainly from 400 to 650 meters. In the South-central Mediterranean Sea, Giant Red Shrimp is fished mainly by 3 fishing fleets: Italian, Tunisian and Maltese trawlers. Tunisia and Malta fleets operated exclusively in the South-central Mediterranean. Italian fleets operate generally throughout the central and eastern Mediterranean. The exploitation of Giant Red Shrimp by Italian trawlers started between the seventies and the beginning of eighties. The commercial landings of the Italian fleet were reconstructed from 1983 (when the stock was nearly unexploited) to 2003 using data provided by various Italian statistical institutes (ISTAT and IREPA). In these years the landings for the two red shrimps, *A. foliacea* and *A. antennatus*, were jointly reported. To estimate the catch of each species, it was necessary to calculate a ratio estimator, as the ratio of ARS catches to the total one of the two species. To this extent, Medits and Commercial data of ARS were used. Afterwards, the ratio estimator was applied to the total catches to obtain the ARS catches. To reconstruct catches in the missing years (1984-1987 and 1996-2000) a simple backcasting-interpolation approach by means JARA (Just Another Red list Assessment) tool was used. Since 2004, the Italian fleet started to move from traditional fishing grounds in the Strait of Sicily to initiate exploiting fishing grounds in the central and eastern Mediterranean and landing either in GSA 16 or in other eastern Mediterranean GSAs. Therefore, official landings in GSA 16 before 2019, collected within

the European DCRF/DCF, included the yield deriving both from the central and eastern Mediterranean basin.

To obtain the fraction of Italian landings deriving from the south-central Mediterranean only in the period from 2004 to 2018, two approaches were followed.

The yield from the eastern Mediterranean was estimated and subtracted from the total landings. The eastern Mediterranean landings were estimated using three different data sources: official data of the trawl fleet registered in GSA16, LEK (Local Ecological Knowledge) and logbooks of Mazara del Vallo’s captains specialized in Deep Water Red Shrimp fisheries.

Since 2019, catch data submitted by Italy within the GFCM Data Collection Reference Framework (DCRF) are provided by fleet segment and GSA of origin, therefore, a "ratio estimator" (equal to 0.6), as a ratio between the total central landings out of the total Italian landings was calculated. This ratio estimator was applied to the Italian total landings in order to go backwards in time up to 2004 for estimating the central landings, assuming the same fishing pattern through the years. From 2019 to 2021, official DCRF were used to obtain the Italian landings deriving exclusively from the south-central Mediterranean (GSAs 12-16, 21w). At the end of the process, four landing time series were reconstructed and maintained for stock assessment considering each one as a different scenario. Mean annual landings for 2019-2021 was 757 t, 46 t and 38 t from Italian, Tunisian and Maltese trawlers, respectively.

Data and parameters: Landing data (in tons) used for the stock assessment are reported in the following table:

	1983	1984	1985	1986	1987	1988	1989	1990	1991	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003
ITAC1+TUN+MLT	277	421	535	675	872	1248	1345	1311	1080	1177	800	826	985	930	928	933	935	935	943	955	887
ITAC2+TUN+MLT	249	368	473	608	787	1123	1210	1180	972	1059	720	743	887	854	836	848	851	846	849	859	798
ITAC3+TUN+MLT	277	368	477	619	808	1248	1345	1311	1080	1177	800	826	985	941	932	919	909	902	943	955	887
ITAC4+TUN+MLT	249	330	429	558	730	1123	1210	1180	972	1059	720	743	887	850	844	835	829	825	849	859	798

	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
	568	918	1059	1148	938	1416	1435	1361	1485	1628	975	1031	1105	1129	1260	842	729	913
	568	918	1059	1148	938	1416	1435	1361	1485	1628	975	1031	1105	1129	1260	842	729	913
	472	762	884	959	783	1018	1028	980	1069	1169	819	866	928	894	1008	842	729	913
	472	762	884	959	783	1018	1028	980	1069	1169	819	866	928	894	1008	842	729	913

Stock abundance indices were derived from the MEDITS survey (Mediterranean International Trawl Survey) carried out in GSA 16 and 15 and from GRUND (GRUppo Nazionale Demersali) survey carried out in the northern sector of the Strait of Sicily. Biomass index data are available for 1985-'86, 1990-'92, and 1994 -2008 for GRUND survey, and from 1994 to 2006 for MEDITS surveys. For assessment purposes, a joint Biomass index was calculated by combining all available surveys into a single time series by using JARA tools.

Assessment method: The assessment was performed through a Surplus Production Models: JABBA. The model required two “priors”, the intrinsic rate of the population increase "r" and a parameter that describes the state of the stock in terms of biomass on carrying capacity (B/K) at the beginning of the time series. Prior "r" was set as moderately high with a mean of 0.7 and a large CV of 0.3 (range 0.23-1.5). Priors B/K were chosen driven by expert knowledge and set equal to 0.7 with a CV of 0.15 (and 0.3), indicating relatively high biomass levels at the beginning of the time series. Catch error was set equal to 0.2 and 0.3 (CV) to take into account the uncertainties related to the reconstruction of catches of the Italian fleet.

Results: Several trials were carried out by varying the model settings and landing time series (5 different settings for 4 catch scenarios). The outputs of all trials performed indicated that the ARS stock is in overexploitation ($F/F_{msy}>1$) and overfished ($B/B_{MSY}<1$). An ensemble modelling approach was used to present final results (Figure 1) based on alternative configuration of the JABBA model). The main results in terms of stock status were: $B/B_{MSY}=0.59$, $F/F_{MSY}=1.53$, $MSY=1,002\ t \pm 94\ t$.

Diagnosis of stock status: Taking into account the final results of the models, Giant Red Shrimp in GSA 12-16, 21w is in overexploitation and overexploited.

Advice and recommendation: The WGSAD validated the stock assessment of Giant Red Shrimp in GSA 12-16, 21w as quantitative. It is recommended to reduce fishing mortality.

N: 8

Stock: Giant Red Shrimp (*Aristaeomorpha foliacea*)

GSA: 18, 19, 20

Author(s): STECF ewg 22-16

Fishery: The Giant red shrimp is mainly found in the epibathyal and mesobathyal waters of the Mediterranean. A specific bottom otter trawl deep water fishery (metièr code DWS) is developed to target this species. DWS is a dynamic fishery and vessels may operate far away from their home port, something spanning over different GSAs. In GSAs 18, 19 and 20 the main fleet targeting the Giant red shrimp is Italian. A modest number of catches come from the Greek fleet and a few tons were coming from the Maltese fleet. A negligible amount of landings (< 0.5% in 2021) were coming from other gears, mostly nets. Discards are virtually absent for this species. Biomass index from MEDITS survey is fluctuating but shows an increasing trend over last 15 years. Catches trend increased until 2017, then started declining.

Data and parameters: Landings for Italy (2003-2021), Greece (2014-2021); Malta (2017-2021); MEDITS survey index (2003-2021).

Data issues: in GSA 20 the survey was missing in the years 2007, 2009 – 2013, 2015 and 2017. The lack of coverage for GSA 20 was considered a relevant issue since in this area are located hauls where high abundance is usually found. GFCM noticed that maturity at age vector used by STECF ewg 22-16 was not plausible. A further data exploration reveals that oscillating pattern was due to different vectors estimated for GSAs 18 and 19. GFCM used fixed parameters from GSA 19 and updated the assessment.

Assessment method: statistical catch-at-age model a4a (Jardim *et al.*, 2014).

Model performance: model diagnostics were considered generally acceptable. The group noted that biomass increased despite a predicted increase of fishing pressure above levels above F0.1. Based on per-recruit analysis, the group observed that low fishing mortality is imposed by the SCAA model on young age classes (1 and 2), which are to a large extent sustaining the high biomass level. Stock recruitment relationship exploration also indicated that Biomass level of the stock never went below Blim. Given that a similar patterns were observed for many other shrimp stocks, some concerns were raised if F01 is a sustainable proxy for Fmsy for shrimps in the Mediterranean Sea.

Results: SSB of Giant red shrimp show an increasing trend from 2003 to 2017. Then catches started to decline steadily until 2021, while SSB was declining until 2019 and then it stabilized around 400 tons. The assessment shows a general oscillating trend in the number of recruits, especially after 2012, with recent years indicating an increasing trend. Fbar (1-3) shows a slight continuous increase until 2017 while it starts declining until 2021 where it reached a value of F of 0.828.

F_{current} (2021)	0.83
F_{01} (2021)	0.371
$F_{\text{current}}/F_{01}$	2.25
Current Total Biomass (tonnes)	1185
Current SSB (tonnes)	351
SSB_{target} (tonnes)	634
SSB_{lim} (tonnes)	158
Current SSB / SSB_{target}	0.55
Current SSB / SSB_{lim}	2.22
Catches 2021 (tonnes)	271.4

Diagnosis of stock status: In overexploitation with relatively intermediate biomass.

Advice and recommendations: Reduce fishing mortality

Figure 6. Stock trajectory estimated from a4a model by STECF EWG 22-16 (blue line) and by GFCM WGSAD (red line).

N: 9

Stock: Red coral (*Corallium rubrum*)

GSA: 8

Author(s): Bitetto I., Cau A., Bramanti L., Sacchi J., Follesa M.C.

Fishery: In this stock assessment the red coral fishery in GSA 8 has been considered in light of the high vulnerability of this species to fisheries. Currently, it is harvested only by authorized SCUBA divers, without the ROV, below 50 m of depth (Recommendation GFCM/43/2019/4).

Data and parameters: *C. rubrum* colonies harvested by fishermen in southern Corsica, under the GFCM Research programme launched in 2020, were sampled in 2021; basal diameter and height in mm were measured by observers on board for each colony. Moreover, weight was measured for each colony. Growth parameters from the assessment of red coral in Sardinian Waters were considered to estimate natural mortality: L_{inf} (basal diameter)= 45 mm; $K=0.007 \text{ years}^{-1}$; $t_0=0 \text{ years}$. A range of natural mortality methods based on life history traits (Then, Hamel, Jensen, ZM and their modifications; http://barefootecologist.com.au/shiny_m) were applied to derive an average natural mortality of 0.034. The size at first maturity was collected by Santangelo et al. (2003) and is equal to 1.85 mm. In the model a logistic curve is assumed for the selectivity of the fleet.

Assessment method: The assessment was carried out using the LBSPR method (Length Based Spawning Potential Ratio, Hordyk 2015 and 2016), developed for data-limited fisheries. This method is based on the spawning potential of the stock in terms of SPR (SSB fished population/SSB unfished population). It is an equilibrium based method, assuming that the length composition data is representative of the exploited population at steady state. It does not require knowledge of the natural mortality rate (M), but the ratio (M/K), which varies less across stocks and species than M (Prince et al. 2015).

Model performance: The LBSPR model is able to fit the 2021 LFD according to the logistic selectivity curve quite consistently among the available years.

Figure 7. Fitting of 2021 LFD by LBSPR.

Results: The results show that the fishery selects the colonies characterized by a diameter above the size at first maturity. Under the assumption of steady state, the stock spawning potential seems highly deteriorated, according to the SPR indicator. Indeed the $SPR=0.08$ is well below the reference value of 0.4 ($SPR = 40\%$, is considered risk adverse for many species (Clark, 2002)). The mature fraction of the population is practically absent in the LFD, being the population mainly represented by small individuals. This could highlight a marked overexploitation situation.

The assessment was endorsed as qualitative advice, because based on only one year of data.

Figure 7. Selectivity parameters, F/M and SPR estimated by LBSPR.

Diagnosis of stock status: Possible high overexploitation.

Advice and recommendation: It is recommended to not increase the fishing mortality.

N: 10

Stock: Red coral (*Corallium rubrum*)

GSA: 11 (NW waters)

Author(s): Bitetto I., Cau A., Carbonara P., Pesci P., Follesa M.C.

Fishery: The red coral fishery in GSA 11 is a key resource of Sardinians waters. In the past this resource was harvested through destructive harvest tools, and then by SCUBA divers with the Remote Operated Vehicle (ROV). Currently, it is harvested only by authorized SCUBA divers, without the ROV, below 50 m of depth (Recommendation GFCM/43/2019/4) and during the fishery season, mainly between May and November. The current assessment is focused on the North-Western waters fishery exploiting the resource in GSA 11.

Data and parameters: The *C. rubrum* colonies harvested by SCUBA divers were sampled in 2012, 2013, 2014 and 2015 from three ports of North-Western Sardinian waters (Alghero, Bosa and Fertilia); the basal diameter, in mm, was measured by observers on board for each colony. LFDs for 2007, 2008 and 2009 from sampling on port were included this year in the assessment. Catch data were available from 1996 to 2019 for the whole Sardinia and in several years the information is available by port. Growth parameters were estimated fitting a von Bertalanffy growth function on the age data collected according to the thin section-organic matrix staining method (Marschal et al. 2004). The growth rate was estimated by area: Northern waters (Castelsardo) and North-Western waters (Alghero). The growth parameters estimated for the North-Western waters specifically are: L_{inf} (basal diameter)= 45 mm; $K=0.007$ years⁻¹; $t_0=0$ years. A range of natural mortality methods based on life history traits (Then, Hamel, Jensen, ZM and their modifications; http://barefootecologist.com.au/shiny_m) were applied to derive an average natural mortality of 0.034. The size at first maturity was collected by Santangelo et al. (2003) and is equal to 1.85 mm. In the model a logistic curve is assumed for the selectivity of the fleet. A CPUE time series was derived as the ratio between the landing and the corresponding active licences used in the three sampled ports. A correction on autocertified data based on observer on board monitoring was also applied.

Assessment method: The assessment was carried out using the LBSPR method (Length Based Spawning Potential Ratio, Hordyk 2015 and 2016), developed for data-limited fisheries, for consistency with the last year assessment. This method is based on the spawning potential of the stock in terms of SPR (SSB fished population/SSB unfished population). It is an equilibrium based method,

assuming that the length composition data is representative of the exploited population at steady state. It does not require knowledge of the natural mortality rate (M), but the ratio (M/K), which varies less across stocks and species than M (Prince et al. 2015). In this assessment CMSY (Froese et al., 2021) was also applied in order to provide a more recent results on the stock status, taking advantage from the catch time series. CMSY is an advanced state-space Bayesian method for stock assessment that allows to estimate fisheries reference points (MSY , F_{msy} , B_{msy}), the status or relative stock size (B/B_{msy}) and the fishing pressure or exploitation (F/F_{msy}). Four scenarios were considered based on two different hypotheses on resilience and on depletion state:

Run	resilience	hypothesis on depletion
1	very low	medium-strong-strong
2	very low	medium-strong-medium
3	low	medium-strong-strong
4	low	medium-strong-medium

Model performance: The LBSPR model is able to fit the LFDs according to the logistic selectivity curve quite consistently among the available years.

Figure 8. Fitting of 2007-2015 LFDs by LBSPR

Concerning the CMSY model, the fitting of the r and K using or not the CPUE is more stable when assuming low resilience. Moreover, the fitting of the exploitation rate improves importantly using the CPUE. Among the 4 runs, the more pessimistic was selected, following a precautionary approach (run 3).

Figure 9. Retrospective analysis and residuals diagnostics by CMSY (run 3).

Results: The results show that the fishery selects the colonies characterized by a diameter above the size at first maturity. Under the assumption of steady state, met in the years when the LFDs is available (2007-2015), the stock spawning potential seems deteriorated, according to the SPR indicator. Indeed

the SPR=0.2 (average across the years) is below the reference value of 0.4 (SPR = 40%, is considered risk adverse for many species (Clark, 2002)). This could highlight an overexploitation situation.

CMSY results show that the stock is exploited below the Fmsy, while the biomass is below the reference level. This is in line with LBSPR results.

The North-western waters stock seems in a better situation in recent years in respect to Northern waters stock.

The assessment was endorsed as quantitative advice on the basis of CMSY results.

Figure 10. Selectivity parameters, F/M and SPR estimated by LBSPR.

Table 1. Selectivity parameters (SL50, SL95), F/M and SPR estimated by LBSPR.

Year	SL50	SL95	FM	SPR
2007	7.48	9.48	1.8	0.17
2008	7.52	9.55	1.82	0.17
2009	7.59	9.67	1.79	0.18
2012	7.64	9.8	1.71	0.19
2013	7.66	9.96	1.59	0.22
2014	7.7	10.18	1.49	0.24
2015	7.76	10.23	1.49	0.23
avg	7.62	9.84	1.67	0.20

Figure 11. Kobe plot summarizing the stock status as estimated by CMSY.

Table 2-Ratios F/FMSY and B/BMSY as estimated by CMSY.

F/FMSY	0.52
B/BMSY	0.37

Diagnosis of stock status: Sustainably exploited with low biomass.

Advice and recommendation: It is recommended to not increase the fishing mortality.

N: 11

Stock: Red coral (*Corallium rubrum*)

GSA: 11 (N waters)

Author(s): Bitetto I., Cau A., Carbonara P., Pesci P., Follesa M.C.

Fishery: The red coral fishery in GSA 11 is a key resource of Sardinian waters. In the past this resource was harvested through destructive harvest tools, and then by SCUBA divers with the Remote Operated Vehicle (ROV). Currently, it is harvested only by authorized SCUBA divers, without the ROV, below 50 m of depth (Recommendation GFCM/43/2019/4) and during the fishery season mainly between May and November. The current assessment is focused on the Northern waters fishery exploiting the resource in GSA 11.

Data and parameters: The *C. rubrum* colonies harvested by SCUBA divers were sampled in 2009 from four ports of Northern Sardinian waters (Golfo dell'Asinara, Castelsardo, Isola Rossa and Santa Teresa di Gallura); the basal diameter, in mm, was measured by observers on board for each colony. Catch data were available from 1996 to 2019 for the whole Sardinia and in several years the information is available by port. Growth parameters were estimated fitting a von Bertalanffy growth function on the age data collected according to the thin section-organic matrix staining method (Marschal et al. 2004). The growth parameters used to estimate natural mortality are: L_{inf} (basal diameter)= 45 mm; $K=0.007$ years⁻¹; $t_0=0$ years. A range of natural mortality methods based on life history traits (Then, Hamel, Jensen, ZM and their modifications; http://barefootecologist.com.au/shiny_m) were applied to derive an average natural mortality of 0.034. The size at first maturity was collected by Santangelo et al. (2003) and is equal to 1.85 mm. In the model a logistic curve is assumed for the selectivity of the fleet. A CPUE time series was derived as the ratio between the landing and the corresponding active licences

used in the three sampled ports. A correction on autocertified data based on observer on board monitoring was also applied.

Assessment method: The assessment was carried out using the LBSPR method (Length Based Spawning Potential Ratio, Hordyk 2015 and 2016), developed for data-limited fisheries. This method is based on the spawning potential of the stock in terms of SPR (SSB fished population/SSB unfished population). It is an equilibrium based method, assuming that the length composition data is representative of the exploited population at steady state. It does not require knowledge of the natural mortality rate (M), but the ratio (M/K), which varies less across stocks and species than M (Prince et al. 2015). In this assessment CMSY (Froese et al., 2021) was also applied in order to provide a more recent results on the stock status, taking advantage from the catch time series. CMSY is an advanced state-space Bayesian method for stock assessment that allows to estimate fisheries reference points (MSY , F_{msy} , B_{msy}), the status or relative stock size (B/B_{msy}) and the fishing pressure or exploitation (F/F_{msy}). Four scenarios were considered based on two different hypotheses on resilience and on depletion state:

Run	resilience	hypothesis on depletion
1	very low	medium-strong-strong
2	very low	medium-strong-medium
3	low	medium-strong-strong
4	low	medium-strong-medium

Model performance: The LBSPR model is able to fit the 2009 LFD according to the logistic selectivity curve quite consistently among the available years.

Figure 12. Fitting of 2009 LFD by LBSPR.

Concerning the CMSY model, the fitting of the r and K using or not the CPUE is less stable when assuming low resilience. Moreover, the fitting of the exploitation rate improves importantly using the CPUE assuming very low resilience. Among the 4 runs, the more pessimistic was selected, following a precautionary approach (run 3).

Figure 13. Retrospective analysis and residuals diagnostics by CMSY (run 3).

Results: The results show that the fishery selects the colonies characterized by a diameter above the size at first maturity. Under the assumption of steady state, the stock spawning potential seems deteriorated, according to the SPR indicator. Indeed, the $SPR=0.12$ is well below the reference value of 0.4 ($SPR = 40\%$, is considered risk adverse for many species (Clark, 2002)). This could highlight an overexploitation situation.

CMSY results show that the stock is sustainably exploited with low biomass.

The Northern waters stock seems in a worse situation in recent years in respect to North-western waters stock.

The assessment was endorsed as qualitative advice on the basis of CMSY results.

Figure 14. Selectivity parameters, F/M and SPR estimated by LBSPR.

Table 3. Selectivity parameters (SL50, SL95), F/M and SPR estimated by LBSPR.

Year	SL50	SL95	FM	SPR
2007	5.72	7.07	1.52	0.12

Figure 15. Kobe plot summarizing the stock status as estimated by CMSY.

Table 4. Ratios F/FMSY and B/BMSY as estimated by CMSY.

F/FMSY	2.34
B/BMSY	0.5

Diagnosis of stock status: Overexploited with low biomass.

Advice and recommendation: It is recommended to decrease the fishing mortality.

N: 12

Stock: Red coral (*Corallium rubrum*)

GSA: 17 (HRV)

Author(s): Bitetto I., Cau A., Bramanti L., Kružić P., Follesa M.C.

Fishery: In this stock assessment the red coral fishery in GSA 17 has been considered in light of the high vulnerability of this species to fisheries. Currently, it is harvested only by authorized SCUBA divers, without the ROV, below 50 m of depth (Recommendation GFCM/43/2019/4).

Data and parameters: *C. rubrum* colonies harvested by fishermen in Croatia, under the GFCM Research programme launched in 2020, were sampled in 2021; basal diameter and height in mm were measured by observers on board for each colony. Moreover, basal diameter and height in mm were measured on pictures taken in situ by scientists. Growth parameters from the assessment of red coral in Sardinian Waters were considered to estimate natural mortality: L_{inf} (basal diameter)= 45 mm; $K=0.007$ years⁻¹; $t_0=0$ years. A range of natural mortality methods based on life history traits (Then, Hamel, Jensen, ZM and their modifications; http://barefootecologist.com.au/shiny_m) were applied to derive an average natural mortality of 0.034. The size at first maturity was collected by Santangelo et al. (2003) and is equal to 1.85 mm. In the model a logistic curve is assumed for the selectivity of the fleet.

Assessment method: The assessment was carried out using the LBSPR method (Length Based Spawning Potential Ratio, Hordyk 2015 and 2016), developed for data-limited fisheries. This method is based on the spawning potential of the stock in terms of SPR (SSB fished population/SSB unfished population). It is an equilibrium based method, assuming that the length composition data is representative of the exploited population at steady state. It does not require knowledge of the natural mortality rate (M), but the ratio (M/K), which varies less across stocks and species than M (Prince et al. 2015).

Model performance: The LBSPR model is able to fit the 2021 LFD according to the logistic selectivity curve quite consistently among the available years.

Figure 16. Fitting of 2021 LFD by LBSPR.

Results: The results show that the fishery selects the colonies characterized by a diameter above the size at first maturity. Under the assumption of steady state, the stock spawning potential seems highly deteriorated, according to the SPR indicator. Indeed the $SPR=0.04$ is well below the reference value of 0.4 ($SPR = 40\%$, is considered risk adverse for many species (Clark, 2002)). The mature fracture of the population is practically absent in the LFD. This could highlight a marked overexploitation situation.

The assessment was endorsed as qualitative advice, because based on only one year of data.

Figure 17. Selectivity parameters, F/M and SPR estimated by LBSPR.

Diagnosis of stock status: Possible high overexploitation.

Advice and recommendation: It is recommended to not increase the fishing mortality.

N: 13

Stock: Red coral (*Corallium rubrum*)

GSA: 22

Author(s): Bitetto I., Cau A., Bramanti L., Salomidi M., Issaris Y., Gerakaris V., Dailianis T., Gerovasileiou V., Follesa M.C.

Fishery: In this stock assessment the red coral fishery in GSA 22 has been considered in light of the high vulnerability of this species to fisheries. Currently, it is harvested only by authorized SCUBA divers, without the ROV, below 50 m of depth (Recommendation GFCM/43/2019/4).

Data and parameters: Data were taken in 2021 on images taken by stereo imaging in situ, under the GFCM Research programme launched in 2020. Basal diameter and height in mm were measured on stereo photos. Growth parameters from the assessment of red coral in Sardinian Waters were considered to estimate natural mortality: L_{inf} (basal diameter)= 45 mm; $K=0.007 \text{ years}^{-1}$; $t_0=0$ years. A range of natural mortality methods based on life history traits (Then, Hamel, Jensen, ZM and their modifications; http://barefootecologist.com.au/shiny_m) were applied to derive an average natural mortality of 0.034. The size at first maturity was collected by Santangelo et al. (2003) and is equal to 1.85 mm. In the model a logistic curve is assumed for the selectivity of the fleet.

Assessment method: The assessment was carried out using the LBSPR method (Length Based Spawning Potential Ratio, Hordyk 2015 and 2016), developed for data-limited fisheries. This method is based on the spawning potential of the stock in terms of SPR (SSB fished population/SSB unfished population). It is an equilibrium based method, assuming that the length composition data is representative of the exploited population at steady state. It does not require knowledge of the natural mortality rate (M), but the ratio (M/K), which varies less across stocks and species than M (Prince et al. 2015).

Model performance: The LBSPR model is able to fit the 2021 LFD according to the logistic selectivity curve quite consistently among the available years.

Figure 18. Fitting of 2021 LFD by LBSPR.

Results: The results show that the fishery selects the colonies characterized by a diameter above the size at first maturity. Under the assumption of steady state, the stock spawning potential seems deteriorated, according to the SPR indicator. Indeed the $SPR=0.18$ is well below the reference value of 0.4 ($SPR = 40\%$, is considered risk adverse for many species (Clark, 2002)). The mature fracture of the population is practically absent in the LFD, being the population mainly represented by small individuals. This could highlight a marked overexploitation situation.

The assessment was endorsed as qualitative advice, because based on only one year of data.

Figure 19. Selectivity parameters, F/M and SPR estimated by LBSPR.

Diagnosis of stock status: Possible high overexploitation.

Advice and recommendation: It is recommended to not increase the fishing mortality.

N: 14

Stock: Musked octopus (*Eledone cirrhosa*)

GSA: 18

Author(s): Giovanni Romagnoni; Isabella Bitetto; Walter Zupa; Giuseppe Lembo; Maria Teresa Spedicato; Marco Kule; Zdravko Ikica.

Fishery:

The horned octopus is a commercially important species. It is fished mainly with bottom trawl nets (OTB). Catch from gillnets and other artisanal gears are minor to negligible. Discards appears negligible in the Italian fleet, and no information is available from other countries. Landings are reported from Italy (accounting for 85-99% of reported landings), Montenegro and Albania.

Data and parameters: Catches were assumed identical to landings. Landings for the Italian fleet were obtained from DCF data (2004-2021). Data from Montenegro were obtained from Fishstat (2006-2018), while data from Albania was only available for the years 2019-2020. For these two countries, landing were reported as aggregate *Eledone spp.*, thus landings of the assessed species were reconstructed using the proportion of landing in the two species in Italian DCF data (2006-2018). Standardised biomass index data were provided by the MEDITS survey (1994-2021). The resilience r parameter was set as high, based on the reported Von Bertalanffy k parameter. Priors for initial and intermediate B/B_0 values were set respectively as medium depletion and low depletion, based on the criteria outlined by Froese et al., 2017 and consistently with the previous assessment (2021). No prior was set on the final year, which was estimated by the model.

Assessment method: CMSY is a Monte-Carlo method that estimates fisheries reference points (MSY , F_{msy} , B_{msy}) as well as relative stock size (B/B_{msy}) and exploitation (F/F_{msy}) from catch data and broad priors for resilience or productivity (r) and for stock status (B/k) at the beginning and the end of the time series. For comparative purposes, LBSPR (Hordyk et al. 2016) and LBB (Froese et al. 2018) models were also used.

Model performance: No particular trends are evidenced in residuals and the retrospective analyses is adequate. A sensitivity analysis was carried out by testing other runs with different parameters setting using objective methods for B/B_0 in the last year, and alternative parameterization. The overall results were consistent with those found using LBSPR and LBB.

Results: The final results of the model reported for the last year (2021) a B/B_{MSY} value of 0.802 and an estimated F/F_{MSY} of 0.767.

Fcurrent	0.383
Lower limit (95% ci)	0.139
Upper limit (95% ci)	0.911
FMSY	0.487
Fcurrent/FMSY	0.767
Lower limit F/FMSY (95% ci)	0.298
Upper limit F/FMSY (95% ci)	2.75
Bcurrent (1000s tons)	1.28

BMSY (1000s tons)	1.65
B_{current}/BMSY	0.802
Lower limit B/BMSY (95% ci)	0.349
Upper limit B/BMSY (95% ci)	1.43
MSY (1000s tons)	0.806
Lower limit MSY (95% ci)	0.685
Upper limit MSY (95% ci)	1.12

Diagnosis of stock status: Sustainably exploited, with relatively low biomass

Advice and recommendations: Do not increase fishing mortality.

N: 15

Stock: Black-bellied angler (*Lophius budegassa*)

GSA: 7

Summary sheet not received.

N: 16

Stock: European Hake (*Merluccius merluccius*)

GSA: 1, 5, 6, 7

Author(s): STECF EWG 22-09

Fishery: European hake is largely exploited in GSAs 1 and 6, mainly by trawlers on the shelf and slope, but also by small-scale fisheries using long lines, gill nets and trammel nets. In GSA 5, hake catches come exclusively from bottom trawlers. They show important oscillations along the data series, between 50 and 200 tons. In the Gulf of Lions (GSA 7), hake is exploited by French trawlers, French gillnetters, Spanish trawlers and Spanish longliners.

Data and parameters: The assessment was carried out in terms of time between 2007 and 2021 as survey indices data were available only from 2007 for GSA 5 (Balearic Islands). Available catch numbers at length and index number at length were sliced using the a4a age slicing routine in FLR (I2a). The analyses were carried out for ages 0 to 5+. According to the resulting selection pattern ages classes 1-3 were chosen to compute the current level of fishing mortality. All data were taken from 2021 EU DCF data call.

Assessment method: The assessment of European Hake carried out and presented during the GFCM benchmark considered the stock configuration including GSAs 1, 5, 6 and 7 as basis for the advice. According to the Assessment for All Initiative (a4a) method (Jardim et al., 2015) a statistical catch-at-age assessment was used. The a4a method utilizes catch-at-age data to derive estimates of historical population size and fishing mortality. Biomass reference points were estimated using the FLRef package.

Model performance: Available data series both in term of catches and survey were considered sufficient to provide advice by analytical model. The retrospective analysis was applied up only to 3 years back, due to the short time series. Models results were quite stable in terms of catch and SSB estimations. Fishing mortality value removing only one year was a bit different but remain quite similar for the previous years. Recruitment was quite different removing two years (not an issues considering the really short time series used).

Results: Based on the a4a results, the European hake SSB shows a decreasing trend. The assessment shows also a decreasing trend in the number of recruits, with an increase in the last year. F_{bar} (1-3) shows a quite stable trend at high levels.

$F_{\text{current}} F_{\text{bar}}$ ages 1-3 (2021)	1.34
$F_{0.1}$ (present assessment)	0.41
SSB _{current} (tons)	1498
B_{MSY}	63696
B_{pa}	7743
B_{lim}	3872
$F_{\text{current}}/F_{0.1}$	3.27

Diagnosis of stock status:

- High overfishing ($F_{\text{current}} > F_{0.1}$) is above 1.66
- Current biomass below B_{lim}

Advice and recommendation: Reduce F_{current} towards F_{MSY}

Figure 20. Comparison of the outputs of the previous years' assessments (purple, blue and green lines) and updated assessment performed this year (red line).

N: 17

Stock: European hake (*Merluccius merluccius*)

GSA: 1

Author(s): Pérez Gil, J.L., Serna-Quintero, J.M., Meléndez, M.J, García, C., González, M., Torres, P., Acosta, J., Galindo, M., León, E., Cíercoles, C.. and Martínez, G.

Fishery: European hake (*Merluccius merluccius* (Linnaeus, 1758)) is one of the target demersal species of the Mediterranean fishing fleets, largely exploited in GSA1 mainly by bottom otter trawlers (96% landings) on the shelf and slope, and by small-scale fisheries using gillnets (3%) and longlines (1%) on the shelf (2021). The otter bottom trawl fleet segment in the GSA1 area is made up of 118 boats (2021), averaging 35 GRT and 176 HP. Catches of European hake show a decreasing trend from 2018 to 2020, with a slight increase in 2021 reaching 263 tons. (Average 2019-2021, 231 tons).

Data and parameters: The assessment was carried out using official landings and data on the size composition of otter bottom trawl catches (including discard) for the years 2003-2021. Catch-at-length data were converted into catch-at-age data by cohort slicing procedures. Length-weight relationship and maturity ogive comes from Spanish DCF.

Assessment method: The state of exploitation of this stock was assessed by means of VPA Extended Survivor Analysis (XSA) (Shepherd, 1999). The software used was the Lowestoft suite (Darby and Flatman 1994) and FLR (Fisheries Libraries in R). The XSA tuning was performed using abundance index series from MEDITS trawl surveys. Yield-per-Recruit (Y/R) analyses was conducted based on the exploitation pattern resulting from XSA model and population parameters.

Model performance: Sensitivity and retrospective analyses were applied in the XSA model in order to check the robustness of the assessment. A deterministic short-term prediction for the period 2022 to 2024 was performed using the FLR libraries and scripts, and based on the results of the XSA stock assessment. The assessment was update of 2021.

Results: Catches and SSB of European hake showed a decreasing trend from 2012 to 2016, with a slight increase in 2017-2019, decreasing in 2020. Recruitment (R) showed fluctuations over the series and steep decline in recent years. Fbar (0-2) in recent years, fluctuates around values close to 1.2-1.5.

$F_{current}$ (F_{bar} ages 0-2 (2019-2021))	1.49
F_{target} (present assessment)	0.24
$F_{current}/F_{target_1}$	6.2
SSB _{current} (year) tonnes	171
SSB 33% percentile biomass(tonnes)	228
SSB 66% percentile biomass(tonnes)	311

Diagnosis of stock status: The stock is in overexploitation, with relatively low biomass.

Advice and recommendation.

- Reduce $F_{current}$ towards $F_{0.1}$
- Progressive reduction of the fishing effort

Figure 21. Comparison of the outputs of the previous year assessment (red line) and update assessment performed this year (blue line).

N: 18

Stock: European hake (*Merluccius merluccius*)

GSA: 3

Author(s): Settih J, Benchoucha S, Elouamari N., Ligas A., Hernandez P.

Fishery:

European hake is a target demersal species of the Mediterranean fishing fleets. It is one of the target demersal species of the Mediterranean fishing fleets. The trawl fishing fleet in GSA03 is heterogeneous, longliners are not found. The number of trawlers operating in this area is 99. *M.*

merluccius in GSA 03 is found at depths ranging from 50 to 510 m. In the period 2019-2021, the mean annual *M. merluccius* production was 91 tonnes.

Data and parameters: This assessment was done in the framework of the Working Group on demersal species. The meeting was held on the 4 to 9 December was attended by experts from Morocco, Algeria and Spain. The assessment was carried out using official landings and data from 2007 to 2021 and from Moroccan Medit survey from 2010 to 2021. Catch-at-length data were converted into catch-at-age data by cohort slicing procedures. Length-weight relationship and maturity ogive comes from Spanish DCF.

Assessment method: A statistical catch at age model (a4a) was used and FLBRP package for yield per recruit analysis, both part of the FLR library. The assessment was carried out over the period 2007-2021, calibrated with fishery independent survey abundance index (MEDITS). This is a new assessment and the submodels configuration.

Model performance: Residuals considered acceptable, while retrospective plots exhibit few unstable patterns. The effect of missing information is also apparent in the estimated confidence limits of estimated harvest, catch, ssb and recruitment.

Results: In the most recent years, SSB continues to decrease, Recruitment shows a small increasing trends, while F is decreasing.

Fcurrent F_{bar} ages 0-2(2021)	1.70
$F_{0.1}$ (present assessment)	0.44
SSBcurrent (tons)	38.07
SSB (33 th)	86.94
SSB (66 th)	118.78
Fcurrent/ $F_{0.1}$	3.86

Diagnosis of stock status: In overexploitation, with relatively low biomass.

Advice and recommendations: Reduce fishing mortality towards $F_{0.1}$.

Figure 22. Hake in GSA 3. Estimated recruitment, SSB, Catch and F_{bar} (ages: 0- 2) and their respective confidence limits. Red line represents the observed catch

N: 19

Stock: European Hake (*Merluccius merluccius*)

GSA: 4

Author(s): Tahar FILALI, Alessandro LIGAS and Pilar HERNÁNDEZ

Fishery: In GSA 04, European hake, *Merluccius merluccius*, is one of the famous marine targeted species. It is largely exploited by bottom trawlers OTB on the shelf and slope, but also by small-scale fisheries using gillnets and trammel (< 6 % of total hake catches in 2021). The minimum landings since 2005 were observed in 2021. In general, the highest biomass index from Algerian demersal surveys data analysis was observed in the Shelf (ALDEMs 2012- 2021). The maximum biomass index is observed in the eastern part of Algerian coast. Smaller size classes, less than 25 cm are the most dominant in trawlers catches. Discards data are not available, the project still in progress.

Data and parameters: Length frequency data coming from the Western area (Ghazaouet) and Eastern area (Annaba) of GSA 4 from commercial trawl catches of five years (2017–2021) were used to assess stock parameters. LFD were weighted to the official landings of each area by sex. The central area landings were summed to the western TRANSBORAN project results. This central area landings are negligible comparing to the others two areas. The stock object of each area was build using FLR package and the two stock objects are combined together. Catch-at-age of the whole area were used with Bouaziz et al. (1998) VBG parameters of males and females and the combined sex VBG parameters of Filali & Hemida (2014). Maturity ogive from the Algerian national data collection program (GSA 04) and the average M vector obtained by Chen & Watanabe method by sexes, were used as input data.

Assessment method: Catch at age data are constructed using a4a slicing and the stock object. Pseudocohort and yield-per-recruit analysis were performed by Vit software. An LBSPR model was used for both females and combined sexes LFDs.

Model performance: Vit program was developed to assess exploited fish stocks in data-poor situations. It was used for qualitative conclusions from several years in GFCM meeting. Quantitative interpretations of stock parameters are recommended when the model is applied to short time series of more than a single year and the resulting variation of the parameters is reasonably low. sensitivity of model was tested using several terminal F and mean fishing mortality from ages most presented in catches each year and for the average pseudocohort was used to estimate F current. Results coming from the model may form the basis for scientifically sound fisheries management advice for medium-term periods. However, the likely low precision of results prevents their transfer to any precise short-term forecasts.

Results: Age classes 1-3 are the most exploited in GSA04, current F is very higher than $F_{0.1}$ which indicate a high overfishing status.

F_{current} ($F_{\text{bar } 1-3}$ in 2021)	0.78 (\pm 0.09)
$F_{0.1}$ (2019)	0.23 (\pm 0.02)
$F_{\text{current}}/F_{0.1}$	3.39
Current SSB (tonnes)	399
33 rd percentile biomass (tonnes)	548
66 th percentile biomass (tonnes)	644

Diagnosis of stock status: In High overexploitation.

Advice and recommendations:

- Reduce $F_{current}$ towards $F_{0.1}$
- Progressive reduction of fishing effort.

N: 20**Stock:** European hake (*Merluccius merluccius*)**GSA:** 05**Author(s):** Marc Farré, Beatriz Guijarro, Natalia González and Virginia Soldán.

Fishery: In the Balearic Islands, commercial bottom trawlers develop up to four different fishing tactics, which are associated with the shallow shelf, deep shelf, upper slope and middle slope, mainly targeted to: (i) *Spicara smaris*, *Mullus surmuletus*, *Octopus vulgaris* and a mixed fish category on the shallow shelf (50-80 m); (ii) *Merluccius merluccius*, *Mullus* spp., *Zeus faber* and a mixed fish category on the deep shelf (80-250 m); (iii) *Nephrops norvegicus*, but with an important by-catch of big *Merluccius merluccius*, *Lepidorhombus* spp., *Lophius* spp. and *Micromesistius poutassou* on the upper slope (350-600 m) and (iv) *Aristeus antennatus* on the middle slope (600-750 m). The European hake (*M. merluccius*) is a target species for this fishery, mainly exploited on the deep shelf and upper slope, with annual landings oscillating between 50 and 150 tons during the last decades (1980-2021). All hake catches from this area come exclusively from bottom trawlers.

Data and parameters: Size composition of commercial trawl catches and official landings (1980-2021), calibrating data from survey indices (2001-2021) and CPUE data from commercial fleet (2000-2021). Biological parameters obtained from scientific studies: growth parameters and maturity ogive from Mellon-Duval *et al.* (2010) and from Spanish National Data Collection Programme; M vector calculated from PRODBIOM.

Assessment method: A4a was used and selected to provide the final advice. Additionally, yield per recruit analysis and short-term forecast analysis were carried out. The assessment is an update from the previous year 2020.

Model performance: The model showed a quite good fit, despite that catch data provided by the model doesn't fit very well with the real catch for the last years, due to the strong oscillations of catch data along all the time series.

Results: Stock abundance, spawning stock biomass and recruitment showed noticeably oscillations along the entire data series, showing no clear trends (Fig. 1).

$F_{current}$ (2021, ages 0-3)	1.28
$F_{0.1}$ (2021)	0.34
$F_{current}/F_{0.1}$	3.77
$SSB_{current}$ (2021, tons)	69.3
33 th percentile SSB (tons)	93.5
66 th percentile SSB (tons)	112.3

Diagnosis of stock status: The stock is in overexploitation, with relatively low biomass.

Advice and recommendation: To reduce fishing mortality.

Data issues: Information used was the official one submitted to the GFCM.

Comparative plot:

Figure 23. Comparison of the outputs of the previous year assessment (2020) and update assessment performed this year (2021).

N: 21

Stock: European hake (*Merluccius merluccius*)

GSA: 6

Author(s): García-Rodríguez, E., Pérez-Gil, J. L, Vivas, M., Esteban, A, Tifoura, A, Meléndez, M. J

Fishery: European hake is a target demersal species of the Mediterranean fishing fleets. It is largely exploited in GSA6, mainly by trawlers on the shelf and slope (95% landings), but also by small-scale fisheries using long lines (2%) and gillnets and trammel nets (3%) (average percents estimated between 2017 and 2020). According to official statistics, around 1000 boats are involved in this fishery, with total annual landings oscillating around 1700 tons for the period 2017-2021 (1531 tons in 2021). The trawler fleet is the largest in number of boats (432).

Data and parameters: The assessment was carried out using official landings and data on the size composition of trawl, long lines and set gillnet catches for the years 2002-2021. Abundance index series from MEDITS surveys were used as indices of abundance independent of the fishery.

Assessment method: an update of an a4a model was used for assessment. Additionally, yield per recruit analysis was carried out.

Model performance: Sensitivity and retrospective analyses were applied in the a4a model in order to check the robustness of the assessment. Results showed no particular retrospective bias in spawning biomass (SSB), fishing mortality (F) or recruitment (R). The population was not rebuilt for the period 1995-2001. Inconsistencies between population and survey indices cohorts observed in 2018 assessment were corrected.

Results: Total biomass (B) and yield (Y) showed a general decreasing trend from 2002 to 2020. Recruitment (R) showed a drastic decline from the maximum observed in 2002. Fishing mortality ($F_{\text{bar}0-2}$) shows a slight increase until the maximum value in 2020 and a decreasing trend in 2021, when the estimated F is 1.25.

$F_{\text{current}}F_{\text{bar}0-2}$ (2020)	1.24
$F_{0.1}$ (present assessment)	0.12
$F_{\text{current}}/F_{0.1}$	10.7
$SSB_{\text{current}(2021)}$ tonnes	1024
SSB 33% percentilebiomass(tonnes)	1487
SSB 66% percentilebiomass(tonnes)	2012

Diagnosis of stock status: Y/R analysis showed that the $F_{\text{current}}= (1.24)$ exceeds the Y/R $F_{0.1}$ reference point = (0.12). The resulting ratio $F_{0.1}/F_{\text{current}} = 10.7$, suggesting that for *Merluccius merluccius* stock in GSA6, the current exploitation level is in over exploitation and the stock size is overexploited (Relative low biomass).

Advice and recommendation.

- Reduce F_{current} towards $F_{0.1}$
- Progressive reduction of the fishing effort

Figure 23. Comparison of the outputs of the previous year assessment (blue line) and update assessment performed this year (red line).

N: 22

Stock: European Hake (*Merluccius merluccius*)

GSA: 8, 9, 10, 11

Author(s): A. Ligas, C. Musumeci, A. Bellodi, I. Bitetto, P. Carbonara, M.C. Follesa, A. Jadaud, A. Massaro, P. Pesci, L. Lanteri, P. Sartor, M. Sbrana, M.T. Spedicato, STECF EWG 22-09

Fishery: European hake is one of the main target species in terms of landings, incomes and vessel involved in the area. In GSAs 9 and 10, it is mainly exploited by trawlers on the shelf and slope, but also by small-scale fisheries using set nets (gillnets and trammel nets) and bottom long-lines. In GSA 11, although hake is not target of a specific fishery, it is one of the most important species in terms of biomass landed. It is caught exclusively by a mixed bottom trawl fishery that operates at depth between 50 and 800 m. No gillnet or longline fleets target this species, but it can be found as bycatch of gillnet fleets targeting other species.

In Corsica (GSA 8), six trawlers are active and their average length is 15 m; these vessels operate with bottom trawls nets along the eastern coasts of Corsica targeting demersal species (Norway lobster, striped red mullet, deep-water rose shrimp, etc.).

Data and parameters: Landings data were reported to the benchmark meeting through the official EU DCF data provided by Italy. In GSAs 9, 10 and 11, most of the landings come from otter trawling. The contribution of set nets to the total landing is around 30% in GSAs 9 and 10; longlines in GSA 10 contribute for around the 15% of the total landings. In GSA 11, landing data come exclusively from the bottom trawl fishery. In GSA8, catch data, proceeding from the limited number of trawlers cover only the period 2009-2021. Landings are very low in all the years where data are available and the discards are not included in the catch because no information is available. Reconstructed data were estimated from 2005 to 2008, considering an average of the available information.

Discards were not available in GSA 9, 10 and 11 for some years, therefore they were estimated using an average proportion between landings and discards computed on the available years.

Taking advantage of the age-length data collected under EU DCR/DCF, two sets of VBGF parameters were computed by sex using the package FSA available in R (Ogle, 2016). In order to obtain an estimate of t_0 close to 0, data of age and length of juveniles coming from studies on otolith daily rings (Belcari et al., 2006; Ligas et al., 2015) were added to the data sets.

Length-weight relationship parameters were estimated by sex as the average of those available in GSAs 9, 10, 11 under EU DCR/DCF. No biological data are available for hake in GSA 8.

Using the selected VBGF parameters a combined vector of proportion of matures-at-age was estimated starting from the vectors of maturity-at-length available under the EU DCR/DCF.

The selected VBGF and LW relationship parameters were used to estimate a range of natural mortality (M) vectors using different models and empirical formulas, as agreed during the benchmark meeting.

MEDITS data from 2005 to 2020 were used to compute the tuning information to be used in the assessment.

Assessment method: Statistical Catch-At-Age, SCAA (a4a, FLR libraries <http://flr-project.org>), FLBRP package for yield per recruit analysis and Flash package for short-term forecast. This assessment was benchmarked in 2019 by GFCM. The biomass reference points were estimated using the FLRef package.

Model performance: Model residuals and retrospective analysis did not show any trends, patterns or violation. The estimates of the coefficients fitted by the selected model, the corresponding standard error and the cryptic biomass were also inspected and resulted consistent.

Results: The results show a decreasing pattern of fishing mortality, even though the value in 2021 ($F_{\text{bar}1-3} = 0.537$) is still well above the reference point ($F_{0.1} = 0.167$) used as proxy for F_{MSY} , with a ratio of 3.22. SSB and recruitment show a decreasing pattern, with an increase in recent years.

Fcurrent F_{bar} ages 1-3 (2021)	0.537
$F_{0.1}$ (present assessment)	0.167
SSBcurrent (tons)	4158
B_{MSY}	53600.6
B_{pa}	11127.84
B_{lim}	5563.918
Fcurrent/ $F_{0.1}$	3.22

Diagnosis of stock status: The diagnosis is that the stock is in high overexploitation and the current biomass is below B_{lim} .

Advice and recommendations: Reduce the fishing mortality towards the reference point.

Figure 24. Comparison of the outputs of the previous years' assessments (purple, blue and green lines) and updated assessment performed this year (red line).

N: 23

Stock: European hake (*Merluccius merluccius*)

GSA: 12-13-14-15-16

Author(s): Falsone F., Fiorentino F., Gancitano V., Scannella D., Ben Mariem S., Jarboui O., Fezzani S., Ben Abdellah O., Mifsud J., Gambin M., Camilleri, K., Vitale S., BesBes M.K., Ceriola L., Arneri E., Cardinale M.

Fishery: In the Strait of Sicily European hake (HKE) is fished by 6 fishing fleets: Italian coastal trawlers, Italian distant trawlers, Tunisian trawlers, Maltese trawlers, Tunisian and Italian artisanal vessels. Mean annual landings of hake for 2018-2021 was about 658 t from Italian and Maltese trawlers and about 1385 t from Tunisian trawlers. Hake is the main commercial by-catch species of deep water

shrimp fisheries and a target species for vessels using longlines and gillnets. Trawlers catching hake exploit a highly diversified species assemblages, the main other commercial species being deep water rose shrimp (*Parapenaeus longirostris*, generally main the target species), striped mullet (*Mullus surmuletus*) and red mullet (*Mullus barbatus*). Size structures of hake catches range between 4 and 72 cm total length (TL) for the Italian-Maltese trawler, 6-68 (TL) for the Tunisian trawler and 10-64 for the Italian-Tunisian passive gears. (TL).

Data and parameters: Fishery dependent data used for the stock assessment in the GSA 16 are reported in the following table:

Fishery	Data type	Fleet	Period	Source
Italian-Maltese trawlers	Commercial landings (tons)	Italian trawlers	1947-2021	ISTAT (1947-2001) DCF (2002-2021)
		Maltese trawlers	2009-2021	DCF
	Discards (tons)	Italian trawlers	2009-2021	
	Length composition of commercial landings (N thousand)	Italian trawlers	2009-2021	
		Maltese trawlers	2009-2021	
	Length composition of discards (N thousand)	Italian trawlers	2009-2021	
Age length key	Italian trawlers	2004-2021		
Tunisian trawlers	Commercial landings (tons)	Tunisian trawlers	1950-2021	Official Tunisian landing statistics
	Length composition of commercial landings (N thousand)	Tunisian trawlers	2007-2021	
	Discards (tons)	Tunisian trawlers	2007-2021	
Italian-Tunisian passive gears	Commercial landings (tons)	Italian passive gears	2004-2021	DCF
		Tunisian passive gears	2014-2021	Official Tunisian landing statistics
	Length composition of commercial landings (N thousand)	Italian fixed nets	2010-2021	DCF
		Tunisian passive gears	2010-2021	Official Tunisian landing statistics

Stock abundance indices were available from the MEDITS survey (Mediterranean International Trawl Survey) carried out in GSA 16 and conducted mainly in 3th quarter of the year. Data on biomass index and length composition are available from 1994 to 2021.

Moreover, the same parameters of the last model were used with the exception for the coefficient variation where for the time series from 2015 to 2021 a value of 0.3 was set. However, the sensitivity analysis showed that this modification improves the diagnostic of the model and overall all tested configurations estimated very similar values in terms of SSB, F and Recruitment.

Assessment method: The assessment was performed through Stock Synthesis model (SS3)

Model performance: A normal distribution was found in residuals of Biomass index as well as in the mean length trend of fishery two (Tunisian trawling). On the contrary, no particular trends are evidenced in residuals for the other fleets. RMSE was for each fleet below the threshold of 30% indicating a good fitting and the retrospective analyses was consistent. Hindcasting performed well on mean length with the exception of the Fleet one (Italian and Maltese trawling fleet combined). While, the hindcasting of MEDITS survey was reasonable but the model is not able to predict the biomass index in 2021 and the MASE value was just a bit higher than 1.

Results: The model estimated a value of F lower than F_{MSY} (0.27, estimated as the F_{1-6} in the last year of the time series, 2021) and a SSB at first January 2022 of 5894 tonnes.

$F_{current}$ (SS3)	0.27
F_{MSY}	0.29
$F_{current}/F_{MSY}$	0.90
Current SSB (tonnes)	5894
SSB_{MSY}	7021
$SSB_{current}/SSB_{MSY}$	0.84

Diagnosis of stock status: Taking into account the final results of the model, European Hake in GSA 12-16 is in sustainable overexploitation and overexploited. According to the group decision of using the mean of the last three models for the stock diagnosis, the species was estimated in overexploitation and overexploited condition.

	2019	2020	2021	Average
$F_{current}$	0.50	0.36	0.27	0.38
$F_{current}/F_{MSY}$	1.72	1.24	0.90	1.29
$SSB_{current}$	4744	4885	5894	5174
$SSB_{current}/SSB_{MSY}$	0.68	0.70	0.84	0.74

Advice and recommendations: Continue to reduce fishing mortality

Comparative plot:

N: 24

Stock: European hake (*Merluccius merluccius*)

GSA: 17 - 18

Author(s): STECF EWG 22-16

Fishery: European hake, *Merluccius merluccius*, is one of the most important demersal species for the Adriatic Sea. In this area, hake is exploited mainly by bottom trawlers and in the southern part of the Adriatic Sea and in Croatian waters longlines are also relevant. Landings present a fluctuating trend all over the time series considered accounting for the highest value in 2006 and the lowest value in 2020. Italy is the country that mainly exploits this species; in particular, Italian bottom trawl catches of GSAs 17 and 18 represents around 75 percent of the total Adriatic catches. Bottom trawl catches are mainly composed by age 0, 1 and 2, whereas longlines exploit bigger individuals.

Data and parameters: The biological information, specifically growth and length-weight relationship parameters, is assumed equal to those estimated by the DCF sampling protocol in the Italian GSA 18. Catch data are included by country and gear, as well as the length composition of catches. Survey data corresponds to the MEDITS index including both GSA 17 and 18. ALKs are included only for one fleet, the longlines operating in Italy GSA 18, and in this year assessment they have been replaced with the new and corrected data.

Assessment method: The present assessment is an update of the evaluation presented in January 2022, but with the correction of ALK data. The fundamental idea of this stock assessment is to use the integrated approach of Stock Synthesis (last version SS3.30.18) to model the size structure data available for the hake. SS3 uses forward projection of population in the “statistical catch-at-age” approach.

Model performance: The model setting well fits the length composition data and the MEDITS index, as well as the new ALK data. However, the retrospective analysis shows some instability, presenting a slight underestimation of F and a substantial overestimation of female SSB. Instead, the run tests show a good fitting for the length data of all the fleet, except for the Italian bottom trawlers, while the MASE is <1 for most of the fleets, except the Italian bottom trawlers operating in GSA 17, the bottom trawlers of Montenegro and the MEDITS data. Also, the influence of the new ALK data have been tested, showing that the corrected age information does not affect substantially the result of the assessment (Figure below).

Figure 25. Comparison between the stock assessment accepted by the GFCM in January 2022 (Hake1718_GFCM, red line) and a new run with the corrected ALK (Hake1718_GFCMcorrected, blue line)

Results: The overall stock status conclusions confirm the positive trend depicting in the last years assessment; spawning stock biomass shows a continuous increasing trend, while fishing mortality constantly decreases since 2015. Recruitment describe a quite stable trend with a decreasing tendency in the last years. In this assessment ALK data have been substituted, thus reference points, for both fishing mortality and biomass, have been restimated following the procedure used during the benchmark assessment (GFCM, 2019).

F_{current} ($F_{\text{bar } 1-4}$ in 2021)	0.39
F_{MSY}	0.23
$F_{\text{current}}/F_{\text{MSY}}$	1.69
Current SSB (tonnes) 2022	4017
B_{lim} (tonnes)	1344
$B_{\text{trigger}} = B_{\text{pa}}$ (tonnes)	1881
$B_{\text{current}}/B_{\text{lim}}$	2.99
$B_{\text{current}}/B_{\text{pa}}$	2.14

Diagnosis of stock status:

Considering the results of the analyses conducted, European hake in GSA 17-18 is subjected to overfishing, being the current $F_{\text{bar}(1-4)}$, equal to 0.39, higher than the proposed reference point ($F_{\text{MSY}} = 0.23$). Based on the biomass level (SSB), the stock results in a state of relative high biomass being the current SSB (2022, 4017 t) higher than B_{pa} and B_{lim} . According to Table 10 of the framework for describing stock status and providing management advice in relation to reference points (GFCM, 2014), the stock is with biomass above reference points and in overexploitation. The establishment of a FRA in the Pomo/Jabuka pits can potentially have driven the increase of hake biomass observed in the most recent years.

Advice and recommendations: Reducing the fishing mortality. The need of a new benchmark or interbenchmark session has been submitted to the working group, in order to produce a more stable model for the next year and evaluate the possibility of including historical data and eventually revise the reference points.

N: 25

Stock: European hake (*Merluccius merluccius*)

GSA: 19

Author(s): I. Bitetto, P. Carbonara, M. Donnaloia, L. Casciaro, M.T. Spedicato, P. Maiorano, G. Cipriano, L. Sion, R. Carlucci (GFCM 2020, benchmark); Ilaria Costantini, stock coordinator (STECF EWG 22-16, benchmark update)

Fishery: Following the last SAC meeting (Rome, Italy, 21–24 June 2022), the benchmark stock assessment of European hake was carried out assuming the stock in the boundaries of the Western Ionian Sea (GSA 19). *M. merluccius* represents one of the most important demersal species in terms of landing and income in GSA 19, especially for longlines (about 20% of the hake landing), gillnets and trammel nets (about 20% of the hake landing), but also for trawlers (about 60%).

Data and parameters: Official landings from DCF are available since 2002 but being the first two years quite different from the rest of the time series, and lacking the longlines in the same years, the assessment was carried out with data from 2004 to 2021. For MEDITS survey indices, the data are available from 1994, but for the present assessment data from 2004 to 2021 were used. The discard data are present from 2006 to 2021, with a gap in 2007 and 2008 (not mandatory). In the years 2004, 2005, 2007 and 2008 the discard (weight and LFDs) has been estimated according to the average discard ratio of the years 2006 and 2009. Biological information on growth such as von Bertalanffy growth parameters, length-weight relationship, maturity and natural mortality at age vectors were obtained as determined at the hake benchmark meeting (GFCM 2020) and are applied to the entire catch timeseries (2004-2021). Deterministic age slicing using agreed growth parameters was used to produce catch at age input for assessment.

Assessment method: Statistical catch at age a4a (assessment for all, <http://flr-project.org/FLa4a>) was performed at the hake benchmark meeting (GFCM, 2020). The STECF EWG 22-16 found that the original Fmodel used for the previous assessment (STECF EWG 21-15) resulted in high instability of the present assessment, especially looking at the retrospective analysis. Also, the analysis of residuals coming from MEDITS index showed a strong inconsistency for 2017. For this reason, the Fishing mortality model was modified and 2017 in MEDITS index was removed. Second, was noticed a change in gear catchability for effort and catches since 2014. To understand how this could affect the retrospective analysis, was conducted an analysis on the proportion of F obtained by the retrospective and on catchability of the survey, using the original sub-models of the previous assessment (STECF EWG 21-15) without MEDITS index for 2017. The analysis highlighted that the F of last 5 years was very different and consequently this gave instability to the model. Otherwise, the catchability of the survey was very stable. For all these reasons, STECF EWG 22-16 agreed to use a model without 2017 for MEDITS index and with a breakpoint for 2015 in Fmodel, in order to consider the change in effort and catches. With this replacement the assessment has greater stability and it is hoped will perform better in the future. Survey catchability and Stock-recruit sub-models remain the same as the one used for the previous assessment (STECF EWG 21-15).

Fishing mortality: $F_{\text{model}} \sim s(\text{age}, k=5, \text{by}=\text{breakpts}(\text{year}, 2015)) + s(\text{year}, k=7) + s(\text{year}, k=7, \text{by}=\text{as.numeric}(\text{age}==0))$

Survey catchability: $Q_{\text{model}} \sim \text{list}(\sim \text{factor}(\text{replace}(\text{age}, \text{age}>2, 2)))$

Stock-recruit: $R_{\text{model}} \sim \text{geomean}(\text{CV}=0.2)$

Model performance: The results and the diagnostics of the fitted model are quite similar to those obtained during last assessment (STECF EWG 21-15), except for the recruitment that is increasing instead of decreasing like in 2020. The retrospective analysed do not show consistent pattern of under- or overestimation of Recruits, SSB and F_{bar} , in the last years.

Results: The $F_{sq}=0.335$ (assumed F_{bar} in the last assessment year 2020) is larger than $F_{0.1}$ (0.211), which is a proxy of F_{MSY} and is used as the exploitation reference point consistent with high long-term yields. This indicates that hake in GSA 19 is over exploited. The catch of hake in 2022, consistent with $F_{0.1}$ (0.211), should not exceed 468 t, 27.9 % less than the current estimated catch (649 t).

$F_{current}$ (F_{bar} 0-4 in 2022)	0.335
$F_{0.1}$ (2021)	0.211
$F_{current}/F_{0.1}$	1.59
Current SSB 2020 (tons)	1527
33 th percentile biomass (tons)	1115
66 th percentile biomass (tons)	1266

Diagnosis of stock status: The diagnosis indicates that hake stock in GSAs 19 is over-exploited.

Advice and recommendations: Reduce the fishing mortality towards the reference point, progressively reducing the fishing effort.

Figure 26. Comparison plot between the last year assessment and the update of this year.

N: 26

Stock: Hake (*Merluccius merluccius*)

GSA: 20

Author(s): D. Mantopoulou – Palouka, V. Sgardeli & G. Tserpes

Fishery: The stock is exploited by various Greek fleet segments, including bottom trawlers and artisanal fisheries using gillnets and demersal longlines. Less than 50% of the landings come from bottom trawlers. The Greek bottom trawl fishery has multi-species characteristics and similarly to most Mediterranean demersal trawl fisheries, captures more than 100 commercial species. However, hake

together with red mullets, and shrimps compose the main bulk of landings. Hake alone comprises 5-15% of the total landings in the Ionian Sea.

Data and parameters: Biological information on growth, i.e. the von Bertalanffy parameters, as well the length-weight relationship were derived within DCF. Natural mortality and maturity vectors were the ones used in 2019 benchmark. The official landings data as reported through the HELSTAT were used in the assessment. Discards ratio to landings was estimated using DCF data and total discards data were calculated using the HELSTAT data. Catch at size data as reported in DCF were used in the assessment. Both catch numbers at length and index number at length were sliced using the I2a age slicing function of FLR.

Assessment method: A statistical catch at age model (a4a) was used and FLBRP package for yield per recruit analysis, both part of the FLR library. The assessment was carried out over the period 2003-2021, calibrated with fishery independent survey abundance index (MEDITS). This is an update assessment and the sub models configuration were the ones used in the previous assessment.

Model performance: Residuals considered acceptable, while retrospective plots exhibit few unstable patterns mainly due to missing years in both catch at age and index data. The effect of missing information is also apparent in the estimated confidence limits of estimated harvest, catch, SSB and recruitment. A complementary assessment for this species, presented by STECF, showed similar results.

Results: In the most recent years, biomass shows increasing trends, while F is decreasing.

F _{current} F _{bar} ages 1-3(2020)	0.714
F _{0.1} (present assessment)	0.133
SSB _{current} (tons)	1619
SSB (33 th)	1402
SSB (66 th)	1793
F _{current} /F _{0.1}	5.37

Diagnosis of stock status: In overexploitation, with relatively high biomass.

Advice and recommendations: Reduce fishing mortality towards F_{0.1}.

Figure 27. European hake in GSA 20. Estimated recruitment, SSB, Catch and Fbar (ages: 1- 3) and their respective confidence limits. Blue line represents the observed catch

N: 27

Stock: European hake (*Merluccius merluccius*)

GSA: 22 - 23

Author(s): D. Mantopoulou – Palouka & G. Tserpes

Fishery: Hake is one of the most important fish stocks in GSA 22 for bottom trawlers, nets and longlines. The stock is distributed in depths between 50 and 600 m, with a peak in abundance between 200 and 300 m. The majority of landings (~60%) comes from bottom trawlers (Anonymous, 2013). The Greek bottom trawl fishery has multi-species characteristics and similarly to most Mediterranean demersal trawl fisheries, captures more than 100 commercial species. However, hake together with red mullets and shrimps compose the main bulk of landings.

Data and parameters: Biological information on growth, i.e. the von Bertalanffy parameters, as well the length-weight relationship were derived within DCF. Natural mortality vector was estimated using Chen and Watannabe method while the proportion of mature individuals at age was based on recent bibliography. The official landings data as reported through the HELSTAT for GSA 22 and 23 and TURKSTAT for GSA 22 were used in the assessment. Catch at size data, as reported through DCF, were used in the assessment. Both catch numbers at length and index number at length were sliced using the I2a age slicing function of FLR.

Assessment method: Biological information on growth, i.e. the von Bertalanffy parameters, as well the length-weight relationship were derived within DCF. Natural mortality and maturity vectors were the ones used in last year's benchmark. The official landings data as reported through the HELSTAT were used in the assessment. Discards ratio to landings was estimated using DCF data and total discards data were calculated using the HELSTAT data. Catch at size data as reported in DCF were used in the assessment. Both catch numbers at length and index number at length were sliced using the I2a age slicing function of FLR.

Model performance: Both residuals and retrospective plots were considered acceptable. And the model was considered suitable for quantitative advice.

Results: In the most recent years, biomass shows increasing trends, while F shows a constant decreasing trend since 2007.

F _{current} F _{bar} ages 0-2(2020)	0.924
F _{0.1} (present assessment)	0.151
SSB _{current} (tons)	6524
SSB (33 th)	6429
SSB (66 th)	7401
F _{current} /F _{0.1}	6.09

Diagnosis of stock status: Possibly in overexploitation

Advice and recommendations: Reduce fishing mortality

Figure 28. European hake in GSA 22. Estimated recruitment, SSB, Catch and Fbar (ages: 1- 3) and their respective confidence limits. Blue line represents the observed catch.

N: 28

Stock: Red mullet (*Mullus barbatus*)

GSA: 01

Author(s): Meléndez Vallejo, M. J.; Pérez Gil, J. L; García-Rodríguez, E.; Ruíz García, C.; Vivas, M.; Esteban, A.; González, M.; Torres, P.; Serna, J.M; Acosta, J; Ciércoles, C.; León, E.

Fishery: In GSA 1, red mullet are among the most important target species for the trawl fisheries. It is largely exploited in all the trawlable areas, both sandy and muddy bottoms mainly by trawlers on the shelf, but also by small-scale fisheries in particular trammel nets (about the 15% of the catches). The amount of discards reported is very low and considered to be negligible. Trawl fisheries developed along the continental shelf and upper slope are multi-specific. Smaller vessels operate almost exclusively on the continental shelf (targeting red mullets, octopus, hake and sea breams) and bigger vessels operate almost exclusively on the continental slope. Red mullet is intensively exploited during its recruitment from September to November. The total trawl fleet has declined from 2003 to 2021, from a maximum number of 188 trawlers in 2006, the GSA 1 fleet catching red mullet is nowadays composed by 94 units. The annual landings in this area fluctuated during the entire assessed series reaching 143 tonnes in 2021.

Data and parameters: The information used for the assessment are the total annual landings from official statistics, the annual catch in number by size class estimated by monthly port sampling and on board observers and the abundance index from MEDITS surveys. Growth parameters are those used in previous assessments by STECF and GFCM for GSA 01 (Demestre et al, 1997). Length-weight relationship and maturity ogive comes from Spanish DCF and the vector of natural mortality by age

was calculated using the Chen & Watanabe method (1989). Selectivity experiences carried out by the IEO with 40 mm diamond and square mesh in the cod-end were also used.

Assessment method: The state of exploitation of this stock was assessed using (SCAA) stock assessment model (a4a) (Jardim and Millar, 2014). The assessment was performed using abundance index series from MEDITS trawl surveys. Abundance indices for 2020 was estimated by GAM adjustment. Yield-per-Recruit(Y/R) analyses was conducted based on the exploitation pattern resulting from a4a model and population parameters.

Model performance:

Log catchability residuals and Retrospective analysis suggest that the model is consistent.

Results: Recruits showed fluctuations in all series, peaking in 2021. SSB showed fluctuations during the assessed period with lowest values in 2012 and highest values during 2016 and 2017, increasing in 2021. A similar pattern was observed in the catch. Fishing mortality showed an upward trend until 2010, decreasing until 2013 and then increasing with maximum values during 2017. Current F (0.87) is higher than F_{0.1} (0.36), chosen as a proxy for FMS, which indicating that the mullet population in GSA 1 is highly overfished with a relatively high spawning stock biomass.

F _{current} (mean FBAR ages 1-2) (2021)	0.87
F _{0.1} (present assessment)	0.36
F _{current} /F _{0.1}	2.4
SSB _{current} (tonnes) (2021)	406.97
SSB 33rd percentile biomass (tonnes)	280.89
SSB 66th percentiles biomass (tonnes)	317.06

Diagnosis of stock status:

- In overexploitation (F_{current}>F_{0.1})
- Relative high biomass (SSB_{current} > SSBiomass at 33rd percentile)

Advice and recommendation: Reduce F_{current} towards F_{0.1}

Figure 29. Comparison of the outputs of the previous year assessment (blue line) and updated assessment of this year (red line).

N: 29

Stock: Red mullet (*Mullus barbatus*)

GSA: 06

Author(s): García-Rodríguez, E.; Vivas, M.; Esteban, A.; Pérez-Gil, J. L; Tifoura, A; Meléndez, M.J.

Fishery: Both species of red mullet, *Mullus surmuletus* and *M. barbatus*, are exploited by trawl and artisanal fleets in GSA 06, although small gears (trammel nets and gillnets) account only for 5% of the total landings of these species (Demestre et al., 1997). Trawl fisheries developed along the continental shelf and upper slope are multi-specific. Small vessels (12-16m length) operate mainly on the shallow shelf targeting on red mullets, octopus, cuttlefish and sea breams. Medium and large vessels usually operates on deep continental shelf and slope areas targeting on hake and crustaceans, but some of these units can also operate on the shallow shelf depending on weather conditions or market prices. Red mullet is more intensively exploited from September to November coinciding with the recruitment period of this species (Martín et al., 1999). The total trawl fleet in the GSA 06 has declined from 810 boats in 1998 to 432 boats in 2021; around 30% of these boats regularly operate in shallow shelf.

According to official statistics, the fishery developed quickly during the seventies reaching a maximum of 1669 tons in the year 1982. Since then landings have widely oscillated around a mean value of 1193 tons (2004-2021) although a decreasing trend is observed. Catches in the period 2004-2010 were composed mainly by individuals of age groups 0 and 1. After the enforcement of the new mesh type in 2010 (40 mm square or alternatively 50 mm diamond) catches in 2011-2021 are composed mainly by individuals of age groups 1 and 2.

Data and parameters: The information used for the assessment are the total annual landings from official statistics, the annual catch in number by size class estimated by monthly port sampling and on board observers and the abundance index from MEDITS surveys. Growth parameters are those used in previous assessments by STECF and GFCM for GSA 06 (Demestre et al, 1997). Length-weight relationship and maturity ogive comes from Spanish DCF and the vector of natural mortality by age was calculated from Caddy's formula, using the PROBIOM Excel spreadsheet (Abella et al., 1997). Selectivity experiences carried out by the IEO with 40 mm diamond and square mesh in the cod-end were also used.

Assessment method: Statistical catch at age model (a4a), Y/R analysis and short term projections. FLR libraries under R language.

Model performance: Log catchability residuals and Retrospective analysis suggest that the model is consistent.

Results: indicate that average fishing mortality for ages 1-2 and catches shows a decreasing trend, while a stable trend in SSB and recruitment were identified during last year. $F_{current}$ (1.42) is higher than $F_{0.1}$ (0.25), chosen as proxy of FMSY, which indicates that red mullet stock in GSA 06 is in overexploitation with relative low biomass.

$F_{current}$ (F_{BAR} ages 1-2 (2021))	1.42
$F_{0.1}$ (present assessment)	0.25
SSB _{current} (tons)	837
SSB (33th)	589
SSB (66th)	791
$F_{current}/F_{0.1}$	5.69

Diagnosis of stock status:

- In overexploitation ($F_{current} > F_{0.1}$)
- Relative low biomass ($SSB_{current} < SSB_{biomass}$ at 33rd percentile)

Advice and recommendation: Reduce $F_{current}$ towards $F_{0.1}$

Figure 30: Comparison of the outputs of the previous year assessment (blue line) and updated assessment performed this year (red line).

N: 30

Stock: red mullet (*Mullus barbatus*)

GSA: 7

Summary sheet not received.

N: 31

Stock: red mullet (*Mullus barbatus*)

GSA: 9

Author(s): STECF EWG 22-09

Fishery: The fishing gears used to catch red mullet in GSA 9 together with other species (mixed catches) are gillnets (GNS), trammel nets (GTR) and bottom trawls (OTB).

Discard of red mullet in GSA 9 occurs mainly from the catches of bottom trawls (OTB). Discard data were available in 2006, and for all years since 2009. For the assessment purposes, in the years where discard data were missing, approximations were made taking into account percentage of catch discarded in previous and/or following year.

Data and parameters: Growth parameters of red mullet in GSA 9 were available from 2003 to 2021 from DCF data. For the aim of the stock assessment a set of von Bertalanffy parameters given by the average along the years was used. Considering the fact that the assignment of the age in the ALK considered the middle of the year as birth date of red mullet, while the a4a model was parameterized with calendar year, it was agreed to shift growth curve by adding 0.5 to t_0 for internal consistency in the stock assessment model. Natural mortality (M) was estimated according to Chen and Watanabe model (1989). An agreed vector of maturity was used for all the red mullet stocks in the West Med. DCF was the data source for data on catches, landings, discards, length frequency distributions and MEDITS index over 2004-2019. MEDITS data showed large variations between years. In 2017 and 2020, the survey was carried out in September-October. Due to the variability of survey timing, age 0 class was not included in the tuning indices used for the assessment. In addition, a sensitivity analysis was performed to show no significant effects of late surveys on the results of the assessment. Age slicing using the length frequency distributions of landings, discards and survey has been carried out by sex (in combination with sex ratio at length) model and then data were combined.

Assessment method: Statistical catch at age model (a4a) (Jardim et al. 2015) and FLBRP package. FLR libraries. The FLRef package was used to estimate biomass reference points.

Model performance: Log residuals of the catch and abundance indices related to outcomes of the best run did not show any particular trend.

Results: The estimated SSB and recruitment show a sharp increase in recent years giving the highest of the whole time series. This is consistent with the increase in total catch and the increase in the MEDITS abundance survey indices.

Fcurrent F_{bar} ages 1-3 (2021)	0.54
$F_{0.1}$ (present assessment)	0.50
SSBcurrent (tons)	1573
B_{MSY}	1846.1
B_{pa}	923.0
Blim	461.5
Fcurrent/ $F_{0.1}$	1.08

Diagnosis of stock status:

- Low overfishing, with (Fcurrent/ $F_{0.1}$ ratio below 1.33
- Current biomass is below $B_{F0.1}$, used as proxy for B_{MSY} , but above B_{pa} .

Advice and recommendation: Reduce fishing mortality

Figure 31. Comparison of the outputs of the previous years' assessments (purple, blue and green lines) and updated assessment performed this year (red line).

N: 32

Stock: red mullet (*Mullus barbatus*)

GSA: 10

Author(s): Isabella Bitetto, Loredana Casciaro, Walter Zupa, Danai Mantopoulou, Pierluigi Carbonara.

Fishery: The fishing gears used to catch red mullet in GSA 10 together with other species (mixed catches) are gillnets (GNS), trammel nets (GTR) and bottom trawls (OTB).

The discard data, in the years with no available information, were reconstructed on the basis of the discard data available, and included in the assessment.

Data and parameters: The information on the age-length key (ALK) and on the growth von Bertalanffy parameters was available from 2002 and appeared consistent with the paper of Carbonara et al. (2018) on age validation of red mullet in Adriatic Sea. Natural mortality (M) was estimated according to Chen and Watanabe model (1989). Maturity ogives by length and age were available from 2002 to 2021 by sex. DCF was the data source for landings, discards and MEDITS survey. MEDITS data show large variations between years. In 2017, the survey was carried out in October-November. Data on landings and discards in 2017 was incomplete. Catch of 2020 presented a large amount of old individuals that last year produced unreliable results. For this reason, for 2020 only the MEDITS was used, after the application of the sex ratio of the previous years (because in 2020 the sex ratio of the MEDITS was anomalous). The 2021 sampling is based on 1 trip in quarter 4 and 53 individuals measured, thus. Age 0 class was not included in the tuning indices used for the assessment because not intercepted every year, as done at WGSAD 2020 and 2021. An Fbar range between 1 and 3 was used, as in previous assessments. The landing before 2002 was collected from ISTAT.

Assessment method: The stochastic surplus production model in continuous time Spict (Pedersen et al., 2016) was used for the assessment. During the STECF EWG 22-09 the statistical catch at age model

(a4a) (Jardim et al. 2015) of last year was also updated and it was presented during the WGSAD 2022 for continuity.

Spict model was considered more appropriate for this stock, considering the poor catch at age information on the last 2 years, that do not allow to have a reliable overview of the recent status of the stock utilizing an age-structured model.

Considering that no information on the discard were available before 2002, the landing was used as proxy of the catch (discard <10%) in Spict. The catch data before 2002 were considered more uncertain respect to the one collected under DCF (weight = 5 before 2002).

Several attempts were made to build a Spict model already during STECF EWG 22-09 without reaching a final model; that work was completed for the WGSAD 2022 (held in December 2022).

Specifically it was noticed that the estimated value of r was too low (~ 0.09), thus a prior on resilience has been set on the basis of Fishbase (0.68). A prior on the ratio B/K was also applied.

2 runs were explored: 1) using the time series from 1972 to 2021; using the time series from 1985 to 2021.

Model performance: The a4a assessment showed trend in the biomass index along all the years, highlighting the unreliability of the model to estimate a reasonable perception of the population. The comparison with the assessment of last year was made with 2021 data, indicating a very different level of recruitment estimated in the assessment of this year. This is probably due to the missing information on recruitment from the commercial data in 2020 and 2021, that does not allow the model to fit the current level of recruitment. For this reason the results were not considered reliable.

Both Spict runs showed more robust results, highlighting a general improved perception of the stock in last years; the retrospective and the diagnostic plots do not show any particular trend and/or autocorrelation in the residuals. The checklist developed in the WKMSYSPICT 2021 was used to evaluate the performances of the two runs.

The results of the checklist highlighted that the short time series is more stable respect to the initial values, while the long time series allows to have a production curve that is more plausible.

Results: The estimated SSB and recruitment show an increase in recent years, current values are the highest of the time series. This is consistent with the increase in the MEDITS abundance indices and the decrease in the fishing mortality, the latter being 0.24 of the F_{MSY} . F displayed a decreasing trend all through the analyzed period, and is now below the reference point.

$F_{current}/F_{MSY}$ (2021)	0.24
B/B_{MSY}	1.5
SSB _{current} (tons)	5458
SSB (33 th)	1507
SSB (66 th)	3229

Diagnosis of stock status:

- Sustainably exploited ($F_c < F_{MSY}$;))
- Relative high biomass (SSB higher than the 66th percentile)

Advice and recommendation: On the basis of the stock assessment results it is advised to not increase fishing mortality.

N: 33

Stock: Red mullet (*Mullus barbatus*)

GSA: 11

Author(s): Bitetto I., Pesci P., Follesa M.C.

Fishery: Red mullet stock is mainly targeted by trawlers (OTB), gillnets (GNS) and trammel nets (GTR) in Sardinian waters. Red mullet represents about the 14% of the OTB, GNS, GTR Sardinian landing (DCF data 2019-2021).

Data and parameters: This is the first time that the stock is assessed. The assessment was carried out using standardized LFD abundance indices (N/km^2), GSA 11 (MEDITS data available from 1994 to 2021); length structure of catches by fishing segment and aggregated catches (landing and discard) from DCF (2005-2021). The Age-Length Key are under revision following Carbonara et al. 2018. The growth parameters used in this assessment are: females, $L_{inf}=29.41$ cm TL, $k=0.237$, $t_0=-0.752$; males: $L_{inf}=23.225$ cm TL, $k=0.31$, $t_0=-0.792$. Length-weight relationship comes from DCF. The maturity at age was assumed equal to 0 at age 0 and from age 1 equal to 1, as currently assumed in the STECF and GFCM stock assessment working groups for red mullet. The natural mortality vector was derived applying Chen & Watanabe method: M assumed equal to 1.38, 0.79, 0.58, 0.5, 0.44 from age 0 to age 4+.

Assessment method: As a first exploration, Extended Survivor Analysis (Darby and Flatman 1994, Shepherd 1999) was applied to catch and MEDITS indices from 2005 to 2021. A sensitivity analysis was carried out on the relevant settings of XSA model:

- $Q_{age} = 1, 2, 3$
- $R_{age} = -1, 0, 1$
- Shrinkage = 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2
- Number of years for shrinkage = 2, 3.

Model performance: The best run was selected according to residuals and retrospective patterns. The corresponding settings are: $q_{age}=3$; $r_{age}=1$; $fse=0.5$; $shkYrs=4$; $shkAges=2$. The results show an oscillating fishing mortality pattern, with current decrease in F , in line with the decrease in catches. This picture is consistent with the decrease in effort due to the EU Western Med MAP and the decrease in fishing mortality observed in red mullet of close areas (GSA 9, 10).

Results: Fishing mortality (F) shows an average value of 0.24 ($F_{bar}(1-3)$) in 2019-2021. The $F_{0.1}$ value estimated in the benchmark was 0.3.

Fcurrent (2019-2021)	0.24
F01	0.3
Fcurrent/F01	0.8
B current (tons) (average 2019-2021)	638
B 33% percentile(tons)	518
B 66% percentile (tons)	610

Figure 32. Plot of the assessment results.

Diagnosis of stock status:

- Underexploited ($F_{current} < F_{0.1}$)
- Relative high biomass (SSB current > SSB 66% percentile)

Advice and recommendation: It is recommended to not increase the fishing mortality.

N: 34

Stock: Red mullet (*Mullus barbatus*)

GSA: 12-14

Author(s): O. Ben Abdallah, N. Ben Hadj Hamida, M. Cherif, O. Jarboui

Fishery: The red Mullet *Mullus barbatus* is an important demersal species for commercial fisheries in the GSAs12-14. It is exploited by trawl and artisanal fleet. Small gears (trammel nets and Gillnets) account for 5% of the total landings of *M. barbatus* (average 2010-2021 period). Trawl fleet account 2629 tones (average 2010-2021 period).

Trawlers fishery exploits a highly diversified species assemblages, the main commercial species being the caramote prawn (*Penaeus kerathurus*), Striped mullet (*Mullus surmuletus*), Hake (*Merluccius merluccius*), sparid fish (*Pagellus erythrinus*, *Diplodus annularis*, *Sparus auratus*). Length catches of red mullet range between 8 and 26 cm total length (TL), with an average size of 14 cm TL.

Data and parameters: Stock assessment of *Mullus barbatus* was carried out using the official Tunisian catch data of bottom trawling in the two GSAs 12-14. Number-at-age data from experimental trawl

surveys carried out in the considered GSAs, were used as tuning data. The vector of natural mortality by age was calculated using the Gislason model. The biological parameters used were: $L_{\infty}= 25.96$, $k= 0.309$, $t_0 = -0.824$, $a=0.0044$, $b= 3.29$ for combined sexes. Maturity by age data was estimated using the maturity ogive parameters of *M. barbatus* female.

Assessment method: The assessment was performed using extended survivor analysis (XSA) as implemented in the FLR (fisheries libraries in R). Model settings in terms of shrinkages and catchability of the best benchmark model (GFCM Benchmark session on MUT, 2018) were assumed. According to the recommendations of the GFCM WG, current F was obtained as average three previous years (2018-20).

Model performance: Model residuals did not show any trend. Overall diagnostics are acceptable, and retrospective analysis is consistent.

Results: According to the recommendations of the GFCM WG, current $F_{(current)}$ was estimated as average of the last three years of the time series considered (i.e. 2018-2021) and equal to 1.47; $F_{0.1}$ was estimated using FLR routine. The result obtained in terms of stock status are reported in the table below.

$F_{current}$ (ages 0-2; 2019-2021)	1.51
$F_{0.1}$ (2018)	0.47
$F_{current}/F_{0.1}$	3.23
Current SSB (tonnes)	2545.6
33 rd percentile biomass (tonnes)	2698.5
66 th percentile biomass (tonnes)	2877.6

Diagnosis of stock status: In High Overfishing Status and Relative low Biomass.

Advice and recommendations:

- Reduce $F_{current}$ towards $F_{0.1}$
- - Progressive reduction of fishing effort.

Comparative plot:

Figure 32. Comparison of the outputs of the previous year assessment and update assessment performed this year.

N: 35

Stock: Red mullet (*Mullus barbatus*)

GSA: 15

Authors: J. Mifsud, M. Gambin, K. Camilleri, V. Gancitano, D. Scannella, F. Falsone, S. Ben Meriem, O. Ben Abdallah, E. Arneri, L. Ceriola, O. Jarboui, S. Vitale, F. Fiorentino

Fishery: Red mullet is one of the main coastal demersal resources in the Mediterranean. It is fished by otter trawls, trammel nets and gillnets (Voliani, 1999; Griffiths *et al.*, 2007). Red mullet is caught together with other important species, such as *Mullus surmuletus* (striped red mullet), *Merluccius merluccius* (European hake), *Pagellus spp.* (seabreams, pandoras), *Uranoscopus scaber* (stargazer), *Raja spp.* (rays), *Trachinus spp.* (weevers), *Octopus vulgaris* (common octopus), *Sepia officinalis* (common cuttlefish), *Eledone spp.* (horned and musky octopuses), and *Lophius spp.* (anglerfish). Red mullet is fished almost exclusively by trawling on shelf bottoms. Based on available knowledge red mullets inhabiting the continental shelf of GSA 15 is considered as a stock unit, with an average annual landing for the period 2009-2021 of about 14 tonnes.

Data and parameters: A revised length frequency distribution series from commercial landings was proposed for the update of the 2020 assessment. Years with few data points were based on LFDs from the closest available year and raising to the landings was done by length class using $a=0.0078$, $b=3.0135$ for combined sexes for the length-weight conversion. The obtained number at length from commercial landings and from the MEDITS survey were converted to catch number-at-age and survey number-at-age using ALK from GSA 16. The MUT Maltese landings were used, and the natural mortality was estimated by the Gislason method.

Assessment method: The assessment was performed using extended survivor analysis (XSA) as implemented in the FLR (fisheries libraries in R). According to the recommendations of the GFCM WG, current F was obtained as the geometric mean of the last three years (2019-2021).

Model performance: Overall diagnostics are acceptable.

Results: The result obtained in terms of stock status are reported in the table below. Current $F_{(1-3)}$ was estimated as the geometric mean of the last 3 years. $F_{0.1}$ was estimated using FLR routine; to allow comparisons the model was also run with 2009-2017 revised LFD data to replicate the benchmark and this reference point was used below. The SSB in 2021 was below the 33th percentile of the SSB time series.

$F_{(1-3)}$ current	1.13
$F_{0.1}$ (Revised benchmark assessment)	0.295
$F_{\text{current}}/F_{0.1}$	3.82
Current SSB in 2021 (tonnes) from XSA	13.47
33 rd percentile SSB (tonnes) – 2021	43.75
66 th percentile SSB (tonnes) - 2021	79.36

Diagnosis of stock status: In high overfishing with a relative low biomass.

Advice and recommendations: Decrease fishing mortality. The group suggested a new benchmark considering other stock models e.g. a4a and the possibility of running a joint assessment for GSAs 15 and 16.

N: 36

Stock: Red mullet (*Mullus barbatus*)

GSA: 16

Author(s): D. Scannella, V. Gancitano, F. Falsone, S. Vitale, L., F. Fiorentino

Fishery: Red mullet, *Mullus barbatus*, is an important species commercial for demersal fisheries in the Strait of Sicily (South-central Mediterranean Sea). It is fished almost exclusively by trawling on shelf bottoms. Based on available knowledge (Gargano et al., 2017) red mullets inhabiting the continental shelf of GSA 16 are considered as a stock unit with an average annual landings for the period 2006-2021 of about 500 tons.

Data and parameters: The data and the parameters used for the stock assessment in the GSA 16 were: i) Catch composition and total catch (2006-2021) according to official national data from Italy; ii) Age-Length Key from commercial catch iii) tuning data from Medits surveys and iv) biological parameters (sex combined): $L_{\infty} = 24.1\text{cm}$, $k = 0.42$, $t_0 = -0.8$, $a = 0.0087$ and $b = 3.07711$. The natural mortality as vector by age group was estimated through the Gislason's method. $F_{0.1}$ was estimated performing a Y/R analysis by FLBRP in R whereas for XSA $F_{0.1}$ estimated during the last benchmark was adopted.

Assessment method: The assessment was performed through extended survivor analysis (XSA) as implemented in the FLR (fisheries libraries in R) using catch data from Italy and Medits data for GSAs 16 as tuning. In addition, a statistical catch at age (a4a), a surplus production model (Bayesian Schaefer model, BSM) and Just Another Bayesian Biomass Assessment (JABBA) model were explored to evaluate the status of the stock.

Results: The XSA model, implemented with the same settings adopted in the last benchmark (2018), provided unreliable results in terms of F levels and SSB as well as poor consistency in the retrospective analysis. For this reason, the group agreed that XSA model was not further suitable to provide scientific advice. Instead, considering the reliability of the a4a results as well as the good diagnostic quality of the selected model, the group decided to consider a4a outcomes, including the $F_{0.1}$ estimation, for providing quantitative scientific advice. The stock status perception provided by a4a was also corroborated by means Jabba model depicting a stock in a sustainable exploitation status.

According to the recommendations of the GFCM WG, current $F_{\text{bar}(1-3)}$ was estimated as geometrical mean of the last three years of the time series considered (i.e. 2019-2021) and equal to 0.23. The estimation of $F_{0.1}$ was 0.45. The main results obtained by a4a in terms of stock status are reported in the table below.

F_{current}	0.23
$F_{0.1}$	0.45
$F_{\text{curr}}/F_{0.1}$	0.52
Current SSB (tons) (average 3y, 2019-'21)	1761
33 rd percentile biomass (tons)	1766
66 th percentile biomass (tons)	1921

Diagnosis of stock status: The current exploitation level is sustainably exploited ($F_{\text{curr}} < F_{0.1}$) with relative low spawning stock biomass ($SSB_{\text{curr}} < 33^{\text{th}}$). The trawl survey data (MEDITS) time series indicated relatively intermediate biomass ($33^{\text{th}} < BI_{\text{curr}} < 66^{\text{th}}$) of the stock in 2021.

Advice and recommendation: It is recommended to not increase the fishing mortality on the species and maintain the trawling ban in late summer-early autumn to avoid the catch of juveniles. In light of the issues encountered in using the XSA model, a new benchmark was requested.

N: 37

Stock: Red mullet (*Mullus barbatus*)

GSA: 19

Author(s): STECF EWG 22-16

Fishery: The fishing gears used to catch red mullet in GSA 19 together with other species (mixed catches) are gillnets (GNS), trammel nets (GTR) and bottom trawls (OTB) mainly operating within 200 m of depth. Discard of red mullet in GSA 19 occurs mainly from the catches of bottom trawls (OTB). Discards of red mullet in the GSA 19 are reported for 2009, 2011-2021. The volume of discards is rather variable among years, but anyway discards no greater than 1% of the total catch.

Data and parameters: Growth parameters were estimated following the age reading procedure described in Carbonara et al. (2018) and are consistent with those estimated in GSA 18 in the same paper and in DCF. The length-to-weight ratio is from DCF and the vector of natural mortality by age was calculated using the method of Chen and Watanabe. The proportion of mature males and females was calculated following Carbonara et al. (2015) as agreed upon during the benchmark meeting for the red mullet assessment in GSAs 17 and 18. DCF was the data source for data on catches, landings, discards, length frequency distributions and MEDITS index over 2002-2021. MEDITS data showed large variations between years. Although the trends of the indices show fluctuations from year to year, an increase in density and biomass indices has been observed in recent years. Indices show important recruitment peaks in 2007, 2014 and 2017 due to the displacement of survey in later period (August, September, December) that it is the recruitment period for red mullet. Due to the variability of survey timing, age 0 class was not included in the tuning indices used for the assessment. In addition, a sensitivity analysis was performed to show no significant effects of late surveys on the results of the

assessment. Age slicing using the length frequency distributions of landings, discards and survey has been carried out by sex (in combination with sex ratio at length) model and then data were combined.

Assessment method: Stock assessments were performed applying an Extended Survivor Analysis (XSA) and an Assessment for All (a4a) methods calibrated with fishery independent survey abundance indices (MEDITS). The differences between methods are minor and do not change the perception of the state of stock or fishery. Both methods were based on the size composition of landings and discards and were taken from DCF. Von Bertalanffy growth parameters, length-weight relationship and natural mortality vector, were taken from parameters used for red mullet in GSA 19 in the previous assessment (GFCM WGSAD 2021) based on the results of GFCM WGSAD benchmark session for the assessment of red mullet in GSAs 12–16 and 19 (2018).

Model performance: Based on the results of retrospectives and residuals both model showed instability in recent years. Survey sampling period (MEDITS) has been done in different year periods. The displacement of MEDITS survey to August (2007), September (2014), December 2017 and October 2020 that it is the recruitment period for red mullet, difficult the tuning of the VPA. The two models run: XSA and a4a, agree on SSB and catch time series. In terms of recruitment, XSA shows an increase in the last year, while a4a shows a decreasing trend. Fbar shows a decreasing trend for both

Results: The FLBRP library available in FLR was used to estimate F0.1 based on the stock object resulting from the assessment results. The value of F0.1 (Fbar 1-3) calculated by the FLBRP package using the XSA assessment results equals 0.38. The current F values (2021) calculated by the XSA model is 0.53, indicating that the stock is intermediate overfishing status ($F_{curr}/F_{0.1} = 1.394$). These results should be viewed with caution due to the instability of the retrospectives.

Fcurrent F _{bar} ages 1-3 (2021)	0.53
F _{0.1} (present assessment)	0.38
SSBcurrent (tons)	611.49
B _{0.33}	519
B _{0.66}	686
B _{MSY}	Not defined
B _{pa}	Not defined
Blim	Not defined
Fcurrent/F _{0.1}	1.394

Diagnosis of stock status: Intermediate overfishing, with ($F_{current}/F_{0.1}$ ratio is between 1.33 and 1.66

Advice and recommendation: Reduce fishing mortality

Figure 32. Comparison of the outputs of of two model runs; A4A and XSA

N: 38

Stock: Red mullet (*Mullus barbatus*)

GSA: 20

Author(s): G. Tserpes & D. Mantopoulou – Palouka

Fishery: Red mullet is exploited by bottom trawlers and various artisanal fisheries using gillnets. Most catches come from the Greek fleets exploiting the area and the majority originates from bottom trawlers (~80percent). The Greek bottom trawl fishery has multi-species characteristics and, similarly to most Mediterranean demersal trawl fisheries, captures more than 100 commercial species. However, few species, such as red mullets, European hake and shrimps, compose the main bulk of landings, with red mullet being one of the most important targets.

Data and parameters: Biological information on growth, i.e. the von Bertalanffy parameters, as well the length-weight relationship were derived within DCF. Natural mortality vector was estimated using Chen and Watannabe method while maturity vectors were derived within DCF. The official landings data as reported through the HELSTAT were used in the assessment. Catch at size data, as reported in DCF, were used in the assessment. Both catch numbers at length and index number at length were sliced using the l2a age slicing function of FLR.

Assessment method: A statistical catch at age model (a4a) was used and the FLBRP package for the yield per recruit analysis, both part of the FLR library. The assessment was carried out over the period 2003-2021, calibrated with the fishery independent abundance index of the MEDITS survey. The same sub-models with the previous year were selected regarding fishing mortality and survey catchability, while a geometric mean model, instead of a year smoother was assumed for the stock-recruitment relationship.

Model performance: Residuals considered acceptable, and the same was observed for the retrospective plot and the other diagnostics (hindcasting and runs test).

Results: In the last decade, biomass shows generally increasing trends, while F is decreasing.

F_{current} (F_{bar} ages 1-3 in 2021)	0.40
$F_{0.1}$ (present assessment)	0.30

SSB _{current} (2021, tons)	603
SSB (33 th percentile)	365
SSB (66 th percentile)	441
F _{current} /F _{0.1}	1.33

Diagnosis of stock status: In overexploitation, with relatively high biomass.

Advice and recommendations: Reduce fishing mortality towards F_{0.1}.

Figure 33. Red mullet in GSA 20. Estimated recruitment, SSB, Catch and Fbar (ages: 1- 3) and their respective confidence limits. Blue line represents the observed catch.

N: 39

Stock: Red mullet (*Mullus barbatus*)

GSA: 22

Author(s): G. Tserpes & D. Mantopoulou – Palouka

Fishery: Red mullet is exploited by bottom trawlers and various artisanal fisheries using gillnets. Most catches come from the Greek fleets exploiting the area and the majority originates from bottom trawlers (~70-80%). The Greek bottom trawl fishery has multi-species characteristics and similarly to most Mediterranean demersal trawl fisheries, captures more than 100 commercial species. However, few species, such as red mullets, European hake and shrimps, compose the main bulk of landings, with red mullet being one of the most important targets.

Data and parameters: Biological information on growth, i.e. the von Bertalanffy parameters, as well the length-weight relationship were derived within DCF. The natural mortality and mortality vectors kept similar with those used in the previous assessments of the stock. The official landings data of fleets exploiting the area, as reported through FAO, were used in the assessment. Catch at size data, as reported in DCF, were used in the assessment. Both catch numbers at length and index number at length were sliced using the l2a age slicing function of FLR.

Assessment method: A statistical catch at age model (a4a) was used and FLBRP package for yield per recruit analysis, both part of the FLR library. The assessment was carried out over the period 2003-2021, calibrated with the fishery independent abundance index of the MEDITS survey. To select the final model for assessment, combinations of various options for submodels regarding fishing mortality, survey catchability and stock-recruitment were investigated. The best model was selected in the basis of better residuals and retrospective patterns.

Model performance: Residuals considered acceptable, and the same was observed for the retrospective plot and the other diagnostics (hindcasting and runs test).

Results: In the last decade, biomass shows increasing trends, while F shows a constant decreasing trend.

F_{current} (F_{bar} ages 1-3 in 2021)	0.25
$F_{0.1}$ (present assessment)	0.29
SSB_{current} (2021, tons)	6535
SSB (33 th percentile)	3470
SSB (66 th percentile)	4052
$F_{\text{current}}/F_{0.1}$	0.86

Diagnosis of stock status: Sustainably exploited, with relatively high biomass.

Advice and recommendations: Not to increase fishing mortality

Figure 34. Red mullet in GSA 22. Estimated recruitment, SSB, Catch and Fbar (ages: 1- 3) and their respective confidence limits. Blue line represents the observed catch

N: 40

Stock: Red mullet (*Mullus barbatus*)

GSA: 24

Author(s): Savaş Kılıç

Fishery: *Mullus barbatus* is an important species for commercial fisheries, as it is one of the most landed demersal species in GSA 24. 176 bottom trawls and 1004 gillnets boats fished during 2021 in GSA 24. About 80% of *Mullus barbatus* is fished by bottom trawls and the most of the remaining part

fished by gillnets. The stock in the eastern side is mainly exploited by bottom trawls, whereas in the west bottom trawling is very limited due to 3 miles trawl exclusion zone where *Mullus barbatus* is mainly fished by artisanal fishers in negligible quantities.

Data and parameters: Official landing data of *Mullus barbatus* by region used in the assessment was obtained from Turkish Statistical Institute. Biological and monthly length frequencies data were collected from commercial fisheries by Mediterranean Fisheries Research, Production, and Training Institute (MEDFRI) between 2018 and 2022 Von Bertalanffy growth parameters reported in the previous stock assessment were used. L50 were estimated using the biological data from the MEDFRI.

Assessment method: LBB and LB-SPR length-based data limited stock assessment models were used in addition to catch-based data limited stock assessment model CMSY.

Results:

Fmsy	0.361
Fc	0.347
Fc/Fmsy	0.959

Diagnosis of stock status: Possibly overexploited with low fishing mortality.

Advice and recommendations: Do not increase fishing mortality

Kobe plot:

N: 41

Stock: Red mullet (*Mullus barbatus*)

GSA: 25

Author(s): Ioannis Thasitis Charis Charilaou

Fishery: Red mullet is an important commercial species in GSA 25, exploited by trawlers and polyvalent small scale vessels using set nets. In both fisheries the species is exploited with a number of other demersal species. In recent years trawl landings proportion is significantly higher. Over the period 1985-2020 catches showed fluctuations with a declining trend for SSF; from 2005 the values remained at similarly low levels. Landings from trawlers show a decreasing trend as well, with a sharp decrease in 1995; from 2012 landings increased slightly and remain at the same levels ever since. During the period of the assessment (2005 – 2022), there have been changes in the two fisheries exploiting the species, mainly reduction on the number of fishing licenses as well as increase of mesh

sizes of set and bottom trawl nets. Catches of red mullet over the assessment period had a declining trend, with highest value in 2007 (47.4t) and lowest value in 2020 (10.1t). In 2011 the trawler fleet was reduced to 2 vessels, while for the small-scale fleet a scrapping program of 174 vessels took place from 2013 to 2015 reducing the number of active vessels to 327.

Data and parameters: The assessment was carried out using official data on commercial catches (2005-2021) and abundance indices from the Cyprus Medits survey (2005-2022). Catch-at-length data were converted into catch-at-age data using Age Length Keys, derived from direct otolith observations of the Cyprus Data Collection Programme under the EU Data Collection Framework. Growth parameters, length-weight relationship and maturity ogive at age were based on data from the Cyprus National Data Collection Programme. A vector of natural mortality by age was used, calculated from Caddy’s formula, using the PRODBIOM Excel spreadsheet (Abella et al., 1997).

Assessment method: The stock assessment method used is SAM a Statistical Catch at Age state space model, updated with the new set of data. State space was preferred due to its inherit capacity to account for gaps in index data (Medits 2014) and the possibility to run without catch-at -age estimations for certain years (2022). Reference point $F_{0.1}$ was estimated based on a Yield per Recruit analysis. A stochastic short-term projection assuming status quo scenario was applied. The analysis on SAM performed using the original code of SAM available at dedicated GitHub (<https://github.com/fishfollower/SAM>). Supportive analysis under Length-based approaches (LBSPR) and an empirical indicator was also applied to ensure the accuracy of the derived results. All methods were showing a similar stock condition.

Model performance: The residuals, the retrospective analysis and a leave out run did not show any model violations.

Results: Spawning stock biomass follows a decreasing trend from 2005 to 2009, it then follows a fluctuating upward pattern up until 2013. From 2014 reduced down to the lowest point of the timeseries in 2018. From 2019 onward an increasing trend is occurring. Recruitment follows a down trend from the beginning of the assessment up until 2018 were it reaches the lowest point of the analysis. It then follows an increasing trend until the end of the analysis. Catches follow a pattern very similar to recruitment. Fishing mortality fluctuates at high level from the beginning of the assessment with two picks in 2008 and 2015. From 2016 F starts to decline to the lowest value in 2020. A slight increase is then follows. A relative figure with all relative graphs is included at the end of the summary.

Current fishing mortality ($F_{\text{current}(2-4)}$) as calculated for 2022 has a value of 0.76. This fishing mortality value corresponds to both fishing fleets that exploit red mullet.

$F_{\text{current}}(\text{ages } 2-4)$	0.76
$F_{0.1}$	0.27
$F_{\text{current}}/F_{0.1}$	2.8
Biomass index (SSB_{2022})(tons)	27
SSB biomass index 33 rd percentile (tons)	25
SSB biomass index 66 th percentile (tons)	30

Diagnosis of stock status: The stock seems to be in overfishing with intermediate biomass.

Advice and recommendation: Reduce fishing mortality.

N: 42

Stock: Striped red mullet (*Mullus surmuletus*)

GSA: 05

Author(s): Beatriz Guijarro, Marc Farré, Virginia Soldán and Núria Zaragoza

Fishery: In the Balearic Islands (western Mediterranean), commercial trawlers develop up to four different fishing tactics, which are associated with the shallow shelf, deep shelf, upper slope and middle slope (Guijarro and Massutí 2006; Ordines et al. 2006), mainly targeted to: (i) *Spicara smaris*, *Mullus surmuletus*, *Octopus vulgaris* and a mixed fish category on the shallow shelf (50-80 m); (ii) *Merluccius merluccius*, *Mullus* spp., *Zeus faber* and a mixed fish category on the deep shelf (80-250 m); (iii) *Nephrops norvegicus*, but with an important by-catch of big *M. merluccius*, *Lepidorhombus* spp., *Lophius* spp. and *Micromesistius poutassou* on the upper slope (350-600 m) and (iv) *Aristeus antennatus* on the middle slope (600-750 m). The striped red mullet, *M. surmuletus*, is one of the target species in the shallow shelf, although it is also caught in the deep shelf. It is also the target species of part of the artisanal fleet, being caught during the second semester of the year mainly by trammel nets but also by gillnets.

Data and parameters: Size composition of commercial trawl catches and official landings (2000-2021) and indexes from bottom trawl surveys (2001-2022). All information was recomputed from a natural to an 'artificial' year, from 1st July to 30th June. Final year used corresponds to July 2021 to June 2022 and 2022 survey. Growth parameters were computed from otholith reading in the study area. Length-weight relationship and maturity ogive were obtained in the area from monthly biological samplings in the Spanish National Data Collection Programme. M vector was updated using Gisalson.

Assessment method: A statistical catch-at-age model (a4a) was used. Yield per recruit analysis and short-term forecast were carried out. The assessment is an update from the previous year (Figure below).

Model performance: The best model showed a good fit for the commercial data but poor for the surveys. Residuals did not show any trend but the retrospective for F show overestimation.

Results: Recruitment showed a decreasing trend between 2004 and 2011, an increasing trend since then. Spawning stock biomass showed a decreasing trend between 2006 and 2013, with an increasing trend since them. F showed the lowest values of the data series in the last year.

F_{current} (2020, ages 1-3)	0.50
$F_{0.1}$	0.24
$F_{\text{current}}/F_{0.1}$	2.06
SSB (2020, tons)	322
33 th percentile SSB (tons)	285
66 th percentile SSB(tons)	373

Diagnosis of stock status: The stock is in overexploitation, with relatively intermediate biomass.

Advice and recommendation: To reduce fishing mortality.

Figure 34. Comparison of the outputs of the previous year assessment (red line) and updated assessment performed this year (green line). Blue line is real catches.

N: 43

Stock: Norway lobster (*Nephrops norvegicus*)

GSA: 05 – Balearic Islands

Author(s): Beatriz Guijarro, Marc Farré and Núria Zaragoza

Fishery: In the Balearic Islands, commercial bottom trawlers develop up to four different fishing tactics, which are associated with the shallow shelf, deep shelf, upper slope and middle slope, mainly targeted to: (i) *Spicara smaris*, *Mullus surmuletus*, *Octopus vulgaris* and a mixed fish category on the shallow shelf (50-80 m); (ii) *Merluccius merluccius*, *Mullus* spp., *Zeus faber* and a mixed fish category on the deep shelf (80-250 m); (iii) *Nephrops norvegicus*, but with an important by-catch of big *Merluccius merluccius*, *Lepidorhombus* spp., *Lophius* spp. and *Micromesistius poutassou* on the upper slope (350-600 m) and (iv) *Aristeus antennatus* on the middle slope (600-750 m). *N. norvegicus* is a target species with a high economic importance.

Data and parameters: Size composition of commercial trawl catches and official landings (2002-2021), indexes from bottom trawl surveys (2002-2021). Growth parameters, length-weight relationship and maturity ogive obtained in the study area (Guijarro et al., 2013). Length was transformed to age by sex combined.

Assessment method: Extended Survivor Analysis (XSA, FLR libraries), Statistical Catch-At-Age SCAA (a4a, FLR libraries) and Yield per Recruit (Y/R, FLRBRP package). Final advice was provided based on a4a.

Model performance: Model residuals did not show any trend. Overall diagnostics are acceptable and retrospective analysis is consistent.

Results: Recruitment showed a decreasing trend since 2007, with minimum values in 2020 and a slight recovery in 2021. SSB showed a decreasing trend until 2017 and a slight increase since then. F values showed higher values in the updated assessment. (Figure below).

F_{current} (2021, ages 2-7)	0.23
$F_{0.1}$ (2021)	0.24
$F_{\text{current}}/F_{0.1}$	0.97
Current SSB (tons)	33
33 th percentile biomass (tons)	37
66 th percentile biomass (tons)	56

Diagnosis of stock status: Sustainable exploited, with relatively low biomass.

Advice and recommendation: Not to increase fishing mortality

Figure 35. Comparison of the outputs of the previous year assessment (red line) and updated assessment performed this year (green line) for *N. norvegicus* in GSA 5. The blue line represents the real catches.

N: 44

Stock: Norway lobster (*Nephrops norvegicus*)

GSA: 06

Author(s): Antonio Esteban, Encarnación García, Miguel Vivas & Amina Tifoura

Fishery: Trawl fleets fishing effort in the ports were quite stable for the period studied with small variations of the number of vessels in the recent years. Vessels length was between 12-24 m. The gears used corresponded to a trawl net 60 and 100 longest rope. The vertical opening was between 1-3 m. The cod end mesh size used was a squared 40 mm of mesh opening. The net was rigged two doors between 500-800 kgs. Trawl fleet in the four ports do daily trips with an unique haul directed to the red shrimp, with a duration between 5-7 hours. The number of harbours with Norway lobster fleets is 31 for the whole area, and the number of boats in this area is 344. Discards of Norway lobster are null. In 2021, landings were around 199 tonnes and total effort over 18128 fishing days by year and CPUE medium, 10,9 kgs/day

Data and parameters: Size composition of commercial trawl catches, official landings and data from MEDITS surveys (2009-2021). Growth parameters from L/W and Age/L relationships from Data Collection Framework (2013-15). M vector from ProdBiom (Abella et al, 1997)

Assessment method: Statistical catch-at-age – SCAA (a4a, FLR libraries), FLBRP package for yield-per-recruit analysis and Flash package for short-term forecast.

Model performance: Log catchability residuals and Retrospective analysis suggest that the model is consistent.

Results: Stock biomass showed oscillations for the entire data series, with a general decreasing trend.

Also recruitment is decreasing, F increase last year with fluctuation along the time series studied.

$F_{\text{current}} (F_{\text{bar } 2-6})$ 2021	0.44±0.11
$F_{0.1}$ (2021)	0.14
$F_{\text{current}}/F_{0.1}$	3.14
Current SSB (tonnes) 2021	286±67
33 rd percentile SSB (tonnes)	399
66 th percentile SSB (tonnes)	601

Diagnosis of stock status: In overexploitation, with relatively low biomass.

Advice and recommendations:

- Reduce F_{current} towards $F_{0.1}$
- Reduction of fishing effort.

Figure 35. Comparison of the outputs of the previous year assessment (red line) and revised assessment performed this year (blue line)

N: 45

Stock: Norway lobster (*Nephrops norvegicus*)

GSA: 9

Author(s): STECF EWG 22-09

Fishery: Due to a lack of information about the structure of *N. norvegicus* population in the western Mediterranean, this stock was assumed to be confined within the GSA 9 boundaries.

Landings of Norway lobster in GSA 9 in the period 1994-2002 were gathered from the Italian official statistics (prior to DCR/DCF) which were collected and stored under the RECFISH project (Ligas, 2019). Although the bulk of the production in GSA 9 is coming from the trawl fisheries (mostly demersal species and mixed demersal and deep-water species trawling), other fisheries (mostly gill nets) provide some contribution to the total production. Discards of Norway lobster are low. Low values of discards (from OTB) are reported in GSA 9 from 2009 onwards. Despite the low values of discards, LFDs are available, and the data were included into the stock assessment.

Data and parameters: In *N. norvegicus*, there is a difference in growth between males and females, with males attaining greater lengths at ages and maximum sizes compared to females. Several sets of VBGF parameters have been reported. Also, for the Length-Weight relationship, several sets of parameters by sex are provided for GSA 9. The VBGF and LW relationship parameters used for the assessment are summarized in the following table.

		Units	Females	Males
VBGF parameters	L_{∞}	mm	56.0	72.1
	K	years ⁻¹	0.21	0.17
	t_0	years	0.0	0.0
LW relationship	A	mm/g	0.00032	0.00038
	B	mm/g	3.24848	3.18164

A vector of proportion of mature by age was computed as a weighted average of the vectors available from the DCF database in GSA 9. A natural mortality vector was estimated by sex using the Chen and Watanabe equation and the growth parameters described above. A combined natural mortality vector was then computed as a weighted average of the vectors by sex.

Assessment method: Statistical catch at age model (a4a) (Jardim et al. 2015) and FLBRP package. FLR libraries. The FLRef package was used to estimate biomass reference points.

Model performance: Some pattern in the residuals from the tuning index (Meditis survey). The assessment is mostly driven by the information provided by the catches.

Results: The estimated SSB shows an increasing trend in recent years giving the highest of the whole time series. This is consistent with the increase in total catch and the increase in the MEDITS abundance survey indices.

F _{current} F _{bar} ages 2-6 (2021)	0.167
F _{0.1} (present assessment)	0.11
SSB _{current} (tons)	402.8
B _{MSY}	927
B _{pa}	463

Blim	232
Fcurrent/F0.1	1.53

Diagnosis of stock status:

- The stock is in overfishing.
- The current biomass is below BMSY and Bpa, but it is above Blim.

Advice and recommendation: Reduce fishing mortality.

Figure 36. Comparison of the outputs of the previous years' assessments (blue and green lines) and updated assessment performed this year (red line). In 2019, a larger number of knots in the tensor in the F submodel was used, thus determining.

N: 46

Stock: Norway lobster (*Nephrops norvegicus*)

GSA: 17

Authors: Angelini S., Arneri E., Belardinelli A., Cacciamani R., Canduci, Cardinale M., Casini, M., Chiarini M., Colella S., Cvitanic D., Domenichetti F., Donato F., Giuliani G., Grilli F., Guicciardi S., Isajlović I., Manfredi C., Martinelli M., Masnadi F., Medvešek P., Panfili M., Penna P., Polidori P., Russo T., Santojanni A., Scarcella G., Scarpini P., Tesauro C., Vrgoč N., Zacchetti L.

Fishery: In the Northern-Central Adriatic (GSA 17), the catch of Norway lobster fluctuates significantly according to depth, time of day and night (circadian fluctuation), and period of the year (seasonal fluctuation). This is mainly due to the behavior of this species, which digs burrows on sandy/muddy bottoms and leaves them mainly in search of food or for mating (e.g. younger individuals and berried females spend most of their time inside the burrows). As a result, different parts of the population are accessible to fishing gear at different times of day. Seasonal fluctuations exist for the same reason; the catch is normally higher in spring, when the sex ratio is more balanced or slightly in favor of females. GSA 17 landings of Norway lobster increased from the 1980s until the first half of the 1990s when a marked negative trend was established until 2002, in the following years the exploitation increased

again with a peak in 2005. In the last decade a worrying decreasing pattern has been observed, which lead to total landings (Italy and Croatia) of approximately 450 tons per year in 2020 and 2021. The majority of Norway lobster catch is due to bottom trawl nets, while a small portion is caught by pots within the Croatian channels.

Data and parameters: In the Northern-Central Adriatic Sea this species is generally characterized by spatially segregated subpopulations (or stocklets) with little or no exchange among them. Differences in Norway lobster length frequency distributions are reported among the ground off Ancona, the northern Adriatic channels, and the Pomo/Jabuka Pits. Numerous studies carried out in GSA 17 have highlighted that the Norway lobster has different growth rates and sizes at first maturity depending on the portion of GSA 17 considered as well as differences in growth by sex. Therefore, a spatially explicit model by sex was used, which has as input official statistics from Italy and Croatia in term of landings and size frequency distribution. The Italian dataset was divided in Pomo/Jabuka Pits area and rest of GSA 17 (mainly Northern Adriatic) following the methodology developed by Russo *et al.* (2018). Croatian data are instead available directly by fishing ground. VBGF parameters were taken from literature by sex and area. Natural mortality vectors by age, sex and area were estimated as an average of different methods using the Barefoot Ecologist’s Toolbox (<http://barefootecologist.com.au/>). The fleet considered in the present assessment were bottom otter trawls in Italy and Croatia. Abundance indices and LFDs were also derived from fishery independent datasets for the two areas identified within GSA 17. MEDITS datasets, separately for Italy and Croatia, were used for the Northern area (outside the Pomo/Jabuka Pits zone). For the Pomo/Jabuka Pits area, total abundances from the UWTV survey, as well as standardised indices and LFDs from specific trawl surveys carried out to monitor Norway lobster and other associated species in the Pomo Fishery Restricted Area (FRA) were used. Indeed, Generalized Additive Models (GAMs) were built to standardise Catch Per Unit Effort obtained from the latter surveys and used to investigate the effect of some environmental and fishery covariates on the spatial distribution and abundance of *N. norvegicus* within the Pomo Pits on trawl surveys carried out within Pomo/Jabuka Pits (Chiarini *et al.* 2022).

Assessment method: An integrated approach (last version SS3.3) to model the size structure data available by year for Norway lobster with 2 areas, 2 sexes and 2 growth morph was used. SS3 uses forward projection of population in the “statistical catch-at-age” approach. Double normal selectivity ogives were applied for the commercial and survey fleets.

Model performance: No particular trends were evidenced in residuals. Run test on all fleets and survey data were considered acceptable with the exception of MEDITS series outside Pomo/Jabuka Pits in Croatia both in the term of biomass index and mean length and of trawl survey series in Pomo/Jabuka Pits in term of mean length only. Retrospective analysis showed some discrepancy, but the values of Mohn rho test were on the limit to be acceptable for crustacean. Finally, the hindcasting was not considered adequate in the case of MEDITS data. Therefore, short-term forecast were not estimated.

Results: The final results of the model reported for 2021 a SSB of 592 tons and an estimated current F of 0.30.

$F_{\text{current}} (F_{\text{bar } 3-6} \text{ in } 2021)$	0.30 (± 0.10)
$F_{40\%} (2021)$	0.42
$F_{\text{current}}/F_{40\%}$	0.71
Current SSB (tonnes)	592 (± 157)
$SSB_{40\%}$ (tonnes)	761
$SSB_{\text{current}}/SSB_{40\%}$	0.78

Diagnosis of stock status: Considering the results of the analyses conducted, Norway lobster in GSA 17 is subjected to sustainable exploitation being the current $F(3-6)$ estimates with SS3 model of 0.30,

lower than the proposed reference point ($F_{40\%} = 0.42$). Based on the spawning stock biomass level (SSB), the stock results in an overexploited state of low biomass being the current SSB estimated by the SS3 model 592 tons; below the reference $SSB_{40\%}=761$ tons. In particular, a clear strong reduction of the population outside Pomo/Jabuka Pits is evident from the outputs.

Advice and recommendations: Reduce fishing mortality

Figure 37. Status advice plot for NEP 17 showing stock trajectories of Recruitment (N. ind. x 1000 Age 0), SSB (Tons), Landings (Tons) and Fishing mortality with associated uncertainty implemented with rapid delta-Multivariate lognormal approximation with to generate joint error distributions, compared to the estimated reference points.

Figure 38. Status advice plot for NEP 17 by area showing stock trajectories of Recruitment (N. ind. x 1000 Age 0), SSB (Tons), Landings (Tons) and Fishing mortality compared to the estimated reference points.

N: 47

Stock: Blackspot seabream (*Pagellus bogaraveo*)

GSA: 01 and 03 (Strait of Gibraltar target fishery)

Author(s): Juan Gil Herrera, Meryem Benziane, Lucía Rueda, Mansour Serghini, Henning Winker, María Soto and Pilar Hernández.

Fishery: This species is one of the most important commercial demersal species in the Strait of Gibraltar area. Discards might be considered negligible. However, there is not much information available on the stock structure of *P. bogaraveo* in this narrow site. The Spanish fishery targeting blackspot seabream has been developing along the Strait of Gibraltar since the earliest 1980's. It is almost a mono-specific fishery, with one clear target species representing 74% from the total landed species, which constitutes a metier by itself. The "voracera", a local mechanized hook line baited with sardine, is the gear used by the fleet from Tarifa and Algeciras ports in Spain. The most important

Moroccan fleets targeting blackspot seabream (among other species) are the longliners mainly based at the port of Tangier and the artisanal fleet of the Strait of Gibraltar area. The fishery is carried out at 200-700 m depth and the gear used is the longline known as well as “*voracera*”. The Moroccan fishery is considered as multi-specific. A consistent part of landings (even from Morocco) is sold in the Spanish market.

Data and parameters: Landings, nominal fishing effort and length composition from Spanish and Moroccan “*voracera*” fleets, when available. Biological parameters (sexratio) from Spain and Morocco sampling programmes while ageing from Spanish National Data Collection Programme. Standardized CPUEs from Spain and Morocco as biomass index since 2009. M scalar value of 0.2 and fix length-weight relationship ($a=3.14$ and $b=0.0087$, respectively). Model length range was from 18 to 62 cm and 3 to 17 ages. Likelihood weights were fixed according to the benchmark ones.

Assessment method: gadget (Globally applicable Area-Disaggregated General Ecosystem Toolbox) model using Rgadget package.

Model performance: update of the 2019 benchmarked model.

Results:

F_{current} (F_{bar} ages 4-16 (2021))	0.26
F_{msy} (2019 benchmark)	0.26
$F_{\text{current}}/F_{\text{msy}}$	1.0090
B_{lim} (benchmark), females pop (tonnes)	264
SSB_{current} (2021), females pop (tons)	256

Diagnosis of stock status: The stock is depleted with unsustainable exploitation

Advice and recommendations: Immediate reduction of fishing mortality and implement a recovery plan

Comparative plot:

Figure 39. Blackspot seabream SoG population: Comparison of the outputs from the benchmark assessment (red line), last year update (orange line) and this year performed assessment (green line). Total Stock Biomass – males and females (top), Stock Spawning Biomass – females (middle up), fishing mortality rates (middle bottom) and recruits at age 3 (bottom).

N: 48

Stock: Deep-water rose shrimp (*Parapenaeus longirostris*)

GSA: 1

Author(s): Pérez Gil, J.L., Serna-Quintero, J.M., Meléndez, M.J., García, C., González, M., Torres, P., Acosta, J., León, E., Ciércoles, C. and Martínez, G.

Fishery: Deep-water pink shrimp (*Parapenaeus longirostris*) is one of the main crustacean species for bottom otter trawl fisheries in the GFCM geographical sub-area Northern Alboran Sea (GSA1). It is an important component of landings in some ports and occasionally a target species of the trawl fleet composed of approximately 100 vessels (2021) that operates on the upper slope.

The annual landings (Y) fluctuated during the all series and increased in the last five years (average in this period: 345 tonnes) reaching up 564 t in 2021.

Data and parameters: The assessment was carried out using official landings and data on the length frequency distribution (LFD) of otter bottom trawl catches for the years 2002-2021. Catch-at-length data were converted into catch-at-age by cohort slicing procedures. Length-weight relationship and maturity ogive comes from Spanish data collection framework (DCF) and Natural mortality vector was estimated using PRODBIOM (Abella *et al.*, 1997). Abundance index series from MEDITS trawl surveys was used in XSA and a4a models analysis.

Assessment method: The state of exploitation of this stock was assessed by means of VPA Extended Survivor Analysis (XSA) (Shepherd, 1999) and statistical catch-at-age stock assessment model a4a (Jardim and Millar, 2014). The software used for both models, is implemented in R (FLR, flr-project.org). Yield-per-Recruit (Y/R) and Spawning-per-Recruit (SSB/R) analyses was conducted based on the exploitation pattern resulting from a4a model and population parameters.

Model performance: Sensitivity and retrospective analyses were applied in the a4a model in order to check the robustness of the assessment. The final model considered for the assessment was a4a.

Results:

$F_{current}$ (F_{bar} ages 0-2 (2021))	1.32
F_{target} (present assessment)	0.7
$F_{current}/F_{target}$	1.83
$SSB_{current(2021)}$ tonness	171
SSB 33% percentile biomass (tonnes)	43
SSB 66% percentile biomass (tonnes)	70

Diagnosis of stock status: The stock is in overexploitation, with relatively high biomass.

Advice and recommendation.

- Reduce $F_{current}$ towards $F_{0.1}$
- Progressive reduction of the fishing effort

Figure 40. Comparison of the outputs of the previous year assessment (red line) and update assessment performed this year (blue line).

N: 49

Stock: Deep water rose shrimp (*Parapenaeus longirostris*)

GSA: 03 (Southern Alboran Sea)

Author(s): Said Bouchoucha, Jamal Settih, Meryem Benziane, Mohamed Malouli Idrissi, Pilar Hernandez & Alessandro Ligas

Fishery: This species is one of the most important commercial demersal species in the Alboran Sea. The fishing gear targetting this species is trawl. The trawlers operating since M’diq port target this specie between Fnideq and Jebha, at depths between 70 and 360 m. For Nador trawlers, they operate between Saidia and Jebha, at depths from 68 to 470 meters. For Al Hoceima trawlers, the limits of their trawling are from Sidi Hssaine to Jebha at depths from 18 to 200 meters. This fleet is a multi-specific and target shrimps in association with other groups of fishes. The deep-water pink shrimp represent annually 5 to 11% of the total landing. All the units are in wood with a men length of 22 m and with a mode of a conservation with glace. This fleet use many types of trawls but the most common trawls are: 2 meters’ vertical open trawl, used to catch benthic species like soles, octopus and shrimps; 5 meters’ vertical open trawl, used to catch benthic and semi-pelagic species.

Data and parameters : Official trawlers landings and CPUE (fishing days) from 2010 to 2021 are used to run a4a. Landings length composition from 2010 to 2021 trawlers fleet, survey length composition from 2013 to 2021, growth parameters estimated by Fisat-II sheperd’s method ($K=0,40$, $L_{inf}=48.1mm$, $t_0=-0.3613$), length-weight Relationship parameters ($a=0,2695$ and $b=1.11496$) (INRH, 2022) and M vector by Gislason were used for the length-age combination.

M vector estimated by Gislason

age	M
0	2.54236
1	1.05141
2	0.71079
3	0.57338

Assessment method: The estimation of the Alboran Sea *Parapenaeus longirostris* was performed using the statistical catch-at-age stock assessment model (a4a)

Model performance: The model gives a good fitting for catches. Several values of k were tested. The model outputs give a good fitting for K=6

Results:

F_{current} (F_{bar} ages 1-2 (year))	2.00341
F_{target} (present assessment)	0.9438712
F_{current}/F_{target}	2.12254596
SSB_{current}(year) (tonnes)	87.162
SSB 33% percentile biomass (tonnes)	104
SSB 66% percentile biomass (tonnes)	180

The model results show that the deep-water pink shrimp stock in Morocco is in a situation of overexploitation.

Advice and recommendation: Reduce F_{current} towards F_{target1}

N: 50

Stock: Deep-sea rose shrimp (*Parapenaeus longirostris*)

GSA: 04

Author(s): S. ROUIDI, T. FILALI, N. AINOUCHE, P. HERNÁNDEZ and A. LIGAS.

Fishery: Deep-water pink shrimp (*Parapenaeus longirostris*) is one of the main crustacean species targeted for trawlers in GSA 04. It is an important component of landings in Western area, occasionally targeted by trawlers operated on the upper slope. In 2021, more than 55 % of catches comes from Alboran part of GSA 04. The annual landings fluctuated during all the assessed series; for this year, the catches are increasing comparatively to the last two years and it's the same for biomass indices calculated from bottom trawl surveys (2012-2021) who showed an increasing trend in last 7 years.

Data and parameters: Length frequency data comes from commercial catches of seven years (2015–2021) sampling in western area are used to extrapolate national landings. Growth parameters and length-weight relationship are coming from national fisheries research program (CNRDPA, 2017), also the ogive maturity was estimated from the national data collection and M vector is obtained by ProdBiom (Abella *et al.*1999), all these parameters were used to run a pseudo-cohort analysis.

Assessment method: National catches at age data are constructed using Plyr package (Slicing), Pseudo-cohort analysis and yield-per-recruit analysis were performed by Vit software using each year separately and the average of three years (2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2015-2017, 2016-2018, 2017-2019, 2018-2020 and 2019-2021). In order to give a support for this assessment, a second assessment are performed by using the length-based spawning potential ratio model (LBSPR) for both sexes and for females separately regarding the sexual dimorphism in growth, it consists to Simulate expected equilibrium length composition, yield-per-recruit, and the spawning potential ratio (Hordyk *et al.*, 2016). Taking into account the available data, a4a model was carried out during data preparation meeting as an exercise.

Model performance: Vit program was developed to assess exploited fish stocks in data-poor situations. It was used for qualitative conclusions from several years in GFCM meeting. Quantitative interpretations of stock parameters are recommended when the model is applied to short time series of more than a single year and the resulting variation of the parameters is reasonably low. Sensitivity

of model was tested using several terminal fishing mortalities. The mean fishing mortality from age classes most abundant in catches was estimated as $F_{current}$. Results coming from this model may form the basis for scientifically sound fisheries management advice for medium-term periods. However, the likely low precision of results prevents their transfer to any precise short-term forecasts. LBSPR model is fitting to length data to estimate selectivity, relative apical fishing mortality and the spawning potential ratio. Length composition is used to estimate the SPR for data-limited fisheries by developing a computational efficient length-structured per-recruit model that splits the population into a number of sub-cohorts, or growth-type-groups, to account for size-dependent fishing mortality rates (Hordyk et al., 2016). a4a model is strongly recommended to have a robust advice, but in our case, the shortness of time series sampling data don't allow us to make a retrospective analysis, at the end, we concluded that the model is very promising for the near future (03 years) and will be adopted and performed for DPS.

Results: Pseudo-cohort analysis in VIT show that age classes 0-2 are the most exploited. $F_{current}$ (1.55) is higher than reference point $F_{0.1}$ (0.57) and the ratio $F_{current}/F_{0.1} = 2.7$ indicate an overfishing status of deep-sea pink shrimp in GSA-4. However, LBSPR results show a contradictory stock status regarding $SPR_{40\%}$ (0.33) near to 0.4 giving a sustainable overfishing situation.

Diagnosis of stock status: In possible overexploitation

Advice and recommendations: Precautionary advice: Reduce fishing mortality

N: 51

Stock: Deep-water rose shrimp (*Parapenaeus longirostris*)

GSA: 05.

Author(s): Marc Farré, Beatriz Guijarro, Natalia González, Virginia Soldán and Aina de Mesa.

Fishery: In the Balearic Islands, commercial bottom trawlers develop up to four different fishing strategies, which are associated with the shallow shelf, deep shelf, upper slope and middle slope, mainly targeted to: (i) *Spicara smaris*, *Mullus surmuletus*, *Octopus vulgaris* and a mixed fish category on the shallow shelf (50-80 m); (ii) *Merluccius merluccius*, *Mullus* spp., *Zeus faber* and a mixed fish category on the deep shelf (80-250 m); (iii) *Nephrops norvegicus*, but with an important by-catch of big *Merluccius merluccius*, *Lepidorhombus* spp., *Lophius* spp. and *Micromesistius poutassou* on the upper slope (350-600 m) and (iv) *Aristeus antennatus* on the middle slope (600-750 m). The deep-water rose shrimp (*P. longirostris*) is a by-catch species mainly exploited on the upper slope. The species has importantly increased in landings since 2017 to currently, ranging from 60-100 tons (mean values of landings lower than 50 tons from 2000 to 2017).

Data and parameters: Size composition of commercial trawl catches and official landings (2001-2021) and survey indices (2001-2021). Biological parameters obtained from studies carried out in the area: growth parameters from Guijarro *et al.*, (2009); length-weight relationship and maturity ogive from the Spanish Data Collection Framework; mortality vector calculated from PRODBIOM.

Assessment method: Both Extended Survivor Analysis (XSA) and a4a were used. Finally, a4a model was selected to provide the final advice. Yield per recruit analysis and short-term forecast were carried out. The assessment is a revised version, not an update, from the previous year 2020 since last year was validated using XSA.

Model performance: A4a residuals did not show noticeable trends and, despite the noticeably rise of the recruitment and SSB in the last year of the time series, the model showed a quite good fit.

Results: The population parameters showed, excepting for F , the highest values at the beginning and at the end of the data series (2016-2021), with very low values in the intermediate years. Historical data showed that catches of this species are usually low, with important peaks in certain periods (e.g.

2001-2003 and 2017-2021). Both SSB and recruitment showed an important increase in the last year of time series (2021). F showed an oscillating trend along the entire series: a decreasing trend from 2001-2007, a rising and then constant tendency from 2008-2017, after an increase for 2018-2019 and finally a sharp decline up to 2021 (Fig. 1).

F _{current} (2021, ages 0-2)	1.33
F _{0.1} (2021)	0.569
F _{current} /F _{0.1}	2.34
SSB (2021, tons)	97.2
33th percentile SSB (tons)	5.8
66th percentile SSB (tons)	24.6

Diagnosis of stock status: The stock is in overexploitation, with relatively high biomass.

Advice and recommendation: To reduce fishing mortality.

Data issues: Information used was the official one submitted to the GFCM.

Issues for future benchmarks: Stock boundaries should be investigated. Mortality vector was computed using methodologies created for fish species so other approaches should be taken into account. The stock assessment should be investigated performing sex-specific slicing using different growth parameters.

Comparative plot:

Figure 41. Comparison of the outputs of the previous year assessment (XSA model selected for 2020) and revised assessment performed this year (a4a assessment selected for 2021).

N: 52

Stock: Deep water rose shrimp (*Parapenaeus longirostris*)

GSA: 06

Author(s): Miguel Vivas, Encarnación García, José Luis Pérez Gil, Antonio Esteban, Amina Tifoura.

Fishery: Deep water rose shrimp is exploited by bottom trawlers. This fishery is developed along deep continental shelf targeting on hake and crustaceans. Vessels length was between 12-24 m.

The number of harbours with rose shrimp landings is 25 for the whole area, and the number of vessels in this area was 399 for the last year (2021).

Total landings in the GSA 6 (2001-2021) were around 6990 tons and 403600 days. In 2021, landings were around 1111 tons and total effort over 38393 fishing days by year and CPUE medium, 28.94 kgs/day. Discards of deep water rose shrimp are negligible.

Data and parameters: Size composition of commercial trawl catches, official landings and data from MEDITS surveys (2001-2021).

Biological parameters obtained from studies carried out in the area: Growth from Guijarro et al., (2009) and length-weight relationship and maturity ogive from the Data Collection Framework; M vector calculated from PRODBIOM. (Abella et al, 1997)

Assessment method: Extended survivor analysis (XSA, FLR libraries), FLBRP package for yield-per-recruit analysis and Flash package for short-term forecast. This is an update assessment.

Model performance: Log catchability residuals and Retrospective analysis suggest that the model is consistent.

Results: Recruitment, SSB and landings showed the highest values at the beginning and particularly at the end of the data series (2001-2021), with very low values in the intermediate years. Both recruitment and SSB showed minimum values from 2004 to 2008. Fishing mortality showed an increasing trend in last seven years.

F _{current} (F _{bar} 0-2) 2019-2021	1.15
F _{0.1} (2021)	0.78
F _{current} /F _{0.1}	1.47
Current SSB (tons) 2019-2021	334.6
33rd percentile SSB (tons)	81.8
66th percentile SSB (tons)	132
Recruitment (Thousands)	524266

Diagnosis of stock status: In overexploitation, with relatively high biomass.

Advice and recommendations: Reduce F_{current} towards F_{0.1}

Figure 42. Comparison of the outputs of the previous year assessment (blue line) and revised assessment performed this year (red line).

N: 53

Stock: Deep-water rose shrimp (*Parapenaeus longirostris*)

GSA: 8, 9, 10, 11

Author(s): STECF EWG 22-09

Fishery: In the present assessment, the stock was assumed to be confined within the GSAs 09, 10 and 11 boundaries. In GSA09, the species shows a wide bathymetric distribution, being present from 50 to 650 m depth with greatest abundance between 150 and 400 m depth over muddy or sandy-muddy bottoms. The highest abundances have been found in the Tyrrhenian part of the GSA (south Tuscany and Latium). In GSA10, aggregations with higher abundance were localised between 100 and 200 m depth, with some intrusions in the deeper waters in three sub-areas. Two most important patches were located in the Gulf of Naples and along the Calabrian coasts in correspondence with Cape Bonifati, while a third one in the Gulf of Salerno. These are the areas where also the main nurseries are localised. The deep-water rose shrimp with hake and red mullet is a key species of fishing

assemblages in the area. In the last decade it was generally also ranked among the species with higher abundance indices (number of individuals) in the trawl surveys as observed for different Mediterranean areas. The species is caught on the same fishing grounds as European hake and the production of this shrimp is steadily growing in the last decade in the southern basin and it reached in 2006 about 10% of the demersal landings. The core of nursery areas in GSA09 overlap with crinoid beds (*Leptometra phalangium*) areas over the shelf-break. This is a peculiar habitat in the GSA09, which is also an essential fish habitat for other commercially important species as the European hake. GSA 8 was included for the first time, although providing negligible contribution in terms of catches.

Data and parameters: Size composition of commercial trawl catches and official landings (2009-2021), Medits survey indices (2009-2021). Growth parameters and maturity ogives were gathered from Italian National Data Collection Programme, while the M vector was estimated using the Chen and Watanabe model. A different maturity-at-age vector was used, with maturity at age0 set equal to zero.

Assessment method: Statistical Catch-At-Age, SCAA (a4a, FLR libraries), FLBRP package for yield per recruit analysis and Flash package for short-term forecast. The FLRef package was used to estimate reference points.

Model performance: Model residuals did not show any trend. Overall diagnostics are acceptable, and retrospective analysis is consistent.

Results: Spawning Stock biomass showed an increasing trend with maximum value in 2016, then increasing again in 2018. A similar trend was observed for recruitment that reached the peak in 2016. F is showing a general increasing pattern.

F _{current} F _{bar} ages 1-3 (2021)	1.40
F _{0.1} (present assessment)	1.26
SSB _{current} (tons)	872
B _{MSY}	855
B _{pa}	427.5
B _{lim}	214
F _{current} /F _{0.1}	1.11

Diagnosis of stock status: In low overexploitation, with biomass above B_{MSY}.

Advice and recommendation:

- Reduce F_{current} towards F_{0.1}
- Progressive reduction of the fishing effort

Figure 42. Comparison of the outputs of the previous years' assessments (purple, blue and green lines) and updated assessment performed this year (red line).

N: 54

Stock: Deep water rose shrimp (*Parapenaeus longirostris*)

GSA: 22

Author(s): Vasiliki Sgardeli; Danai Mantopoulou-Palouka; George Tserpes

Fishery: The stock is exploited almost exclusively by bottom trawlers. The Greek bottom trawl fishery has multi-species characteristics and similarly to most Mediterranean demersal trawl fisheries, captures more than 100 commercial species. However, deep water rose shrimp together with hake and red mullets compose the main bulk of landings. Deep water rose shrimp comprises around 15% of total trawl landings in the Aegean Sea.

Data and parameters: The stock assessment utilizes landings data from the Hellenic Statistical Authorities (HELSTAT), length frequency distributions from DCF and a survey index obtained from the MEDITS trawl survey in the period 2003-2021. A revision to the landings data from HELSTAT has been made. In particular, data before 2015 were reconstructed using an average ratio of deep-water shrimp landings over all shrimp landings (DPS and TGS) from recent years (2017-2021). The computed fraction (~90%) was applied to the total shrimp landings before 2015 to obtain the reconstructed stock landings. In addition, Turkish fleets' landings from GSA22, available since 2006, were added to obtain the landings' time series used in the assessment. Due to the absence of stock specific growth curves, the biological parameters for the species (VBGF, length-weight relationship, maturity, etc.) were borrowed from ITA GSA 18 (Kolitari et al., 2014).

Assessment method: The assessment was performed using the statistical catch-at-age model, a4a (Jardim *et al.*, 2015).

Model performance: The model was considered much improved with respect to the previous year's assessment. Model diagnostics were acceptable, but a poor fit to the total catch time series was evident especially towards recent years.

Results: The assessment shows that the stock is in overexploitation, while the current (2021) biomass is over the 66th quantile of the historical time series (relatively high biomass). Due to the uncertainty in the historical landings' time series, the uncertainty with respect to the growth of the species and the poor fit to the total catch, the assessment was considered suitable for qualitative advice.

F _{current} (F _{bar} ages 0-2 (2021))	1.953
F _{target} (present assessment)	0.522
F _{current} /F _{target}	3.736
SSB _{current} (year) (tonnes)	4026
SSB 33% percentile biomass (tonnes)	3033
SSB 66% percentile biomass(tonnes)	3613

Diagnosis of stock status: In possible overexploitation (Qualitative)

Advice and recommendations: Reduce fishing mortality

Comparative plot: The assessment is considered a revised assessment due to the change in the landings' time series.

N: 55

Stock: Thornback ray (*Raja clavata*)

GSA: 25

Author(s): Ioannis Thasitis, Charis Charilaou

Fishery: Thornback ray is a species interacting with all fleets in GSA 25. It is also considered to have some interaction with recreational fishery too. The exact magnitude of recreational catches is missing as there was no catch declaration nor sampling on these landings. Catch declarations for this species are also problematic for commercial fishery.

Data and parameters: Due to the lack of landings data the assessment was carried out using Biomass index from the Cyprus Medits survey (2005-2022).

Assessment method: Due to the issues presented in catch data, an alternative approach was used based on AMSY methodology. Resilience priors of the AMSY, were derived from Fishbase. To account for the missing year (2014) in the Medits timeseries a state space analysis was used (BCrump R code) to interpolate 2014 value.

Model performance: The retrospective analysis did not show any trend.

Results: The time series of the median relative catch predicted by AMSY shows a steady increasing condition from the beginning of the timeseries until 2013 were a significant decline (although above MSY levels) goes down up until 2019. The trend is then reverted increasing until the end of the assessment period. Fishing pressure expressed as the ratio F/F_{msy} is reduces rapidly to sustainable levels from 2005 to 2011 and remains to low ratio values until the end. Time series of CPUE expressed as B/B_0 has a similar trend with Medits index and remains above the ratio of 1 from 2009 onwards.

F/F_{msy}	0.154 (2020)
B/B_{msy}	1.91 (2021)

Diagnosis of stock status: The assessment was validated as qualitative and the stock seems to be exploited sustainably with relatively high biomass.

Advice and recommendation: In sustainable exploitation. Not to increase fishing mortality.

N: 56

Stock: Lessepsian lizardfish (*Saurida lessepsianus*)

GSA: 24

Author(s): Savaş Kılıç, Sinan Mavruk

Fishery: The lessepsian lizardfish (*Saurida lessepsianus*) is a migrant species from the Indo-West Pacific through the Suez Canal to the Northeastern Mediterranean Sea (GSA 24). *Saurida lessepsianus* is a demersal species, found over mostly sandy or muddy bottoms of coastal waters as deep as 200 m. It's population and commercial importance has increased considerable and has been one of the most common species caught in the trawl fishery in the northeastern Mediterranean. About 95% of lessepsian *Saurida lessepsianus* is fished by bottom trawls and the most of the remaining part fished mostly by gillnets.

Data and parameters: Official landing data of *Saurida lessepsianus* has not been collected by the Turkish Statistical Institutes because of naming and reporting mainly as silverfish by the fisherman. So, landing data has been estimated from the landing of silverfish reported in the micro data of Turkish Statistical Institute for 2019, 2020 and 2021. Biological and monthly length frequencies data were collected from commercial fisheries by Mediterranean Fisheries Research, Production, and Training Institute (MEDFRI) between 2019 and 2022. Von Bertalanffy growth parameters were estimated from the length-frequencies by using by TropFishR package in R. L_{50} and L_{95} were estimated using the biological data from the MEDFRI.

Assessment method: The length-based spawning potential ratio (LB-SPR) data limited stock assessment model were used for the assessment.

Results:

Year	LB-SPR	
	SPR Female	Stock statues
2019	0.41	Sustainable exploited
2020	0.45	Sustainable exploited
2021	0.32	Overexploited

Diagnosis of stock status: Possibly overexploited.

Advice and recommendations: Not to increase fishing mortality.

N: 57

Stock: Common Cuttlefish (*Sepia officinalis*)

GSA: 17

Author(s): Armelloni E. N., Scanu M., Masnadi F., Polidori P., Santojanni A., Martinelli M., Sabatini L., Cacciamani R., Marceta B., Isajilovic I., Arneri E., Scarcella G.

Fishery: The common cuttlefish is a valuable resource in the Northern Adriatic Sea (GSA 17) where it is targeted by trawled gears (otter trawl, “Rapido” trawl) and set gears (trammel nets, pots and fyke nets). The stock is shared by Slovenian, Croatian and Italian fleets, with the latter accounting for an average of more than 90% of catches per year. The reproductive behavior of the species influences its catchability: during fall the recruits moves from coastal waters (nursery) to the circalittoral zone (feeding ground) and in the next spring the same cohort goes back to the shallower infralittoral region to spawn and, subsequently, die (semelparous species). Indeed, recruits dominate trawl landings whether the coastal fishery targets mainly adults during the spawning time. Historical catches trend is declining, and from 2010 onward were registered some of the lowest values.

Data and parameters: Landings for Italy (1973-2021), Slovenia (1992-2021); Croatia (1992-2021); Yugoslavia (1974-1991); SoleMon survey index (2005-2021).

Data issues: Yugoslavia data (1974-1991) are considered representative of the sum of Croatia and Slovenia data, which were available from 1992 onward. Solemon survey in 2021 missed the southernmost area envisaged in the protocol for technical issues. A correction factor of 0.934 was applied to 2021 to account for the missing sampling. See stock assessment form for more details.

Assessment method: JABBA (Winker *et al.*, 2018): Bayesian state-space implementation of the Schaefer surplus production model. Priors for final depletion obtained with AMSY (Froese *et al.*, 2020). Comparison were made with CMSY model (Froese *et al.*, 2017) and SPiCT model (Pedersen and Berg, 2017).

Model performance: three surplus production model results were considered acceptable based on diagnostic. JABBA and SPiCT stock perception were comparable, while CMSY indications were more pessimistic. Based on diagnostic quality and plausibility it was decided to give advice based on JABBA model.

Results: biomass trend showed an almost monotonous decline in the early part of the timeseries, until 1995, then it oscillated without large spikes until 2007. In 2008 it was observed a steep decline which led the biomass to fall below 0.5 B/B_{msy} in 2009. From 2012 onward, the biomass did not shown sign of recovering and in 2021 it was still below 0.5 B/B_{msy}. Exploitation highly oscillated during the whole timeseries. Until 2001 were observed high spikes alternated to years of exploitation at values close to F_{msy}. Subsequently the F remained quite above the F_{msy} for the period 2002-2021, excluding year 2020. During the years 2016-2021 the F declined but it was slightly above the F_{msy} in 2021.

F _{current} (2021)	0.279
Lower limit (95% c.i.)	0.175
Upper limit (95% c.i.)	0.422
F _{msy} (2021)	0.203
F _{current} /F _{msy}	1.37
Lower limit F _{curr} /F _{msy} (95% c.i.)	0.76
Upper limit F _{curr} /F _{msy} (95% c.i.)	2.07

Current Biomass (thousand tonnes)	7.973
B_{msy} (thousand tonnes)	29.106
Current Biomass / B_{msy}	0.27
L. limit Current Biomass/ B_{msy} (95% c.i.)	0.18
U.limit Current Biomass/ B_{msy} (95% c.i.)	0.437
MSY (thousand tonnes)	5.93
Catches 2021 (thousand tonnes)	2224.486

Diagnosis of stock status: In overexploitation with low biomass.

Advice and recommendations: Reduce fishing mortality

Figure 42. Stock trajectory estimated from the JABBA model

N: 58

Stock: Common sole (*Solea solea*)

GSA: 17

Author(s): STECF EWG 22-16

Fishery: Common sole is a demersal and sedentary species, living on sandy and muddy bottoms and is one of the most commercially important species of the FAO-GFCM area (Mediterranean and Black Sea). In the Adriatic in 2021, 60% of the catches is provided by the Italian rapido trawl fleets (TBB), 19% from the Italian, Slovenian and Croatian set netters (GNS and GTR) operating mostly within

3 nautical miles from the coast, 18% from the Italian otter trawlers (OTB), and the remaining 3% from the Croatian rampon fishery (DCF ITA HRV).

Assessment method: The biggest novelty used in this update benchmark assessment is that an ensemble modelling approach (Dietterich, 2000) was used to present results with a quantitative criterion based on diagnostic scores for weighting the runs. In summary, to address structural uncertainties, a range of alternative SS3 models (Methot and Wetzel 2013) was selected through diagnostics (interconnected diagnostic tests; Carvalho et al. 2021, Maunder et al. 2020), to be stitched together using delta-Multivariate log-Normal estimator (delta-MVLN; Winker et al. 2019).

Data and parameters: The model use a long historical series of catches, 1953-2021. The model used was organized into 6 fleets: 5 commercial and 1 survey. The commercial fleets, each with its own selectivity, are represented by individual gears (Italian trawlers, Italian *rapido*, Italian nets, Croatian and Slovenian nets and Croatian *rampon*) while the survey included as tuning index was the SoleMon (2005-2021). In addition, the model includes, where available, length structures by fleet. Size are then converted to age inside the model. In collaboration with to the study group of the AdriaMed regional project - FAO (SG-OTHSOLEA), the von Bertalanffy growth parameters used were estimated by applying non-linear least square algorithm to age data collected in GSA 17 following the methodology by Carbonara and Follesa 2019. Ensemble approach was selected as the best solution because it represents all possible states of nature of the stock under analysis based on a number of sources of natural and fisheries uncertainty. Major uncertainty was linked to an alternative hypothesis of selectivity which has a large influence on the assessment (double normal vs cubic splines settings). Other alternative plausible hypothesis was based on different levels of natural mortality (3 Ms) and steepness (3 h). The final model grid for the ensemble included all combinations of alternative values for these three nested variables (18 runs).

Model performance: Interconnected diagnostic tests (cookbook by Carvalho *et al.* 2021) were carried out on all ensemble candidate runs. The diagnostic tests were considered acceptable and diagnostics scores were used as weighting factor during ensemble procedure. However, overall diagnostics for the CS (Cubic Spline) set (run 9 to 18) continue to deteriorate slightly compared to the benchmark model leading to heavier emphasis in the ensemble of models assuming dome-shaped selection for all fleets. This may represent a small increase in the risk of an assessment with a cryptic biomass. Nevertheless, results in terms of main output value are stable and consistent with the benchmark and with the update of 2021.

Results: The final results of the model reported for the last year (2021) an SSB of 3440 tons and an estimated recruitment of 86378 (1000s) specimens. The current F is 0.18.

F_{current} ($F_{\text{bar } 1-4}$ in 2020)	0.19 (0.09–0.33)
$F_{\text{current}}/F_{40\%}$	0.75 (0.39 - 1.50)
Current SSB (tonnes)	3440 (1685 - 9059)
$SSB_{\text{current}}/SSB_{40\%}$	0.85 (0.33 - 1.61)
Recruitment (1000s)	86378 (40613 - 166465)

Diagnosis of stock status: The output of the model reported for the last year (2021) a spawning biomass estimated below the reference point (SSB_{40}) and fishing mortality was estimated to be below the reference value (fishing mortality level at SSB_{40}). In the last year, the trajectory of the stock from the Kobe plot reflected its recovering status.

Advice and recommendations: Though F is less than target reference point, the WG recommends to reduce fishing mortality due to the low spawning biomass of the stock.

N: 59

Stock: Spot-tail Mantis shrimp (*Squilla mantis*)

GSA: 17

Author(s): Scanu M., Masnadi F., Armelloni E. N., Angelini S., Santojanni A., Domenichetti F., Colella S., Donato F., Cacciamani R., Calì F., Martinelli M., Arneri E., Cardinale M., Scarcella G.

Fishery: *Squilla mantis* is in GSA17 ranks first among the crustacean landed in the Adriatic ports, it is an important component of local multispecies trawl, gill net fishery and a specialized pot fishery is developing. Adriatic sea accounts for around 80% of the Italian annual landings for this species. The species is present also in Croatian and Slovenian statistics (max 10 tons per year), however, considering this small amount of catches these data have been summed up with the Italian fleet using the same gear. Catches show marked dial periodicity with significantly more animals caught at night. The burrowing behavior of *S. mantis* makes it vulnerable only when individuals are out of their burrows and this occurs mainly at night, between sunset and sunrise. Seasonal variations in catchability result from reduced out-of-burrow activity, because females rarely exit their burrow when they are incubating their egg mass in spring and early summer. Conversely, catches increase in winter, when mating takes place. Catches increase further in late autumn with the arrival of new recruits.

Data and parameters: The overall trend in catches from '50s is a clear increase, although cyclical peaks and troughs every 3-4 years. A strong decrease results evident between 2010 and 2013. From 2014 to 2016 a new slight increasing trend has been registered.

The SS3 analyses has been carried out considering the following four fleets:

1. OTB
2. GNS
3. TBB
4. FPO

The Stock Synthesis model used in this assessment is a seasonal size structure data model based on the separate fleet LFD from 2009 to 2021; some LFD were excluded from the assessment due to small sampling effort highlighted in the data section. Pots and traps fleet has LFD only in 2020.

The age classes considered range from 0 to 4, but plug group was set at age 6 in order to not force the model to fit.

Tuning data were provided by SOLEMON survey, carried out in fall for the years 2005-2021, and the LFD of the survey from 2012 to 2021 were also used as input data. Due to missing hauls in 2020, a spatio-temporal ecological model was used to predict Biomass index in missing points, and the Abundance index for the whole area was estimated its results in combination with real observations. The same happened in 2021 but it was applied a correction factor to scale the value of the survey in order to overcome the missing hauls.

The growth parameters used to run the assessment was the one studied by Froglija et al. (1996) in GSA 17. Since into data are present animals very big compared to these parameters, the WGSAD asked for the re-investigation of all biological parameters. Natural mortality vector was obtained from PRODBIOM model (Abella et al., 1998) and maturity from the literature (Colella et al., 2016).

Data and parameters issues: Since into data are present animals very big compared to the Froglija's parameters, the WGSAD asked for the re-investigation of all biological parameters. The WGSAD pointed out also issues related to the LFDs.

Assessment method: The fundamental idea of this stock assessment is to use the integrated approach of Stock Synthesis (last version SS3.3) to model the size structure data available for the mantis shrimp.

SS3 uses forward projection of population in the “statistical catch-at-age” approach. To follow the stepwise growth of this crustacean species a seasonal model has been developed.

Model performance: No particular trends were evidenced in residuals. Run test on all fleets and survey data, hindcasting and retrospective analysis were considered acceptable.

Results: The final results of the model reported for 2021 a SSB of 6600 tonnes and an estimated current F is 0.32.

F_{current} ($F_{\text{bar 1-3}}$ in 2021)	0.32 (± 0.05)
$F_{40\%}$ (2019, 2020, 2021)	0.33
$F_{\text{current}}/F_{40\%}$	0.96
Current SSB (tonnes)	6600 (± 870)
$SSB_{40\%}$ (2020)	6333

Diagnosis of stock status: Considering the results of the analyses conducted, Mantis shrimp in GSA 17 is subjected to sustainable exploitation being the current $F(1-3)$ estimates with SS3 model of 0.32, lower than the proposed reference point ($F_{40\%} = 0.33$). Based on the spawning stock biomass level (SSB), the stock result in a state of high biomass being the current SSB estimated by the SS3 model 6600 tons; above the reference $SSB_{40\%}=6333$.

Advice and recommendations: Do not increase fishing mortality

Figures:

Figure 43. Spawning Stock Biomass and standard deviation calculated by SS3 model (blue), with $SSB_{40\%}$ (black dotted line) percentile.

Figure 44. Fishing effort and standard deviation calculated by SS3 model (blue), and F40% (black dotted line).

N: 60

Stock: Goldband goatfish (*Upeneus moluccensis*)

GSA: 27 - Palestine

Authors: Reda M. Fahim, Hatem H. Mahmoud, Abdelnasser Madi, Mohamed Abutair, Stefano Lelli, John G. Ramirez, Elisabetta B. Morello,

Fishery: The goldband goatfish, *Upeneus moluccensis*, is a species belonging to the Mullidae family of Indo-Pacific origin. It is widespread in the warmer waters of the Indian and Pacific Oceans as far east as New Caledonia and has found the eastern Mediterranean Sea from the Red Sea via the Suez Canal. It is mainly exploited in Palestine by trawl fishery. However, a minor percentage comes from gill nets.

Data and parameters: Data has been collected within a fisheries data collection system supported by the FAO EastMed project, along the coast of the Gaza Strip in four landing sites (Gaza City, Dar al Balah, Khan Yunes and Rafah). The first pilot study was completed at the end of 2013. The sampled years are from 2013 to 2020. The monthly length frequency distributions were raised to the monthly landings. Growth parameters were estimated using the ELEFAN_SA algorithm for the sexes combined. The length-weight relationship, the length at first maturity (L_{m50}) and the sex ratio were also studied. An average natural mortality (M) was used considering the average from eight estimators using the tool incorporated in http://barefootecologist.com.au/shiny_m.html. Because the unbalance sampling by month and years, and poor model fitting for some years, data was aggregated by periods (2013-2016) and (2017-2020) and then used for the assessment.

Assessment method: Length-Based Spawning Potential Ratio (LBSPR) as well as VIT software were used. In VIT, the Y/R analysis was applied for the calculation of the reference point $F_{0.1}$.

Model performance: The methods were used in a complementary and integrated way. Consistency between results, inputs and life history parameters was cross-checked among methods.

Results: Regarding VIT, The Y/R analysis indicated a level of fishing mortality as 0.786 and 0.954 for the periods (2013-2016) and (2017-2020), respectively. The target reference points $F_{0.1}$ were 0.621 and 0.639 for the same periods. The ratio $F_c/F_{0.1}$ were 1.266 and 1.493. For LBSPR, the SPR was 0.26 and 0.185 for the periods (2013-2016) and (2017-2020), respectively.

Diagnosis of Stock status: The stock is in a status of overfishing.

Advice and recommendations: To consider a reduction of the fishing mortality towards $F_{0.1}$.

General conclusions and recommendations

Joint session of the working groups on stock assessment

82. A joint session of the WGSAD and WGSASP took place to address several activities for future work, including the determination of minimum conservation reference sizes in response to Resolution GFCM/2021/44/2, the construction of timelines and new methodologies towards a more integrated analysis of regional stock status. The WGSAs reiterated the importance of coupling the time series of catches with events related to the fishery and the environment and underlined the need for historical information on the fishery towards better informing stock assessments on the exploitation levels in the past, in particular for those models making use of priors. The WGSAs acknowledged the forward approach for the analysis of stock status at a regional level currently employed by SoMFi (State of Mediterranean and Black Sea Fisheries), noting it provided a historical perspective of advice on stock status concentrating on the outputs of each assessment each year. The WGSAs praised the comparison made between this approach and the so-called backward approach that analyzes stock trajectories as estimated from the most recent assessments. The WGSAs underlined that while the two approaches provided similar trends in overall fishing pressure, the backward approach was advisable as it may deliver a more realistic view of the trend in $F/FMSY$ since the beginning of the time series (increasing coverage and quality) and allowed for comparisons with assessments from other organizations (e.g., the STECF in the Mediterranean) and other regions worldwide (e.g. the FAO SOFIA).

83. The WGSAs were also presented standardized procedures for preparing, labelling and archiving assessment outputs and generating STAR files, with the aim of improving reproducibility and transparency, while reducing time consuming post-processing and error checking as well as working towards the automation of the table of advice in the future. The method is based on several R functions developed to facilitate the process of generating a compatible STAR csv file for the most commonly used assessment software. In addition, a novel Shiny Application was associated to these functions for the live visualization of stock assessment outcomes from validated age-structured assessments conducted with a4a, xsa, FLSAM and SS3. The WGSAs agreed to trial the method during the meeting.

Assessment

84. Only eight out of the 60 validated assessments adopted during the WGSAD meeting indicated sustainable stock exploitation. Four of them were referring to red mullet stocks, while three concerned stocks of crustacean species, (Blue and red shrimp, Norway lobster and Spottail mantis shrimp). In addition a thornback ray stock was possibly under sustainable exploitation. It should be noted that four additional stocks were found to be overexploited but with low fishing mortality levels.

85. All hake stocks were found to be in overexploitation, or possibly in overexploitation with varying biomass levels.

86. Assessments of deep-water rose shrimp covered nine GSAs of the western, and one GSA of the eastern Mediterranean. All stocks were found to be in overexploitation, or in possible overexploitaion (qualitative assessments were performed in GSAs 3, 4 and 22).

87. Assessments of red mullet were performed in 16 GSAs throughout the Mediterranean. The stocks were under sustainable exploitation in GSAs 10 and 22, while in the rest GSAs they were found to be in overexploitation with varying biomass levels.

88. Assessments of blue and red shrimp were performed in seven GSAs of the western and central Mediterranean. Sustainable exploitation was estimated for GSA 1, while in the rest GSAs the stocks were found to be overexploitation, with varying biomass levels.
89. Assessments of red shrimp covered 12 GSAs of the western, central and Adriatic regions. In all cases, the stocks were estimated to be under overexploitation.
90. Assessments of Norway lobster were performed in three GSAs of the western Mediterranean (5, 6 and 9) and in the Northern Adriatic (GSA 17). In two cases (GSAs 5 and 17) the stocks were found to be under sustainable exploitation, while in the rest GSAs they were under overexploitation. Biomass levels, however, were always low and in GSAs 9 and 17 they were estimated to be below reference points (overexploited stocks).
91. Common cuttlefish and Spottail mantis shrimp were assessed in GSA 17 (Northern Adriatic). Spottail mantis was sustainably exploited, while common cuttlefish was found to be under overexploitation and overexploited.
92. Blackspot seabream was assessed in the Alboran Sea GSAs (1 and 3, Strait of Gibraltar) and it was found to be depleted with unsustainable exploitation.
93. Striped red mullet was assessed in GSA 5 and it was found to be in overexploitation.
94. Horned octopus was assessed in GSA 18 and it was found to be under sustainable exploitation but overexploited (biomass below reference points).
95. Thornback ray that was assessed in GSA 25 is likely under sustainable exploitation (qualitative assessment).
96. Blackbellied angler was assessed in GSA 7 and it was found to be under possible overexploitation (qualitative assessment).
97. Brushtooth lizardfish and Goldband goatfish were assessed qualitatively in GSAs 24 and 27 respectively. The stock of Brushtooth lizardfish was possibly overexploited, while that of Goldband goatfish was found to be under possible overexploitation.
98. Common sole was assessed in GSA 17 and was found to be overexploited but current fishing mortality is low.
99. Assessments of red coral were performed in GSAs 8, 11, 17, and 22. All stocks were found to be overexploited or possibly overexploited. Current fishing mortality is low in the northwestern waters of GSA 11, while the species is under overexploitation in the northern part of the aforementioned GSA.

Methods

100. The WGSAD acknowledged the gradual progress from VPA-like models towards statistical catch-at-age (SCAA) methods, following its previous advice. However, further work is needed, particularly on diagnostics, to allow the application of SCAA assessments on additional stocks.
101. The WGSAD underlined the importance of assessing species at the correct stock unit level and recommended that the outcomes of different projects investigating stock units around the Mediterranean (e.g. the MEDUNITS project) be taken into account when performing assessments.
102. The WGSAD noted that many hake models estimated high exploitation ratios (F/F_{tgt}) which have been sustained over time, but with no evident consequences on SSB; this was likely due to the misspecification of trawl selectivity (which should be dome-shaped but in many cases is not configured as such). The WGSAD underlined the need to reflect on this issue and recommended a holistic view of all hake assessments in terms of assumed or estimated selectivity of trawl fleets and catchability of surveys.

103. The WGSAD reiterated the importance of providing adequate diagnostics of model performance utilizing newly available tools and packages (e.g. “a4adiags” for a4a). Combination of different diagnostic tools is considered important to evaluate model fits to the data and identify the most appropriate model runs for providing advice.

104. The importance of providing consistent information in the table of advice, following the terminology that has been already agreed was reiterated. Thus, the term “New assessment” refers to a new combination of GSA/Species or a stock that has not been assessed for a long term; the term “Updated” refers to assessments keeping the same assumptions (biological parameters, model settings, etc.) with a previously presented assessment and one more year of data; the term “Revised” refers to assessments carried out regularly, when there are significant changes (methods, data, etc.).

105. The WGSAD remarked the importance of extending the time series of catches as far back as possible in order to better inform models and anchor biomass scale and associated reference points. In this context, the WGSAD discussed the need to set minimum requirements, based on the life history of the species in question, to the length of the time series used in statistical catch at age models.

106. The WGSAD underlined the importance of identifying the spatial resolution of catches from fishing trips exploiting multiple GSAs. This is particularly important for the assessment of hake, deep-water rose shrimp and deep-water red shrimp stocks.

107. In the case of species with strong sexual dimorphism (e.g. European hake, red mullet, shrimps, etc.), the WGSAD underlined the importance of sex-specific slicing to accurately track the two sexes within the assessment, and recommended a simulation study to investigate the effects of different slicing approaches (sex-combined vs separate-sexes) as well as the differences between the use of slicing vs true ages in the case of finfish.

108. The WGSAD recommended that the assessment of shrimp species in general (ARS, ARA and DPS) be supported by: i) a holistic analysis of length frequency distributions from both fishery dependent and fishery independent data in order to understand the more general dynamics of these species, ii) an investigation of the size structure by quarter and sex towards a visual cohort analysis giving an idea of how the cohorts progress in each quarter and possibly facilitating a move towards the use of quarterly models. Future standard practice should involve plotting LFDs by sex.

109. In the case of species with strong sexual dimorphism (e.g. European hake, red mullet, shrimps, etc.), the WGSAD underlined the importance of, where possible, estimating the spawning potential ratio (SPR) from LBSPR and the depletion in LBB for female LFD data and life history parameters.

110. The WGSAD acknowledged the importance of taking into account drivers other than fishery-related ones (e.g. environmental) in the future towards a future consideration of changes in stock productivity; this is particularly evident for shrimp species.

111. For CMSY applications that use the BSP for fitting to time series of CPUE observations (i.e. no Catch-Only), it is recommended to relax or completely remove the final biomass depletion prior, so that the model can be effectively updated by new observations in future.

112. For filling data gaps in survey and/or catch-at-size data the WGSAD encouraged the use of modeling approaches that take into account spatial and temporal parameters. This will increase the robustness of estimates, overcoming the limitations of simple interpolation techniques. However, this strictly refers to filling partial data gaps of missing survey stations, whereas filling data for completely missing years should be avoided.

113. The WGSAD underlined the usefulness of the data preparation meetings performed in advance of the working group, noting they had contributed considerably to the improvement of input data and assessment quality and should continue in the future well in advance of the WGSA sessions.

Advice

114. The WGSAD noted that several western Mediterranean stocks had biomass reference points (Bpa and Blim) calculated and this was an important premise for the future performance of management strategy evaluation as well as towards understanding the effectiveness of management plans. The WGSAD recommended the organization of a workshop/training on biomass reference points for Mediterranean stocks with the aim of calculating biomass reference points for as many stocks as possible in the future.

115. When biomass reference points are not estimated by the assessment model, reporting on relative biomass levels in the table of advice could be misleading, especially when using age-based models that do not include a stock–recruitment relationship. The WGSAD once again suggested this issue be tackled in the imminent revision of the GFCM framework for the provision of advice. The WGSAD, nevertheless, noted that reporting on trends for standing stock is still useful and, in this sense, the most recent period was deemed more meaningful, although short time series should be taken with caution. In order not to lose the information, the relative biomass will be included on the comments column of the table of advice

116. The WGSAD underlined the urgent need for a revision of the GFCM framework for the provision of advice with special emphasis on biomass reference points and on the explicit inclusion of a framework for data-limited assessments.

117. The WGSAD underlined the need for a number of new and additional benchmark sessions, in order of priority:

- New benchmark for blackspot seabream in the Strait of Gibraltar (GSAs 1-3) in 2024 as per the provisions on Recommendation GFCM/45/2022/3
- New benchmark for hake in the Adriatic Sea (GSAs 17-18) in order to provide more punctual advice towards informing the multiannual management plan for demersal fisheries in the Adriatic Sea (Rec. GFCM/43/2019/52)
- New benchmark for red mullet in GSA 16, and possibly in GSAs 12-14, 15 and 19, considering these were the first benchmark assessments performed dating back to 2018
- Spottail mantis shrimp in GSA 17
- Hake in GSAs 20, 22 and 23

118. Given their economic importance and their inclusion in a EU multi-annual management plan with a recent implementation of catch limits, the WGSAD recommended to include *Aristeus antennatus* and *Aristaeomorpha foliacea* in the list of priority species for the western Mediterranean.

119. The WGSAD reiterated the importance of establishing a clear path for the consideration of STECF assessments within the GFCM, with particular emphasis on those assessments that only cover EU GSAs. The current status often results in effort duplications and encompass the risk of producing conflicting results that impede the provision of robust advice.

Adoption of the report and of the recommendations

120. The conclusions and recommendations were adopted by the WGSAD on 17 December 2022. The whole report was adopted after revisions and amendments by electronic correspondence.

2 Recommendation GFCM/43/2019/5 on a multiannual management plan for sustainable demersal fisheries in the Adriatic Sea (geographical subareas 17 and 18)

Agenda

1. Joint opening and arrangements of the WGSAs (WGSAD and WGSASP)
2. Introductory session for the WGSAD
3. Adoption of the Agenda
4. Assessment of priority stocks for the subregion
5. Updates of benchmark assessments
6. Assessments of non-priority species – updates of previously presented assessments
7. Assessments of non-priority species – new assessments
8. Closing Session:

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Table of advice

#	GSA	Species	Method	Current Levels	Reference Points	Quantitative Status	Stock Status	Scientific Advice	WG Comments
1	1	Aristeus antennatus	a4a	$F_c = 0.39$, $B_c = 322$	$F_{0.1} = 0.42$	$F/F_{ref} = 0.92$	Sustainable exploitation	Do not increase fishing mortality	Update assessment ; relatively high biomass
2	2	Aristeus antennatus	XSA	$F_c = 0.62$, $B_c = 160$	$F_{0.1} = 0.41$	$F/F_{ref} = 1.51$	In overexploitation	Reduce fishing mortality	Revised assessment ; relatively high biomass
3	5	Aristeus antennatus	a4a	$F_c = 1.47$, $B_c = 102$	$F_{0.1} = 0.331$	$F/F_{ref} = 4.45$	In overexploitation	Reduce fishing mortality	Updated assessment with relatively low biomass
4	6	Aristeus antennatus	a4a	$F_c = 1.67$, $B_c = 237$	$F_{0.1} = 0.34$	$F/F_{ref} = 4.91$	In overexploitation, with relatively low biomass	Reduce fishing mortality	Revised assessment with additional data
5	18,19,20	Aristeus antennatus	a4a	$F_c = 0.91$, $B_c = 201$	$F_{0.1} = 0.206$	$F/F_{ref} = 4.43$	In overexploitation	Reduce fishing mortality	New assessment

6	9,10,11.1,1 1.2	Aristaeomorph a foliacea	a4a	$F_c = 0.77$, $B_c = 466$	$F_{0.1} = 0.43$, $B_{pa} = 381.3$, $B_{lim} = 190.6$	$F/F_{ref} = 1.8$, $B/B_{threshold} = 1.22$, $B/B_{limit} = 2.45$	Biomass above reference point and in overexploita tion	Reduce fishing mortality	Update assessment with biomass reference points
7	12,13,14,15 ,16, 21w	Aristaeomorph a foliacea	JABBA			$F/F_{ref} = 1.52$, $B/B_{target} = 0.59$	Overexploit ed and in overexploita tion	Immediat e action to ensure a reduction in fishing mortality	Updated assessment ; STF available
8	18,19, 20	Aristaeomorph a foliacea	a4a	$F_c = 0.83$, $B_c = 352$	$F_{0.1} = 0.371$	$F/F_{ref} = 2.25$	In overexploita tion	Reduce fishing mortality	New assessment
9	8	Corallium rubrum	LBSPR				Possibly overexploit ed	Reduce fishing mortality	New assessment ; qualitative advice ($F/M = 3.16$)
10	11 (northwest ern waters)	Corallium rubrum	CMSY			$F/F_{ref} = 0.53$, $B/B_{target} = 0.37$	Overexploit ed with a low fishing mortality	Reduce fishing mortality and/or impleme nt a	New assessment

								recovery plan	
11	11 (northern waters)	Corallium rubrum	CMSY				Possibly overexploited and in overexploitation	Immediate action to ensure a reduction in fishing mortality	New assessment ; qualitative advice (F/Fref = 2.34, B/Btarget = 0.47)
12	17 (HRV)	Corallium rubrum	LBSPR				Possibly overexploited	Reduce fishing mortality	New assessment ; qualitative advice (F/M = 4.56)
13	22	Corallium rubrum	LBSPR				Possibly overexploited	Reduce fishing mortality	New assessment ; qualitative advice (F/M = 1.28)
14	18	Eledone cirrosa	CMSY-BSM			F/Fref = 0.79, B/Btarget = 0.77	Overexploited with a low fishing mortality	Reduce fishing mortality and/or implement a	Revised assessment

								recovery plan	
15	7	Lophius budegassa	a4a	$F_c = 0.69$	$F_{0.1} = 0.255$		In possible overexploitation	Reduce fishing mortality	New assessment ; qualitative advice
16	1,5,6,7	Merluccius merluccius	a4a	$F_c = 1.34, B_c = 1498$	$F_{0.1} = 0.41, B_{pa} = 7743, B_{lim} = 3872$	$F/F_{ref} = 3.27, B/B_{threshold} = 0.19, B/B_{limit} = 0.39$	Depleted and in overexploitation	Implement recovery plan	Updated advice with biomass reference points
17	1	Merluccius merluccius	XSA	$F_c = 1.49, B_c = 171$	$F_{0.1} = 0.24$	$F/F_{ref} = 6.21$	In overexploitation	Reduce fishing mortality	Complementary advice; relatively low biomass
18	3	Merluccius merluccius	a4a	$F_c = 1.70, B_c = 300$	$F_{0.1} = 0.44$	$F/F_{ref} = 3.86$	In overexploitation, with relatively low biomass	Reduce fishing mortality	Revised assessment
19	4	Merluccius merluccius	VIT	$F_c = 0.77$	$F_{0.1} = 0.23$	$F/F_{ref} = 3.34$	In overexploitation	Reduce fishing mortality	Updated assessment
20	5	Merluccius merluccius	a4a	$F_c = 1.28, B_c = 69$	$F_{0.1} = 0.34$	$F/F_{ref} = 3.77$	In overexploitation, with	Reduce fishing mortality	Complementary advice

							relatively low biomass		
21	6	Merluccius merluccius	a4a	$F_c = 1.24, B_c = 1024$	$F_{0.1} = 0.12$	$F/F_{ref} = 10.36$	In overexploitation, with relatively low biomass	Reduce fishing mortality	Updated complementary advice; revise growth parameters
22	8,9,10,11.1, 11.2	Merluccius merluccius	a4a	$F_c = 0.54, B_c = 4158$	$F_{0.1} = 0.167, B_{pa} = 11128, B_{lim} = 5564$	$F/F_{ref} = 3.22, B/B_{threshold} = 0.37, B/B_{limit} = 0.75$	Depleted and in overexploitation	Implement recovery plan	Updated benchmark assessment ; with biomass reference points
23	12,13,14,15,16	Merluccius merluccius	SS3	$F_c = 0.377, B_c = 5174.33$	$F_{msy} = 0.29, B_{msy} = 7021$	$F/F_{ref} = 1.3, B/B_{target} = 0.74$	Overexploited and in overexploitation	Reduce fishing mortality	Updated benchmark assessment . Current indicators are based on the average of the models of the last three years on a precautionary basis

24	17-18	Merluccius merluccius	SS3	$F_c = 0.39$	$F_{msy} = 0.23$	$F/F_{ref} = 1.7$	In overexploitation	Reduce fishing mortality	Updated benchmark assessment . Blim not considered plausible. Benchmark in need of an overhaul
25	19	Merluccius merluccius	a4a	$F_c = 0.34$	$F_{0.1} = 0.21$	$F/F_{ref} = 1.59$	In overexploitation with relatively high biomass	Reduce fishing mortality	Updated benchmark assessment with revised model
26	20	Merluccius merluccius	a4a	$F_c = 0.71, B_c = 1619$	$F_{0.1} = 0.133$	$F/F_{ref} = 5.34$	In overexploitation, with relatively intermediate biomass	Reduce fishing mortality	Update assessment showing consistent results with an assessment presented using different historical catch series

27	22,23	Merluccius merluccius	a4a	Fc = 0.92, Bc = 6524	F0.1 = 0.151	F/Fref = 6.09	In overexploitation, with relatively intermediate biomass	Reduce fishing mortality	New assessment ; showing consistent results with an assessment presented for GSA 22 alone but using different historical catch series
28	1	Mullus barbatus	a4a	Fc = 0.87, Bc = 406	F0.1 = 0.36	F/Fref = 2.4	In overexploitation, with relatively high biomass	Reduce fishing mortality	Updated assessment
29	6	Mullus barbatus	a4a	Fc = 1.42, Bc = 849	F0.1 = 0.25	F/Fref = 5.68	In overexploitation, with relatively high biomass	Reduce fishing mortality	Updated assessment
30	7	Mullus barbatus	a4a	Fc = 0.48, Bc = 755	F0.1 = 0.471, Bpa = 246, Blim = 123	F/Fref = 1.02, B/Bthreshold = 3.07, B/Blimit = 6.14	Biomass above reference point and in	Reduce fishing mortality	Updated assessment ; with biomass

							overexploita tion		reference points
31	9	Mullus barbatus	a4a	$F_c = 0.54, B_c = 1573$	$F_{0.1} = 0.5, B_{pa} = 923, B_{lim} = 461.5$	$F/F_{ref} = 1.08, B/B_{threshold} = 1.7, B/B_{limit} = 3.41$	Biomass above reference point and in overexploita tion	Reduce fishing mortality	Updated assessment ; with biomass reference points
32	10	Mullus barbatus	SPiCT			$F/F_{ref} = 0.24, B/B_{target} = 1.48$	Sustainably exploited	Evaluate potential fishing opportun ities	Revised assessment
33	11	Mullus barbatus	XSA	$F_c = 0.24, B_c = 638$	$F_{0.1} = 0.3$	$F/F_{ref} = 0.8$	Sustainably exploited, with relatively high biomass	Do not increase fishing mortality	New assessment
34	12,13,14	Mullus barbatus	XSA	$F_c = 1.51, B_c = 14593$	$F_{0.1} = 0.466$	$F/F_{ref} = 3.23$	In overexploita tion, with relatively low biomass	Reduce fishing mortality	Updated benchmark
35	15	Mullus barbatus	XSA	$F_c = 1.13, B_c = 13.47$	$F_{0.1} = 0.295$	$F/F_{ref} = 3.82$	In overexploita tion, with relatively low biomass	Reduce fishing mortality	Updated benchmark

36	16	Mullus barbatus	a4a	$F_c = 0.12, B_c = 1937$	$F_{0.1} = 0.42$	$F/F_{ref} = 0.29$	Sustainable exploitation, with relatively high biomass	Do not increase fishing mortality	New model, recommended for advice in view of a new benchmark assessment
	16	Mullus barbatus	XSA	$F_c = 0.57, B_c = 1041$	$F_{0.1} = 0.42$	--	--	--	Benchmarked model no longer recommended for advice
37	19	Mullus barbatus	XSA	$F_c = 0.53, B_c = 611$	$F_{0.1} = 0.38$	$F/F_{ref} = 1.39$	In overexploitation	Reduce fishing mortality	Updated benchmark assessment; a4a model also trialled but was not considered stable enough to provide advice
38	20	Mullus barbatus	a4a	$F_c = 0.4, B_c = 603$	$F_{0.1} = 0.3$	$F/F_{ref} = 1.33$	In overexploitation, with relatively	Reduce fishing mortality	Updated assessment

							high biomass		
39	22	Mullus barbatus	a4a	$F_c = 0.25, B_c = 6535$	$F_{0.1} = 0.29$	$F/F_{ref} = 0.86$	Sustainable exploitation, with relatively high biomass	Do not increase fishing mortality	Revised assessment with new sub-model settings
40	24	Mullus barbatus	CMSY in addition to LBB, and LBSPR			$F/F_{ref} = 0.92, B/B_{target} = 0.61$	Overexploited with low fishing mortality	Do not increase fishing mortality	Update assessment
41	25	Mullus barbatus	SAM	$F_c = 0.76, B_c = 27$	$F_{0.1} = 0.27$	$F/F_{ref} = 2.81$	In overexploitation, with relatively intermediate biomass	Reduce Fishing Mortality	Updated Assesment
42	5	Mullus surmuletus	a4a	$F_c = 0.5, B_c = 322$	$F_{0.1} = 0.243$	$F/F_{ref} = 2.06$	In overexploitation, with relatively intermediate biomass	Reduce fishing mortality	Updated assessment
43	5	Nephrops norvegicus	a4a	$F_c = 0.23, B_c = 33$	$F_{0.1} = 0.237$	$F/F_{ref} = 0.97$	Sustainably exploited, with relatively low biomass	Do not increase fishing mortality	Updated assessment

44	6	Nephrops norvegicus	a4a	$F_c = 0.44, B_c = 286$	$F_{0.1} = 0.14$	$F/F_{ref} = 3.14$	In overexploitation, with relatively low biomass	Reduce fishing mortality	Update assessment
45	9	Nephrops norvegicus	a4a	$F_c = 0.17, B_c = 403$	$F_{0.1} = 0.109, B_{pa} = 463, B_{lim} = 232$	$F/F_{ref} = 1.53, B/B_{threshold} = 0.87, B/B_{limit} = 1.74$	Overexploited and in overexploitation	Reduce fishing mortality immediately	Updated assessment ; with biomass reference points
46	17	Nephrops norvegicus	SS3	$F_c = 0.3, B_c = 592$	$F_{b40} = 0.418, B_{40} = 761$	$F/F_{ref} = 0.72, B/B_{target} = 0.78$	Overexploited with low fishing mortality	Reduce fishing mortality and/or implement a recovery plan	New assessment . STF should not yet be used. Stock overexploited (SSB below SSB40%). Explore use of commercial CPUE outside Pomo/Pit area.

47	1,3	Pagellus bogaraveo	gadget	$F_c = 0.26, B_c = 256$	$F_{msy} = 0.259, B_{pa} = 369, B_{lim} = 263$	$F/F_{ref} = 1.01, B/B_{threshold} = 0.69, B/B_{limit} = 0.97$	Depleted with unsustainable exploitation	Immediate reduction of fishing mortality and implement a recovery plan	Updated benchmark assessment . Needs a new benchmark session because of the likely change in the biomass index standardization procedures
48	1	Parapenaeus longirostris	a4a	$F_c = 1.32, B_c = 171$	$F_{0.1} = 0.74$	$F/F_{ref} = 1.78$	In overexploitation	Reduce fishing mortality	Update assessment without estimated 2020 index; relative high biomass
49	3	Parapenaeus longirostris	a4a	$F_c = 2.00, B_c = 87$	$F_{0.1} = 0.94$		In possible overexploitation	Reduce fishing mortality	New assessment ; qualitative advice

50	4	Parapenaeus longirostris	VIT	$F_c = 1.44$	$F_{0.1} = 0.57$		In possible overexploitation	Reduce fishing mortality	Update assessment ; qualitative advice
51	5	Parapenaeus longirostris	a4a	$F_c = 1.33, B_c = 97$	$F_{0.1} = 0.569$	$F/F_{ref} = 2.34$	In overexploitation, with relatively high biomass	Reduce fishing mortality	Revised assessment ; STF available
52	6	Parapenaeus longirostris	XSA	$F_c = 1.15, B_c = 335$	$F_{0.1} = 0.78$	$F/F_{ref} = 1.47$	In overexploitation, with relatively high biomass	Reduce fishing mortality	Updated assessment
53	8,9,10,11.1, 11.2	Parapenaeus longirostris	a4a	$F_c = 1.4, B_c = 872$	$F_{0.1} = 1.26, B_{pa} = 427.5, B_{lim} = 213.7$	$F/F_{ref} = 1.11, B/B_{threshold} = 2.04, B/B_{limit} = 4.08$	Biomass above reference point and in overexploitation	Reduce fishing mortality	Revised assessment including GSA 8 and a new maturity vector; with biomass reference points
54	22	Parapenaeus longirostris	a4a	$F_c = 1.95, B_c = 4026$	$F_{0.1} = 0.522$		In possible overexploitation	Reduce fishing mortality	Revised assessment with new

									catch data. Qualitative advice
55	25	Raja clavata	AMSY				Possibly sustainably exploited	Do not increase fishing mortality	New Assesment; qualitative advice (F/Fref = 0.15, B/Btgt = 1.91)
56	24	Saurida lessepsianus	LB-SPR				Possibly overexploit ed	Do not increase fishing mortality	New assessment validated; qualitative advice
57	17	Sepia officinalis	JABBA			F/Fref = 1.37, B/Btarget = 0.27	Overexploit ed and in overexploita tion	Immediat e action to ensure a reduction in fishing mortality	Revised assessment with a new model
58	17	Solea solea	SS3 ensemble			F/Fref = 0.75, B/Btarget = 0.86	Overexploit ed with low fishing mortality	Do not increase fishing mortality	Updated benchmark assessment
59	17	Squilla mantis	SS3	Fc = 0.32, Bc = 6600	Fb40 = 0.33, SSB40 = 6333	F/Fref = 0.96, B/Btarget = 1.04	Sustainably exploited	Do not increase	Updated assessment

								fishing mortality	
60	27 (Palestine)	Upeneus moluccensis	VIT	Fc = 0.95	F0.1 = 0.639		Possibly in overexploitation	Reduce fishing mortality	New assessment - qualitative advice